

**Inception of the Late Smithian (Early Triassic) Ammonoid Extinction:
A Taxonomical Revision of the Cosmopolitan *Anasibirites* Fauna**

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ABSTRACT

The Early Triassic is the time of a world struggling to recover from the most severe biodiversity crisis ever recorded in our geological past. The Permian-Triassic boundary mass extinction (*ca.* 252 Ma) caused the loss of about 81% marine species and the end of the Paleozoic marine world. Contrary to benthic organisms, whose recovery suffered a 5 Myr delay, nektonic organisms such as conodonts and ammonoid underwent their first diversification pulses already within the first 1.5 Myr after the extinction event. Ammonoids potentially reached diversity levels comparable to or higher than those of the Permian already 2 Myr after the Permian-Triassic mass extinction, and more than 200 genera were produced in less than 5 Myr. The biotic recovery that unfolded throughout the Early Triassic was however not a continuous process: it was interrupted at least once by the most severe extinction event of Triassic time that took place in the late Smithian. It was the first, most important ammonoid global extinction-diversification cycle after the end Permian extinction. It unfolded stepwise within the time span of 600 ky and it severely decimated nekto-pelagic organisms, though its causes have yet to be unravelled. The *Anasibirites/Wasatchites* ammonoid fauna defines the first step of the late Smithian extinction and it is characterised by cosmopolitan genera, although cosmopolitanism at the species level has yet to be assessed. This early late Smithian ammonoid fauna features a predominance of newly evolved prionitids, whose main genera include *Anasibirites* Mojsisovics, *Hemiprionites* Spath, *Wasatchites* Mathews, and the more rare *Xenoceltites* Spath. The high degree of intra- and interspecific variation typical of prionitids has led to a complex, typologically based taxonomy pervaded by a profusion of species and genera. In the frame of previous research that has tried to shed light on the biotic recovery of the Early Triassic, this thesis aims to give a thorough population-based taxonomical revision of the pivotal early late Smithian *Anasibirites* fauna. Our analyses are based on an exceptional collection of late Smithian prionitids from NE Nevada, and a smaller collection of late Smithian *Xenoceltites* from Spitzbergen. A taxonomical revision that takes into account intraspecific and ontogenetic variations can help achieve a better understanding of the actual extinction's intensity and of the cosmopolitan character of this fauna which in turn will create a solid base for future biostratigraphical studies.

In the first chapter of this thesis we focus on the species-level composition of the prionitids genera *Hemiprionites*, *Gurleyites*, and *Arctoprionites*. The 700 measurable specimens comprised in our dataset, alongside an even larger quantity of non-measurable material recovered from NE Nevada allowed us to implement biometric and geomorphometric-ontogenetic analyses as well as classical descriptive morphological studies. This in turn allowed us to synonymized *Arctoprionites* and *Gurleyites* with *Hemiprionites* and to reduce the early late Smithian *Hemiprionites* species to two species only: *H. typus* Waagen and *H. slocomi* Mathews. This reduction of *ca.* 90% of the available species names for these three genera, points to a more severe intensity of the first phase of the late Smithian extinction than previously assessed.

The second chapter of this thesis presents the rest of our Nevadian collection. Biometric and morphological analyses are here combined with an attentive comparison of our material with precedent work. The genus *Anawasatchites* McLearn is synonymised with *Wasatchites* Mathews and a first occurrence of *Aspenites* within

the *Anasibirites* fauna is reported. In addition, a new genus, *Eowasatchites*, is described from the base of the *Anasibirites* zone. Comparison of our material with specimens from both high and low latitudes from previous studies contributed to give new insights into the spreading of late Smithian cosmopolitanism at the species level, with most discussed species being recognized in both the Boreal and Tropical realm.

The third chapter of this thesis focuses on the genus *Xenoceltites* Spath. *Xenoceltites* is one of the cosmopolitan genera that developed in the aftermath of the late Smithian extinction. As such, it also holds fundamental importance for the development of accurate biostratigraphic correlations across paleolatitudes. Accurate correlations can only be achieved on the grounds of a robust taxonomy which, in the case of *Xenoceltites*, has been hindered by the lack of sufficiently big samples. This study aims to add to our current understanding of the genus by reporting an exceptionally well-preserved collection of *Xenoceltites* from Spitzbergen. This collection allowed us to confirm previously attempted synonymisations of Spath's original three species of *Xenoceltites* into a single one, *X. subevolutus* and to establish the cosmopolitan character of this species.

This chapter thus concludes the taxonomical review of the early late Smithian ammonoid fauna.

Keywords: Ammonoids, late Smithian extinction, taxonomy, cosmopolitanism, NE Nevada, Spitzbergen.

Introduction

AMMONOIDS

Ammonoids are a group of externally shelled cephalopods that originated in the Early Devonian from the Early Ordovician Orthocerida (Kröger & Mapes 2007) and became extinct at the end of the Cretaceous. They are considered to be excellent index fossils: their widespread occurrence allows intra- and interbasinal correlation of sections representing distinct depositional environments (e.g. Brayard *et al.*, 2013) and their overall distribution in time and space allows precise long-distance biostratigraphic correlations across paleolatitudes (Landman *et al.* 1996). Their high turnover rates often allow the construction of biozones spanning less than 100,000 years duration (e.g. House, 1985). Throughout their lifespan ammonoids underwent many adaptive radiations (Fig.1); the Triassic, in particular, was a time of consecutive episodes of intense radiation and extinction associated with abrupt biogeographic changes. Such shifting biogeographic patterns were often concomitant to severe climatic and oceanographic changes (e.g. Brayard *et al.* 2006, 2007a, 2009a, b, 2015; Monnet *et al.* 2013) although the link between ammonoid biogeographic patterns and climatic variables has not yet been fully unravelled (see Goudemand *et al.* 2019).

Figure 1: Total generic richness. Modified after Brayard *et al.* 2009c

EARLY TRIASSIC STRATIGRAPHY

Based on the radiometric ages of the Permian-Triassic boundary (PTB; ca. 252 Ma, Burgess et al. 2014; Baresel et al. 2017) and of the Early-Middle Triassic Boundary (ca. 247 Ma, Ovtcharova et al. 2015) the Early Triassic had a duration of approximately 5 Myr. Subdivisions into stages for this epoch commonly include either two (Induan and Olenekian; Kiparisova, L.D. & Popov 1956), three (Griesbachian, Nammalian, Spathian; Guex 1978) or four substages (Griesbachian, Dienerian, Smithian, Spathian; Tozer 1967, 1974; Brayard et al. 2006). In 1992 the Subcommission on Triassic Stratigraphy officially decided on the two-fold partitioning (Visscher 1992); however, the definition of the Induan-Olenekian boundary on a global scale is still controversial. In fact, the Olenekian type locality was defined in the Boreal realm, specifically in the Olenek Basin of northern Siberia while the original Induan stratotype was defined in the Tethyan domain of Salt Range (Pakistan; Kiparisova, L.D. & Popov 1956, see also Brühwiler et al. 2010b). Because the magnitude of the ammonoid turnover at the Induan-Olenekian boundary has been minor compared to that of other intra-Triassic events, and because the boreal realm is generally characterized by a very low carbonate content, which induces a considerable bias in the ammonoid record preservation, a definite stratigraphic correlation between the two geographic domains is yet to be achieved (Brayard et al. 2006; Ovtcharova et al. 2006, Krystyn et al. 2007a, b, Brühwiler et al. 2010b; Brosse et al. 2013). On the other hand, the boundaries of Tozer's (1967) fourfold subdivision are better defined with regard to both ammonoid and conodont events, which explains why Tozer's substages are more frequently used in most Lower Triassic research (e.g. Brayard et al. 2006; Ovtcharova et al. 2006; Brosse et al. 2013; this work). One of the main

Figure 2: modified after Dai et al. 2023. The age of the Induan-Olenekian boundary is based on sample CHIN40 (Galfetti et al. 2007d) according to the most recent calculations of Widmann et al. (2020). The age of the SSB is based on Widmann et al. 2020, while both the ages of the Permian-Triassic boundary and of the end Spathian are taken from the latest version of the ICS International Chronostratigraphic Chart (v2022/10).

weaknesses of the twofold stages subdivision is in fact its failure to capture the most severe intra-Triassic extinction event, the late Smithian extinction, which profoundly impacted nektonic organisms such as ammonoids and conodonts.

Calibration between zircon U-Pb radiometric ages and ammonoid zones has proven the four stages to be characterised by a very uneven duration: a maximal duration of 1.4 ± 0.4 Myr has been estimated for the Griesbachian-Dienerian stages, while the duration of the Smithian is estimated to 0.7 ± 0.6 Myr (Galfetti et al. 2007d). The Spathian stage amounts to at least half of the duration of the entire Early Triassic i.e. ca. 2.5 to 3 Myr (Ovtcharova et al. 2006; see also review of Zhang et al. 2019).

New precise U-Pb radiometric ages place the Smithian-Spathian boundary (SSB) between 249.29 ± 0.06 and 249.11 ± 0.09 Ma (Widmann *et al.* 2020).

Based on global ammonoids biostratigraphy recent works recognized further subdivisions within the Smithian/Spathian substages and divided them into early/middle/late subunits, which allows a much higher biostratigraphic resolution (Brühwiler *et al.* 2010a; Guex *et al.* 2010; Brayard *et al.* 2013, 2021; Jenks *et al.* 2015; Jattiot *et al.* 2017; Jenks & Brayard 2018; Dai *et al.* 2023). Figure 2 shows the main representative ammonoid genera for each substage, according to the attentive revision of Dai *et al.* (2023).

PALEOGEOGRAPHY OF THE EARLY TRIASSIC

The Early Triassic is characterised by a relatively simple and stable Pangean palaeogeography (Fig. 3). The large oceanic domain of Panthalassa constituted roughly 90% of the end-Permian ocean, while the remaining 10% was occupied by the Tethys ocean, centred on the Equator, entrenched within the crescent shaped Pangea and connected to the East with Panthalassa (Scotese & Schettino 2017).

Figure 3: Early Triassic Pangea. Courtesy of Christian Verard.

The Tethys is commonly subdivided into an older component known as the PalaeoTethys, which dates back to the Late Ordovician-Silurian when rifting of the northern Gondwana margin led to its opening (Stampfli *et al.* 1991; Stampfli & Borel 2002), and a younger constituent, the Neotethys. The latter originated following several rifting phases of the northern Gondwana margin in the Late Carboniferous/Early Permian all throughout the Triassic (Stampfli *et al.* 1991). Despite the simple Pangean palaeogeography of the time, there were also several microcontinents and terranes drifting across the Tethys and the Panthalassa towards convergence zones (e.g.

Nichols & Silberling 1979; Tozer 1982; Şengör 1984; Kojima 1989; Natal'in 1993; Parfenov *et al.* 1993; Belasky *et al.* 2002; Yancey *et al.* 2005; Scotese & Schettino 2017). The Cimmerian microcontinents were an almost continuous belt of continental blocks comprising today's Iran, parts of Afghanistan and Tibet and western Indochina and originated following the same rifting event that led to the opening of the Neotethys. After separating from the northern Gondwana margin these blocks started drifting northward within the Tethys, driven by the northward subduction of the Palaeotethys below the Eurasian margin, a subduction which caused the formation of various back-arc basins (Şengör 1979, 1984; Stampfli *et al.* 1991; Metcalfe 1996; Besse *et al.* 1998; Stampfli & Borel 2002). Drifting of the Cimmerian blocks culminated in their final accretion to the Siberia/Kazakhstan Asian area (Laurasia) by the end of the Triassic and led to the complete closure of the Palaeotethys ocean in Middle Triassic times (Metcalfe 1999; Stampfli & Borel 2002; Xu *et al.* 2015). Drifting on the eastern edge of the Tethyan domain in the Early Triassic, at an approximately equatorial position, was the Cathaysian microcontinent which included the South China block, most of Indochina and East Malaya (Şengör 1979, 1984; Metcalfe 1996, 1999; Xu *et al.* 2015). Finally, analysis of ammonoids assemblages brought evidence of a sub-equatorial position of the Chulitna Terranes (today's Alaska) on the western side of the Pangea and of an equatorial position of the South Prymorie terrane at the Tethys/Panthalassa interface (Nichols & Silberling 1979, Brayard *et al.* 2009b).

AMMONOID RECOVERY IN THE AFTERMATH OF THE END PERMIAN EXTINCTION

The Early Triassic (251.902-247.2 Ma; Cohen *et al.* 2013, updated) was a time of faunal recovery following the Permian-Triassic boundary mass extinction (PTBME, *ca.* 252 Ma; Burgess *et al.* 2014). The PTBME was the most severe extinction event ever recorded, most likely triggered by the eruption of the Siberian traps and its associated repercussions (e.g. Reichow *et al.* 2009; Svensen *et al.* 2009; see also Brayard & Bucher 2015). It caused the loss of 79% of marine invertebrate genera during the Changhsingian and an estimate of 81% marine species (Raup & Sepkoski Jr 1982; Payne & Clapham 2012; Stanley 2016). Most Paleozoic organisms such as trilobites, tabulate and rugose corals or brachiopods suffered a severe reduction in diversity or disappeared all together (Erwin 1994; Brayard & Bucher 2015). The PTBME brought the Paleozoic world to an end, allowing the expansion of new Mesozoic marine communities (Erwin 1994). The ensuing Early Triassic was characterised by a delayed biotic recovery for most organisms. It is widely accepted that the apparent delay of biological renewal reflects the persistently unfavourable environmental conditions that prevailed during that time (e.g. Payne *et al.* 2004; Goudemand *et al.* 2019; Widmann *et al.* 2020). Sedimentary, geochemical and palynological records suggest severe global changes in climate, sea-level and oceanic geochemistry (such as anoxia, euxinia or acidification) thus bringing support to a significantly unstable Early Triassic time (e.g. Payne *et al.* 2004, Galfetti *et al.* 2007c; Hermann *et al.* 2011, 2012; Romano *et al.* 2013; Hochuli *et al.* 2016; Goudemand *et al.* 2019; Widmann *et al.* 2020). Such severe environmental upheavals were reflected in the diversity fluctuations of nekto-pelagic organisms such as ammonoids and conodonts during the entire Early Triassic (Brayard & Bucher 2015). With regards to ammonoids, only a few ceratitid lineages survived the extinction: the genus *Otoceras*, which only lasted through the Griesbachian and is considered to be the last descendant of the Permian Araxoceratidae family; the genus *Proharpoceras*, an offshoot of the Late Permian Anderssonoceratidae; and the family Xenodiscidae

ancestral to most ammonoids of the Triassic order Ceratitida, which led Triassic ammonoids to be interpreted as a monophyletic clade (Tozer 1981a; Brayard *et al.* 2006, 2007b, a; McGowan & Smith 2007; Brayard & Bucher 2015). One Prolecanitid genus, *Episageceras*, is also reported to have survived the crisis (Tozer 1981a; Saunders *et al.* 2004; Brayard & Bucher 2015). Despite being among the organisms most affected by the end Permian extinction, research has shown that ammonoids recovered faster than many benthic groups (Brayard *et al.* 2006, 2009c, Brühwiler *et al.* 2010a). In fact, recovery of most benthic organisms was moderate during the Early Triassic and only accelerated at the beginning of the Middle Triassic, about 5 Myr after the PTBME (e.g. Hallam 1991; Senowbari-Daryan *et al.* 1993; Flügel 1994; Retallack 1995; Benton *et al.* 2004; Payne *et al.* 2004; Fraiser & Bottjer 2005; Hautmann 2007; Brayard & Bucher 2015; Hofmann *et al.* 2015; Grasby *et al.* 2016; Friesenbichler *et al.* 2021). In contrast, the first diversification pulses of nektonic organisms such as ammonoids (Brayard *et al.* 2006, 2009b, Brühwiler *et al.* 2010a) and conodonts (Orchard 2007) took place already within the first 1.5 Myr after the extinction event. Research suggests that ammonoids might have been the first marine invertebrates to fully recover by the middle Spathian (Brayard *et al.* 2006). Within 2 Myr after the PTB, ammonoid diversification had potentially already reached diversity levels comparable to or higher than those of the Permian and more than 200 genera were produced in less than 5 Myr, characterised by new biogeographical distribution patterns (Brayard *et al.* 2006, 2009c). The different recovery dynamics of nektonic and benthic groups are commonly associated to the higher interspecific competition characteristic of the nekton, as interspecific competition has been proven to constitute a main driver of diversification in the early stages of community restoration (Hautmann *et al.* 2015). However, it has also been suggested that the quick recovery of ammonoids' diversity may also result from ammonoids' ability to exploit a wide range of trophic resources and niches (Brayard *et al.* 2009b).

EVOLUTION OF AMMONOIDS THROUGHOUT THE EARLY TRIASSIC

Throughout their recovery in the Early Triassic, ammonoids went through various radiation and extinction phases. They were characterized by: i) a very low generic diversity in the Griesbachian. ii) A moderate increase of generic diversity in the Dienerian. iii) An explosive radiation at the beginning of the Smithian. iv) A severe stepwise extinction event at the end of the Smithian, which unfolded in the timespan of 600 ky (Widmann *et al.* 2020) and caused the largest ammonoid turnover of the Early Triassic. v) A following second explosive radiation in the Early Spathian (Brayard *et al.* 2006, 2009b). vi) A last significant, though less devastating, global decrease of generic diversity recorded at the Spathian-Anisian boundary (Brayard *et al.* 2006, 2007a, 2009b, c; Brosse *et al.* 2013). As opposed to Tethyan ammonoids, which reached their diversity peak during the Smithian, Boreal specimens seem to have reached the highest diversification level in the younger Spathian and were overall characterized by a lower diversification degree (Brayard *et al.* 2006). High turnover rates, i.e. intense restructuring of communities rather than accumulation of new taxa with high origination rates seem to have characterized the recovery during Smithian times (Brühwiler *et al.* 2010a).

To this generic diversification scenario is associated a prominent biogeographical structuring of faunas, which saw the Griesbachian stage characterized by a marked cosmopolitanism, followed by an increasing endemism in the Dienerian from which another short term cosmopolitan biogeographic distribution developed in the early Smithian. During the middle Smithian, a clear latitudinal diversity gradient starts developing, characterised by a

unimodal shape that shows an increase of diversity from high to low latitudes. This endemic distribution was then once again temporarily replaced by a cosmopolitan biogeographical pattern in the late Smithian, concurrent to the late Smithian extinction. After that, a marked level of endemism gradually emerged in the Spathian, characterized by an asymmetric bimodal character with a marked peri-Equatorial decrease of diversity and a relative higher boreal generic richness (Brayard *et al.* 2006, 2007a). This Early Triassic path toward recovery was also characterised by global changes in ammonoid morphological disparity, potentially reflecting ecological settings or environmental influences, such as climatic variations with its associated repercussions (Brosse *et al.* 2013). A high morphological disparity characterised by three extreme morphotypes was observed during the Griesbachian, which contrasts with the low generic richness of this time and may reflect a non-selective PTBME, which randomly affected the morphospace landscape. In the Dienerian, a contraction of the morphospace to the lowest disparity levels of the Early Triassic is observed, which stands in contrast with the rising generic richness and may indicate a constrained radiation related to environmentally driven ecological selectivity. From this time on, morphological expansion matches taxonomical diversification, with a broad morphological range observed during the early-middle Smithian taxonomic radiation, shifting to a severe loss of disparity concurrent to the late Smithian extinction and to a subsequent morphospace similar to that of early-middle Smithian in the Spathian, related to the origination of new taxa (Brosse *et al.* 2013).

THE SMITHIAN AND SPATHIAN TIME

As hinted by the numerous evolutionary trends visible from Early Triassic ammonoids, it is clear that the global recovery trend of the Early Triassic has been no continuous process. It was interrupted at least once in the late Smithian when the most severe intra-Triassic extinction event took place, in association with a brief episode of ammonoid cosmopolitanism. The intensity of this event is comparable to that of the PTBME and it severely decimated nekto-pelagic organisms such as conodonts and ammonoids (Brayard *et al.* 2006, 2009c; Orchard 2007). Only four species-poor ammonoid lineages survived: xenoceltitids (considered the probable ancestor of most of the Spathian taxa; Galfetti *et al.* 2007c), sageceratids, palaeophyllitids and proptychitids (Brayard & Bucher 2015). The causes of this extinction are still under debate. What has become clear so far, is that the Smithian and Spathian were times of extremely unstable and rapid climate changes observed on a global scale. They were characterized by pronounced carbon and oxygen isotopic excursions as well as by alterations of the net water balance between evaporation and precipitation (Payne *et al.* 2004, Galfetti *et al.* 2007c, a; Romano *et al.* 2013, 2016; Goudemand *et al.* 2019; Widmann *et al.* 2020). Studies have shown that the Smithian-Spathian boundary (SSB, ca. 249 Ma, Widmann *et al.* 2020) is distinguished by a global positive $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ excursion associated with a cooling event that started during the early late Smithian and peaked at the SSB, accompanied by a matching positive oxygen isotope peak measured in biogenic phosphate (Galfetti *et al.* 2007b; Romano *et al.* 2013; Goudemand *et al.* 2019; Widmann *et al.* 2020). Based on recent oxygen isotopic measurements from Salt Range (Pakistan) Goudemand *et al.* (2019) was able to reconstruct a clear picture of the evolution of climate throughout this time, which was characterised by 1) a cooling interval in the early Smithian; 2) a thermal maximum in the middle Smithian (contrary to Sun *et al.*'s (2012) assertion of a late Smithian Thermal Maximum) associated with a negative $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ shift (Romano *et al.* 2013; Song *et al.* 2013, 2014; Goudemand *et al.* 2019; Widmann *et al.* 2020)

and with warm temperatures persisting until the early late Smithian. 3) a second cooling interval in the late late Smithian-early Spathian, which likely culminated into a short ice age and a glacio-eustatic regression, as suggested by the presence of a global gap straddling the SSB in shelf environments (Hammer *et al.* 2019; Widman *et al.* 2020; Bucher H. ongoing work); 4) mid-Spathian temperatures comparable with those of mid-Smithian time; 5) renewed cooling around the late Spathian (Romano *et al.* 2013; Song *et al.* 2014; Goudemand *et al.* 2019; Widmann *et al.* 2020). In a previous study, through the aid of oxygen isotopes, Romano *et al.* (2013) detected a 4°C warming of seawater temperature building up towards the late Smithian in the Salt Range and a cooling trend developing at the base of the Spathian. Short-termed depositional breaks in the area prevented the authors from observing the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ pattern around the SSB. However, they could observe that the evolution of oxygen isotopes in the Salt Range positively correlates with the $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ record of the same region, which, in turn, parallels the carbon isotopes curves of other localities both in the Tethyan and Boreal realm (e.g. Galfetti *et al.* 2007b; Tian *et al.* 2014; Hansen *et al.* 2018). Horacek *et al.* (2007), for example, observed a matching carbon isotope trend in Italy, i.e. in the Palaeotethys, characterised by steep rise of $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ to positive values at the SSB, and the same carbon isotopes evolution was observed in South China by Tian *et al.* (2014) and Galfetti *et al.* (2007c), in the Arctic Canada by Grasby *et al.* (2013) as well as in the western US (Thomazo *et al.* 2016). Romano *et al.* (2013) thus concluded that oxygen isotopes from Salt Range paralleled climatic changes on a global scale. Palynological records brought further insights into the reconstruction of the Smithian-Spathian palaeoenvironment: a prominent spore spike was detected during the middle Smithian, while a shift from lycopod dominated vegetation to a gymnosperm dominated one was recorded during the late Smithian-early Spathian (Hermann *et al.* 2011). Proliferation of spores is usually linked to more humid conditions, while gymnosperms reflect a drier environment. Combined with oxygen isotopes data, this allows to infer a shift from prevailing warm-humid conditions in the middle Smithian, to cool arid conditions during the early Spathian, which developed into a more homogeneous climate throughout the Spathian (Galfetti *et al.* 2007b; Hochuli & Vigran 2010; Hermann *et al.* 2011; Romano *et al.* 2013; Hochuli *et al.* 2016; Widmann *et al.* 2020). Figure 4 sums up the evolution of global climate, sea-level and ammonoid diversity from the mid-Smithian to basal Spathian according to Widamnn *et al.* 's (2020) reconstruction. As previously noted, the SSB is characterized by a global sedimentary gap which was first observed in the Boreal latitudes, where it is made visible by peculiar truncated shape of the carbon isotope excursion (Hammer *et al.* 2019). Ammonoid age control indicates that the onset of this gap in the high paleolatitudes occurred earlier than in the Tropics (Hammer *et al.* 2019). In fact, while in the lower latitudes the late Smithian is distinguished by the older *Anasibirites* zone and the younger *Xenoceltites/Glyptophiceras* zone, the latter is missing from the higher paleolatitudes, which are characterized by the sole presence of the *W. tardus* zone (correlative of the low-latitudes *Anasibirites* zone). The diachronous character of the gap is possibly associated with the higher sensitivity of Boreal latitudes to temperature changes (e.g. Roots 1989): Boreal latitudes are in fact subjected to a quicker cooling, thus to a quicker decrease in precipitations when compared to low paleolatitudes. This would cause an earlier shut down of chemical weathering and its associated clastic sediment input. In combination with the depleted carbonate production proper of Boreal latitudes and its associated carbonate undersaturation, this would lead to a more extended sedimentary and fossil gap. In the low latitudes, on the other hand, prolonged warmer temperatures would sustain the production and accumulation of carbonate and siliciclastic sediments for a relative longer timespan, compared to the Boreal realm. In association with the

higher carbonate production levels and the sufficient carbonate oversaturation proper of the Tropics, this would then allow preservation of fossils throughout the *Glyptophyceras* zone in the Tropical realm. Once the climate had globally cooled enough to initiate ice formation, a eustatic sea level drop would have left sediments exposed causing a reduction of the nektonic niche and a consequent erosion of the sediments (Bucher H., work in progress). Unique tectonic settings have been observed in the Western USA Sonoma Basin: here the high subsidence and sedimentation rates compensated for the global eustatic sea level fall and thus for the associated hiatus, allowing the preservation of a new, still undescribed zone of late Smithian or (more likely) early Spathian affinity, which has so far been observed in NE Nevada only (Widmann et al. 2020; Bucher H., ongoing work; this work). While the causes of the late Smithian extinction have yet to be unravelled, it is clear that before the cooling would become strong enough to cause a glacio-eustatic sea level fall in association with an intense extinction event, various processes must have been at work. Possible mechanisms leading to the cooling may include silicate weathering with the contribution of the burial of organic carbon (the biological pump) as sinks for atmospheric CO₂, but research on this matter is still in progress (Widmann et al. 2020; H. Bucher, ongoing work).

Figure 4: Widmann et al. (2020)'s five-phase evolution of global climate, sea-level and ammonoid diversity from the mid-Smithian to basal Spathian.

GOALS OF THE Ph.D.

The main goal of this thesis is the revision of the taxonomy of ammonoids from the early late Smithian *Anasibirites*/*Wasatchites* zones. This fauna defines the first step of the late Smithian extinction (Widmann et al. 2020) and is characterised by a cosmopolitan character, which has been observed by previous work at the genus level (Tozer 1981b; Brayard et al. 2013). The development of a cosmopolitan biogeographic pattern predates the climatic shift from a warm middle to early-late Smithian to a cool late-late Smithian and early Spathian (Brayard et al. 2006; Goudemand et al. 2019; Widmann et al. 2020) and is thus likely associated to the opportunistic radiation of novel taxa following the release of biotic constraints that accompany extinction events (e.g. Button et al. 2017). Due to their largely typological taxonomy, ammonoid cosmopolitanism of the *Anasibirites* fauna at the species level has yet to be reassessed. The high degree of intra- and inter-specific variation of the late Smithian prionitids has made it difficult for taxonomists to separate prionitid taxa, which has led to an intricate taxonomy characterized by a profusion of species and genera (e.g. Tozer 1961, 1971, 1994; Piazza 2015; Brayard et al. 2020). A thorough taxonomical revision that takes intraspecific and ontogenetic variations into account (in the sense of the modern population-based approach to taxonomy) is thus fundamental in order to obtain a clear understanding of the extinction's intensity and assess how cosmopolitan late Smithian ammonoid genera and species were. It will hopefully also create a solid base for biostratigraphical studies to come.

Chapter I and II of this thesis rely on a large, well preserved ammonoid collection from north-eastern Nevada (Thaynes Fm.) which allowed the implementation of a quantitative, population-based approach based on classical descriptive morphology in combination with biometric analyses and geomorphometric ontogenetic analysis. Chapter III, on the other hand, is based on a smaller ammonoid collection from the high latitudes of Spitzbergen.

- Chapter I focuses on the taxonomical review of the three prionitid genera *Hemiprionites* Spath, *Arctoprionites* Spath and *Gurleyites* Mathews, which constituted the most abundant part of our collection and for which geomorphometric ontogenetic analyses could be implemented. This Chapter has been submitted to *Papers in Palaeontology*.
- Chapter II revises the remaining prionitid genera of the *Anasibirites* fauna, i.e. *Anawasatchites* McLearn, *Wasatchites* Mathews, *Anasibirites* Mojsisovics alongside other reported early late Smithian genera recovered in NE Nevada (such as *Subvishnuites* Spath and *Xenoceltites* Spath) and a new genus found in abundant quantities at the base of the *Anasibirites* horizon.
- Chapter III presents a new collection of *Xenoceltites* from the high latitudes of Spitzbergen, with the aim of adding to our (relatively poor) current understanding of this cosmopolitan late Smithian genus, through biometric analyses and attentive comparison with previous literature.

Both Chapters II and III are here presented ready for submission to the *Swiss Journal of Paleontology*.

While not directly related to the taxonomical revision of the late Smithian ammonoid fauna, Chapter IV constitutes an additional project that aims to contribute to our understanding of the biotic recovery of ammonoids in the aftermath of PTBME. This project was initiated in the Author's Master Thesis and it was perfected for publication throughout the course of this Ph.D. It is here presented ready for submission to *Biological Reviews*. This supplementary chapter presents an improved investigation of the global response of

ammonoids' body size through the Smithian and the Spathian climatic upheavals, discussing the results in a new light that takes into consideration biotic and abiotic factors that may have played a decisive role into controlling ammonoid body size evolution through this time.

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Chapter I

The late Smithian (Early Triassic) ammonoid extinction: revision of *Hemiprionites* Spath, *Gurleyites* Mathews and *Arctoprionites* Spath (Prionitidae) based on new data from north-eastern Nevada

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The late Smithian (Early Triassic) ammonoid extinction: revision of *Hemiprionites* Spath, *Gurleyites* Mathews
and *Arctoprionites* Spath (Prionitidae) based on new data from north-eastern Nevada.

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ABSTRACT

Along with conodonts, ammonoids were impacted deeply by the stepwise and global late Smithian (Early Triassic) nekton extinction. With the exception of one or (possibly) two xenoceltid genera, all other known late Smithian ammonoid genera belonged phylogenetically to the Prionitidae. Obtaining a clear understanding of this extinction's intensity requires thorough taxonomic revision of the late Smithian prionitids to clarify the number of valid genera and species. This clarification is also required prior to any assessment of how cosmopolitan late Smithian ammonoid genera and species were. Classically, late Smithian prionitid genera include *Wasachites*, *Anawaschites*, *Anasibirites*, *Hemiprionites*, *Gurleyites*, and *Arctoprionites*, all of which were defined, largely, on a typological basis. This study, focused on the species-level composition of the last three of these genera. Extensive collections from north-eastern Nevada (Thaynes Fm.) facilitated implementation of a quantitative, population-based approach, with emphasis on intraspecific and ontogenetic variation as described by Buckmann's Law of Covariation. In this task, we employed classic biometry, geomorphometry, and statistical analyses. Results suggest *Hemiprionites walcotti* Mathews, *Gurleyites smithi* Mathews, *Arctoprionites resseri* Mathews and *Arctoprionites nodosus* Frebold be regarded as synonyms of *Hemiprionites typus* Waagen, and the re-instatement of *Hemiprionites slocomi* Mathews. As a result, *Arctoprionites* and *Gurleyites* are synonymized with *Hemiprionites* which now contains only two species: *H. typus* Waagen and *H. slocomi* Mathews. With a reduction of c. 90% of the available species names for these three genera, the intensity of the first phase of the late Smithian extinction appears much more severe than assessed previously.

Key words: late Smithian extinction, Northeast Nevada, *Hemiprionites*, *Gurleyites*, *Arctoprionites*, intraspecific variation.

The intricate taxonomy of Hemiprionites Spath, Arctoprionites Spath and Gurleyites Mathews

The genus *Hemiprionites* Spath, 1929, is one of the six prionitid genera that classically make up the early late Smithian ammonoid fauna (c. 249.5 Ma; Widmann et al. 2020), alongside *Anasibirites* Mojsisovics, *Gurleyites* Mathews, *Arctoprionites* Spath, *Wasatchites* Mathews, and *Anawasatchites* McLearn. The oldest prionitids typically occurred during the middle Smithian and include the following genera: *Prionites* Waagen, *Meekoceras* Hyatt, *Stephanites* Waagen, and *Punjabites* Brühwiler and Bucher (see Brühwiler et al. 2012a). None of these survived into the late Smithian and all late Smithian prionitids were newly evolved, perhaps with the single exception of middle Smithian *Hemiprionites roberti* (see Jenks et al., 2010). Higher taxa crossing the middle-late Smithian boundary, i.e. the onset of the late Smithian extinction, are restricted to prionitids, and the long ranging sageceratids, palaeophyllitids and proptychitids. As palaeophyllitids and proptychitids re-appeared from the early Spathian they obviously were present in the late Smithian as virtual lineages.

The early late Smithian fauna, commonly referred to as the *Anasibirites/Wasatchites* Zone, defines the first step of the late Smithian extinction (Widmann et al. 2020). The causes of the extinction remain subjects of debate (e.g. Goudemand et al. 2019; Widmann et al. 2020). The entire step-wise late Smithian extinction spanned c. 600 kyr (Widmann et al. 2020) and severely decimated nekto-pelagic organisms (Orchard 2007; Brayard et al. 2006). The late Smithian collapse of ammonoid taxonomic richness was accompanied by the emergence of cosmopolitanism in this clade, at least at the genus level. This move toward cosmopolitan geographic distributions predated the climatic shift from a warm middle to early late Smithian to a cool late Smithian and early Spathian (Brayard et al. 2006; Goudemand et al. 2019; Widmann et al. 2020). Late Smithian cosmopolitanism had been observed first within the *Anasibirites/Wasatchites* Zone at the genus level (Tozer, 1981; Brayard et al. 2013). However, due to their largely typological taxonomy,

ammonoid cosmopolitanism at the species level has yet to be reassessed on the basis of intraspecific variation before processes underlying cosmopolitan distributions can be addressed. Tozer (1994) described the early late Smithian fauna as reflecting an 'arbitrary' taxonomy. According to his previous observations on 300 specimens collected from a single bed, 'no two specimens are alike' (Tozer, 1994, p. 78). Tozer suggested that most species were linked by forms representing transitional morphologies and suspected most named species were 'morphotypes of a smaller number of unusually variable species' (Tozer, 1994, p. 78). Thereafter, compilations of the primary literature without taxonomic reassessment also introduced a bias in the interpretation of the origin of the late Smithian cosmopolitanism, even at the genus level (e.g. Dai & Song, 2020). Such literature-based compilations also influenced estimates of extinction intensity, especially when dealing with low diversity faunas. The intergrading morphology of early late Smithian prionitids had also been noticed by Spath (1934) who assigned them to a single family. The high degree of intra- and inter-specific variation displayed by the prionitids has led to an intricate taxonomy characterized by a profusion of species and genera, most likely being synonyms when seen in the light of Buckman's Law of Covariation (Westermann 1966).

To this day the genera *Hemiprionites* Spath, *Arctoprionites* Spath and *Gurleyites* Mathews remain objects of taxonomic controversy. The genus *Hemiprionites* was first erected by Spath, 1929, renaming what had been defined initially as *Goniodiscus typus* Waagen, 1895. The lectotype of the latter became *Hemiprionites* Spath's (1934) genotype and holotype, though its poor preservation and small size later gave rise to doubts regarding this genus' validity (see Tozer 1961, p. 72). Among the original nine species Mathews' (1929) assigned to *Goniodiscus*, Brayard & Bucher (2008) synonymized all but *H. walcotti* and *H. butleri* with the type species, *H. typus*, while also erecting a new species, *H. klugi*. The more recent analysis of Jattiot et al. (2017), however, further synonymized *H. butleri* with the type species and *H. klugi* with *H. walcotti*. Two additional species of

Hemiprionites are also to be found in Spath (1934): *H. timorensis* and *H. garwoodi*. Both Piazza et al. (2015) and Brayard et al. (2020) tentatively synonymized the latter with *Arctoprionites nodosus* (Frebald 1930), while the former was synonymized with *H. walcotti* by Brayard et al. (2020). This left only two current species to be recognized widely within this late Smithian genus: *H. typus* (Waagen 1895) and *H. walcotti* (Mathews 1929). *Hemiprionites shimizui*, a further species of *Hemiprionites*, was mentioned by Bando (1964), but is apparently known only from Japan and is based on poorly preserved material. Lastly, *H. roberti*, was erected by Jenks et al. (2010), though it is apparently restricted to the uppermost middle Smithian.

The genus *Arctoprionites* was established by Spath (1930) for the Arctic *Goniodiscus nodosus* (Frebald, 1930). Similarities between smoother variants of this species and *H. typus* had been already noticed by Frebald (1930), leading him to assign this species to the same genus as *H. typus* (i.e., *Goniodiscus*). Not only could Frebald find no substantial difference between the suture lines of the two species, he also pointed to their similar biometric parameters, ventral crenulation and occasional minute depression visible on the outer edge of the flanks of both forms. In addition, Frebald (1930) noted that the radial folds of *G. nodosus* resembled those characteristic of *H. typus*. Spath (1930) later assigned *Goniodiscus nodosus* to a different genus, i.e. *Arctoprionites*, but with no clear justification (see Spath 1930, p. 86). Until Brayard et al. (2020), two *Arctoprionites* species were recognized: the arctic form *A. nodosus* (Frebald, 1930) and the western American form *A. resseri* (Mathews, 1929, originally designated as *Kashmirites resseri*), typical of lower latitudes. A third species, *A. williamsi* (Tozer, 1994) was synonymised with *A. resseri* by Jenks & Brayard (2018).

Gurleyites, the third genus considered herein, was established by Mathews (1929). It was temporarily rejected by Smith (1932) as its morphology resembled that of ‘a typical *Goniodiscus*’ (Smith, 1932 p. 76), but was reinstated by Spath (1934) who regarded it as transitional between *Anasibirites* and *Wasatchites*. To our knowledge, aside from sparse mentions in later research reports (e.g. Kummel, 1957 in Tozer 1961, p. 70; Tozer, 1961; Wang and

He, 1976) no in-depth analysis of this genus had been conducted until that of Brayard et al. (2020). These authors synonymized all *Gurleyites* species erected previously (to be found in Mathews, 1929; Spath, 1934 and Wang and He, 1976), as well as *Arctoprionites resseri*, with the type species *Gurleyites smithi*. In addition, they reassigned *A. nodosus* (the remaining *Arctoprionites* species) to *Gurleyites*, thus suppressing the genus *Arctoprionites*.

A population-based approach

The brief historical overview given in the previous paragraph summarizes the difficulties ammonoid taxonomists faced in separating prionitid taxa (e.g. Tozer 1961, 1971, 1994; Piazza et al. 2015; Brayard et al. 2020). Tozer (1961 p. 72; 1971 p. 999) stated his conviction that *Hemiprionites* Spath could be a spurious genus: ‘[...] The type species [...] is small and not particularly well preserved. Some ‘species’ (e.g. *H. timorensis* Spath) are linked by continuous contemporary transitional forms, with *Anasibirites*. Some of the Utah *Hemiprionites* described by Mathews (1929) may represent the young of *Gurleyites*. It is possible that all *Hemiprionites* are either the young of other, distinctively sculptured Prionitidae, or conservative variants, revealing the characters of the ancestral Meekoceratidae’. Furthermore, Tozer (1971, p. 999) noted that species which include a large variety of ‘*infrasubspecific variants*’ can only be defined and recognized when the full range of variation is evident in a single assemblage of coexisting ammonoids. This view is consistent with what is referred to today as a population-based approach to taxonomy.

A taxonomical population approach (*sensu* Monnet et al. 2010; see also Tozer 1961, 1971) rests on the idea that most living species are characterized by intra-specific morphological variation of different intensity, which is thought to be reflected by a continuous Gaussian distribution between end-member variants (Monnet et al. 2010). This contrasts with widespread use of the *typological* approach, in which species are defined on the basis of few individuals that show the most morphological similarities. Some of the variation now assigned to the intra-specific level of

ammonoids has customarily been treated as being relevant only above the species-level. The implicit goal behind such typological over-splitting is maximization of biostratigraphic resolution, as this was the case in earlier phases of ammonoid palaeontology. But acceptance of the typological approach comes at the expense of an accurate representation of intrinsic variation in natural assemblages. Therefore, a population-based approach is likely to lead to synonymization of many typologically defined species (Monnet et al. 2010).

With regard to ammonoids, Buckman's First Law of Covariation (Westermann 1966) requires an assessment of intra-specific variation, and can only be recognized readily via access to large samples (Monnet and Bucher 2005; Monnet et al. 2010). Ammonoid intra-specific variation has been detected in many studies (e.g. Silberling 1959; Silberling & Nichols 1982; Dagens & Weitschat 1993; Hammer & Bucher 2005; Monnet & Bucher 2005; Monnet et al. 2010; see also Morard & Guex 2003, p. 7608, tab. 1 for further examples) and ranges from slender, involute, compressed and weakly ornamented forms to robust, more evolute, depressed forms with coarser ornamentation (Westermann 1966). According to Monnet et al. (2005), robust variants are generally more suited for identifying the diagnostic features of a species since slender variants tend to converge towards similar and less informative smooth shapes in phylogenetically closely related species or subclades. Of course, description of intra-specific variation is crucial for correct taxonomical assignment (Monnet et al. 2010).

Heterochrony represents another source of intraspecific variability in ammonites, as has been noted in numerous studies (e.g. Schmidt 1926; Dommergues 1986; Mitter 1990; Beznosov & Mitter 1995; Courville & Cronier 2003; Baudouin et al. 2011, 2012; Bersac & Bert 2012). This refers to the shifting of the succession of developmental stages (paedomorphosis or peramorphosis), duration of growth and rate of growth between ancestor and descendant species or between specimens of the same species (Gould 1977; Alberch et al. 1979; McNamara 2012; see also Dommergues 1986; Dommergues and Meister 1989; Mitter 1990; Bersac and Bert 2012). Schmidt (1926) observed this

phenomenon in Carboniferous ammonoids, and proposed the terms bradymorphic and tachymorphic to designate individuals of a species that retain characteristics of juvenile morphologies later in the ontogeny (i.e. retarded development, more commonly referred to as paedomorphic forms; e.g. Baudouin et al. 2012) or that present traits proper of later ontogenetic stages early in their development (i.e. accelerated development, more often referred to as peramorphic forms; e.g. Baudouin et al. 2012). According to Mitter (1990, p.10) and Beznosov and Mitter (1995) paedo- and peramorphic trends between specimens of the same size are observed in the duration of developmental stages of the shell sculpture. Extreme end-member variants can differ from typical states of the species so strongly that they might be mistaken for different species in a sparse sample or assemblage. In fact, most of the intra-specific shape variation induced by heterochrony is a by-product of variable growth rate as documented by Urdu et al. (2010a,b) in living gastropods.

The aim of this study is to clarify the fuzzy taxonomy of *Hemiprionites* Spath, *Arctoprionites* Spath and *Gurleyites* Mathews. Our extensive collection of specimens (c. 700 measurable specimens) from different localities in northeastern Nevada, allowed the implementation of a quantitative, population-based approach, with emphasis on intraspecific and ontogenetic variation. Biometric analysis, geomorphometric ontogenetic analysis as well as classical descriptive morphology were implemented with the aim of sorting out this taxonomic conundrum.

GEOLOGICAL SETTING

Paleogeographical context

The Sonoma Foreland Basin (SFB) is a pull-apart basin, located within an active tectonic margin resulting from the emplacement of the Golconda allochthon during the Sonoma Orogeny around the time of the Permian-Triassic boundary (Dickinson 2013; Ingersoll 2019; Caravaca et al. 2017). In the Early Triassic this basin was at a near-equatorial position on the western margin of Pangea (Fig. 1). Presently, basinal deposits extend from eastern

Figure 1: Early Triassic Pangea showing the paleoposition of the Sonoma Basin. Courtesy of Christian Verard. Modified after Edward et al. 2023.

Nevada, to Utah, Idaho and parts of Wyoming (Dickinson 2006, 2013; Caravaca et al. 2017). Regional maximal onlap of the Thaynes Group was reached in the late Smithian (Carr & Paull 1983; Paull & Paull 1993; Lucas et al. 2007; Brayard et al. 2013, 2015, 2020, 2021), during the late Smithian *Anasibirites-Wasachites* and *Xenoceltites-Glyptophiceras* zones. Late Smithian fossiliferous strata occur both in stratigraphically and laterally continuous series (e.g. Palomino Ridge, Jattiot et al. 2017) as well as in tongues of reworked carbonate blocks wedging in the base of the Spathian dark shales. These wedges are related to extensional or transtensional block faulting which is especially dense in the Crittenden Springs area. On uplifted blocks, the base of the Thaynes Fm. consists typically of dark shales of earliest Spathian age that rest unconformably upon the eroded upper boundary of the Dienerian Dinwoody Fm. This unconformity is underlined by a centimetric accumulation of iron oxides that suggests emersion. The few Dienerian ammonoids found a couple of meters below this unconformity indicate both late and middle Dienerian ages, suggesting differential uplift and subaerial erosion of the Dinwoody Fm. All Smithian ammonoids from this area are found within reworked blocks embedded in decametric to hectometric tongues of polygenic breccia resulting from intense synsedimentary block faulting and associated subaerial erosion and brecciation during the early Spathian (BH, pers. obs.).

Localities and facies description

Smithian marine deposits of the Sonoma Foreland Basin belong to the Lower Triassic Thaynes Group, that represents relatively shallow epicontinental depositional areas (Brayard et al. 2013, 2020, 2021; Olivier et al. 2018). They extend over a large area that covers parts of Wyoming, Idaho, Utah and Nevada, thinning from northwest to southeast across Utah, where they interfinger with the terrestrial Moenkopi Group (Lucas et al. 2007; Brayard et al. 2013).

The Thaynes Gp. (*sensu* Lucas et al. 2007) includes both Smithian and Spathian substages that are renowned for exceptional ammonoid succession or for occasional mass occurrences of ammonoids (see Kummel & Steele 1962; Brayard et al. 2009a; Guex et al. 2010; Jenks 2007; Jattiot et al. 2017; Jenks et al. 2010, 2013; Jenks and Brayard 2018; Stephen 2010). All Smithian ammonoids from the Crittenden Spring area, inclusive of our collection, were recovered from middle and late Smithian heterometric limestone blocks that have been reworked and redeposited in submarine wedges during the early Spathian age. Although imbrication of shells can be observed locally in these blocks, no evidence of storm deposits was found. Preservation varied from block to block and also across the different layers of a single block, suggesting changing early diagenetic conditions. Many beds were characterized by dense shell accumulations indicating mechanical current sorting. Polished

slabs cut perpendicular to the bedding plane of heterometric blocks revealed frequent minor erosional discontinuities. However, direction of geopetal structures was consistently normal, with no shell overturned as would be expected from reworking. A few blocks showed some beds of middle Smithian age with discrete signs of early dolomitization and discrete in situ brecciation. Although all the Thaynes Fm. rocks were locally affected by thermal alteration, strata of late Smithian age are commonly darker than the light grey to yellowish middle Smithian strata, suggesting an increasing content of organic matter during the late Smithian.

Samples were collected by H. Bucher and R. Jattiot from locations in the area of Silver Creek (SIL 119, SIL 83, SIL 62, WIL 1, WIL 2, WIL 4, WIL 6, WIL 10, WIL 11, WIL 100) and Crittenden Springs (CS 33, see Fig. 2). The *Anasibirites-Wasatchites* zone is usually thin (max. 30 to 40 cm), consisting of dark grey, micritic limestone packed with occasionally imbricated shells. If middle and late Smithian ammonoid-bearing carbonate blocks are all characterized by moderate to low sedimentation rates, none of them presented indications of internal reworking that would lead to biostratigraphic contradictions when compared to extended sections in other parts of the basin. The resulting picture of the middle and late Smithian depositional environments, as documented from these 'exotic' blocks, is that of carbonate shoals swept by currents, sampling a broad array of shallow to moderate water depth. We also noted that a majority of the carbonate ammonoid-bearing facies in Crittenden Springs area had a much lower siliciclastic fraction (or none at all) when compared to expanded Smithian records exposed in a more southerly part of the basin (e.g. Palomino Ridge, Jattiot et al. 2017).

Figure 2: Northeastern Nevada with locations of the sections from which our specimens were collected.

METHODS

Measurements and biometry

Our material consists of 720 well-preserved specimens collected from the *Anasibirites-Wasatchites* Zone in northeastern Nevada. It is worth mentioning that the number of specimens retrieved and prepared is at least twice as large as the number that could actually be measured and considered for biometric analyses. Crushed or partly flattened, less well-preserved specimens could, however, still provide valuable information for the descriptions.

Specimens were first split into empirical morphological groups (i.e., morphs) based on overall shell geometry and strength of ornamentation. Morph groups were then compared statistically. Biometric analyses were based on the standard linear measurements of the ammonoid shell, i.e., shell diameter (D), whorl height (H), whorl width (W) and umbilical diameter (U). To determine how these parameters vary within and across the groups, they were plotted as ratios of the diameter (H/D, W/D, U/D) in order to eliminate the influence of growth (Monnet et al., 2010). The ratios H/W and H/U were also calculated to quantify aspects of whorl compression and involution throughout ontogeny. Morph groups

were then compared in order to quantify between-group differences.

Normality plots and growth analysis

Normality of the classical geometric parameters was statistically tested via the Shapiro-Wilk test (see e.g. Hammer & Harper 2006; Ghasemi & Zahediasl 2012). This test can be applied to sample sizes as small as 3 (Hammer & Harper 2006) and still be sensitive to outliers (Leu et al. 2018). Conformance and/or deviation from normality was also inspected visually by means of probability plots. Allometric growth patterns of each parameter was tested by means of linear models implemented both on the bulk of samples and on single ontogenetic curves taken from each morph (see Appendix, Chapter 1 for a detailed description of the implemented statistical procedure).

LDAs and PCAs

Linear discriminant analysis (LDA, see Xanthopoulos et al. 2013) was used to assess how and if morph groups could be discriminated on the basis of the calculated ratios (H/D, W/D, U/D, H/W). An LDA quantifies between-group differences by maximizing the separation of group centroids relative to within-groups dispersion. The linear discriminant vectors produced by this process were then combined to create multidimensional discriminant spaces into which individuals — as represented by their measured ratios — can be projected. This analysis also ranks the discriminant axes in order of their ability to represent variation among the group-specific centroids: LD1, the first axis created, accounts for the greatest amount of variation between group centroids, LD2, the next greatest, etc. For each discriminant vector/axis, the weighting coefficients of each variable indicate the unique contribution of each ratio in contributing to group identification.

Due to the very high intraspecific variation characterizing our samples, a principal component analysis (PCA) was also implemented in order to further explore patterns of form covariance. In this context the PCA was used to reduce dimensionality of our data, thus facilitating its efficient analysis. A key difference between the LDA and PCA

approaches is PCA operates on the pooled covariance/correlation matrix. Therefore, while the first axis created by the LDA (LD1) attempts to maximize the separation of the groups, the first principal component (PC1) accounts for the direction of variation within the dataset as a whole without taking any account of the existence or composition of morph groups. For our PCA the ratio data were first normalized to have unit variance, to ensure all variables were weighted equally in the analysis (see also Hammer & Harper 2006).

It is worth mentioning that both LDA and PCA are ‘descriptive and explorative methods’ that do not hold any statistical significance in themselves (Hammer and Harper 2006, p. 87). As such, irrespective of the character of our measured ratios’ distributions, the representation of between-morph group (LDA) and between-specimen (PCA) patterns of variation using linear models can reveal such patterns and assist in their interpretation. If a linear model can identify stable group differences correctly despite the data being non-normal, as is often the case with palaeontological data, such analyses can also serve to test the hypothesis that taxonomic groups defined previously exist and can be distinguished. If, on the other hand, the LDA and PCA models are unable to identify groups, this would *not* necessarily or definitively speak to the issue of whether the groups in question exist. Such a result could also indicate that i) linear models are not sufficient to quantify group differences or ii) that the variables measured do a poor job of representing the between-group differences that do exist (Monnet C. personal communication).

Ontogeny

For groups represented by numerous specimens, individual ontogenetic curves were traced from radial cross sections of the conch. Linear models were then implemented on semilandmark data representing these ontogenetic series to test for allometry. Morphological ontogenetic development was also checked by partly removing the outer whorls in order to expose earlier whorls of selected specimens.

Morphometric analyses

Once tracings of the conch's cross-section had been obtained, a geometric morphometric analysis was performed on the radial cross sections in order to better quantify ontogenetic shape transformations. Two approaches to the quantification and modelling of ontogenetic trajectories were implemented: one based on form representation by a sparse set of two-dimensional (2D) landmark point locations and the other based on a combination of landmarks and outline semilandmarks under the extended eigenshape sampling protocol (MacLeod 1999; see Fig. 3). For the landmark dataset the coordinate positions of fourteen two-dimensional (2D) landmark points were collected from the tracing of each specimen's ontogenetic sequence as documented by the inner conch whorls. These points specified the conch's general form at each growth stage, including the position of the umbilicus, diameter of the umbilicus (as two umbilical radii), shape of the umbilicus (difference between umbilical radii), position and length of the maximum lateral extent of the ultimate and penultimate whorl section, and position and length of the chord defined by the umbilicus and venter for both the ultimate and penultimate whorl sections. Taken together, these landmark coordinates not only contain all information collected traditionally in ammonite

morphometric studies using linear-distance variables – including ontogenetic investigations (e.g. Dera et al. 2010; Kutugin & Knyazev 2017) – but preserve an accurate, geometric representation of how all parts of the shell quantified by these landmark coordinates relate to one another.

In addition to these landmark data, the precise shape of each specimen's outline at each stage of its ontogenetic sequence was also quantified via a collection of both landmark and semilandmark outline coordinates. These coordinates were obtained from the set of raw, 200-step digitized outlines by using four landmark locations (umbilicus location on right and left side, ultimate whorl venter, penultimate whorl venter, see Fig. 3) to divide the cross-section outline into four segments. Each segment was then evaluated to determine how many equally-spaced semilandmark point locations were necessary to represent the geometry of the segment curve to an accuracy ratio of 0.99 (see MacLeod 1999, 2012 for details of this procedure). After evaluation it was determined that the profile of the ultimate whorl could be represented by 48 equally spaced semilandmark points (24 semilandmarks per side) and that of the penultimate whorl by 38 equally-spaced semilandmark points (19 semilandmarks per side) with the two umbilical landmarks being common parts of both ultimate and penultimate whorls and two venter landmarks occupying medial

Figure 3: Landmarks and semilandmarks used to quantify morphological variation of the different morphs through ontogeny. The 2D coordinates of 14 landmarks (red icons) were collected (left) to quantify the position of the umbilicus and gross shapes of the ultimate and abultimate chambers. The coordinates of 4 landmarks (red icons) and 86 semilandmarks (blue icons) were collected for the outline dataset (right) to quantify the form of the entire shell profile through ontogeny.

positions on the ultimate and penultimate whorls between the left and right sequences. In total, 90 coordinate points were used to quantify the ontogenetic sequence of these outlines.

Since the shape sampling density was so great — especially for the first few outlines in each species' ontogenetic sequence, semilandmark sliding (to positions of minimum bending energy) was unwarranted as the spatial scope for adjustments in this regard was so limited. Semilandmark sliding is problematic in a number of additional ways (both theoretical and practical, see MacLeod 2015) all of which were avoided by foregoing use of this somewhat exotic procedure. Collection and analysis of these outline data ensured that our analysis could include accurate representations of the actual shapes of these specimens in addition to the somewhat approximate shapes recorded by the landmark data.

Following collection and, in the case of the semilandmarks, interpolation of these data, the landmark and semilandmark datasets were aligned using the generalized, least-squares Procrustes approach (see Rohlf and Slice 1990) with centroid size estimates and set of shape coordinate being saved to different datasets. Ordinations of the landmark and outline shape configurations were obtained via Procrustes PCA (Zelditch et al. 2012; MacLeod 2017).

RESULTS

Identified morphological groups

Empirical morphological observation suggests four main morphs exist in our sample (see Figs 4-13). These are distinguishable mainly on the basis of their umbilical shape and/or strength of conch ornamentation. The first morph is similar to *Hemiprionites walcotti* (Mathews 1929; hereafter termed the *walcotti* morph). It is chiefly discernible on the basis of a narrow umbilicus, as well as a smooth and generally more compressed conch (Figs 4 and 5A-E). Mechanical preparation revealed smooth inner whorls (Figs 4AJ-AM and 5A-E).

A second morph, hereafter referred to as *nodosus* morph, was identified as bearing a marked resemblance to *Arctoprionites nodosus* (Frebald 1930) and to *Gurleyites smithi* (Mathews 1929). Its

most noticeable morphological feature is the presence of a more-or-less prominent, radially elongated bullae on the outer whorls along with an evolute umbilicus (Figs 10-12). Ontogenetic preparation uncovered some specimens bearing megastriae (see Fig. 12A-C) on their otherwise smooth inner whorls (Fig. 12D-Q). While the *walcotti* morph is the slenderest, most involute and smoothest of the morphs within our sample, the *nodosus* morph stands on the opposite end of the morphological variation spectrum, being the most robust, most evolute and most strongly ornamented morph.

A third morph was identified as conforming to the type species of *Hemiprionites*, i.e., *Hemiprionites typus* (see Fig. 5F-AK and Figs 6-9). Its most prominent characteristic is a remarkably variable ornamentation, ranging from weak folds, to slightly prominent ribs, sometimes faintly crossing the venter and creating a crenulated effect on its surface (see Figs 6U-W and 7U-W). Moreover, the *typus* morph has a more evolute umbilicus than the *walcotti* morph and is generally more involute than the *nodosus* morph (though intraspecific variation of umbilical diameter between the last two groups largely overlaps). This places *typus* between the *walcotti* and *nodosus* morphs. The absence of bullae is the main criteria for distinguishing the *typus* morph from the *nodosus* morph. Just as was the case for the *nodosus* morph, mechanical preparation of the inner whorls revealed the presence of megastriae in the inner whorls of some specimens (Fig. 9A-T). In rare cases, megastriae seem to persist to larger sizes (Fig. 9D-G). When megastriae are absent, inner whorls are smooth (Fig. 9U-Z), and cannot be differentiated from the inner whorls of the *nodosus* morph.

Our last morph was distinguished on the basis of its very shallow umbilicus that exposes the inner whorls and its peculiar compressed conch that exhibits a flat and almost bicarinate venter (Fig. 13). The morphology of this group bears a strong resemblance with *H.* (i.e. *Goniodiscus*) *slocomi* that was erected by Mathews (1929). It is hereafter referred to as the *slocomi* morph. Only five specimens were assigned to this morph category.

Figure 4: *Hemiprionites typus*. Walcottii morphs. A-C PIMUZ 39031, loc. SIL83; D-G: PIMUZ 39032, loc. SIL119; H-J: PIMUZ 39033, loc. SIL119; K-M: PIMUZ 39034, loc. WIL4; N-O: PIMUZ 39035, loc. SIL83; P-R: PIMUZ 39036, loc. SIL119; S-T: PIMUZ 39037, loc. SIL83; U-W: PIMUZ 39038, loc. SIL83; X-Z: PIMUZ 39039, loc. SIL119; AA-AC (x0.5): PIMUZ 39040, loc. WIL6; AD-AF (x0.5): PIMUZ 39041, loc. SIL83; AG-AI (x0.5): PIMUZ 39042, loc. SIL119; AJ-AM (x0.5): PIMUZ 39043, loc. SIL119. Scale bar: 1cm

Figure 5: *Hemiprionites typus*: Walcott morph. A-E (X0.5): PIMUZ 39044, loc. SIL83. Typus morph : F-G (X0.5): PIMUZ 39045, loc. WIL10; H-J: PIMUZ 39046, loc. SIL83; K-M: PIMUZ 39047, loc. WIL6; N-P (X0.5): PIMUZ 39048, loc. WIL10; Q-S: PIMUZ 39049, loc. WIL4; T-V: PIMUZ 39050, loc. SIL83; W-Y: PIMUZ 39051, loc. SIL119; Z-AB: PIMUZ 39052, loc. WIL6; AC-AE: PIMUZ 39053, loc. WIL6; AF-AH: PIMUZ 39054, loc. WIL6; AI-AK: PIMUZ 39055, loc. SIL83. Scale bar: 1cm

Figure 6: *Hemiprionites typus*: Typus morph. A-B: PIMUZ 39368, loc. SIL119; C-E: PIMUZ 39369, loc. SIL119; F-H (X0.5): PIMUZ 39370, loc. SIL119; I-K: PIMUZ 39371, loc. SIL119; L-N: PIMUZ 39372, loc. CS33C; O-Q (X0.5): PIMUZ 39373, loc. SIL119; R-T: PIMUZ 39374, loc. SIL119; U-W: PIMUZ 39375, loc. SIL119. Scale bar = 1cm.

Figure 7: *Hemiprionites typus*. Typus morph. PIMUZ 39376, loc. WIL6; D-F: PIMUZ 39377, loc. SIL119; G-H: PIMUZ 39378, loc. SIL119; I-K (X0.5): PIMUZ 39379, loc. SIL119; L-N(X0.5): PIMUZ 39380, loc. SIL119; O-Q: PIMUZ 39381, loc. WIL6; R-T: PIMUZ 39382, loc. SIL83; U-W: PIMUZ 39383, loc. SIL119; X-Z: PIMUZ 39384, loc. SIL119; AA-AC: PIMUZ 39385, loc. SIL119; AD-AE(X0.5): PIMUZ 39386, SIL119; AF-AH(X0.5): PIMUZ 39387, loc. SIL119. Scale bar: 1cm

Figure 8: *Hemiprionites typus*. Typus morph. A-C(x0.5): PIMUZ 39388, loc. SIL119; D-F: PIMUZ 39389, loc. WIL10; G-I: PIMUZ 39390, loc. WIL6; J-L: PIMUZ 39391, loc. SIL83; M-O (X0.5): PIMUZ 39392, loc. WIL6; P-Q: PIMUZ 39393, loc. SIL119; R-S: PIMUZ 39394, loc. SIL119; T-U: PIMUZ 39395, loc. SIL119; V(X0.5): PIMUZ 39396, loc. SIL119; W-Y(X0.5): PIMUZ 39397, loc. SIL119; Z-AB: PIMUZ 39398, loc. SIL119; AC-AD: PIMUZ 39399, loc. SIL83; AE-AF(X0.5): PIMUZ 39400, loc. SIL119; AG-AH: PIMUZ 39401, loc. WIL6. Scale bar: 1cm

Figure 9: *Hemiprionites typus*. A-T: Typus morph showing megastriae in the inner whorls: A-C: PIMUZ 39402, loc. SIL119; D-G: PIMUZ 39403, loc. SIL119; H-K(X0.5): PIMUZ 39404, loc. SIL119; L-N: PIMUZ 39405, loc. SIL119; O-Q: PIMUZ 39406, loc. SIL119; R-T: PIMUZ 39407, loc. SIL119. U-Z Typus morph without megastriae in the inner whorls: U-W(X0.5): PIMUZ 39408, loc. SIL83; X-Z (X0.5): PIMUZ 39409, loc. SIL119. Scale bar: 1cm

Figure 10: *Hemiprionites typus*. Nodosus morphs A-C: PIMUZ 39066 loc. SIL119; D-E: PIMUZ 39067, loc. SIL119; F-H: PIMUZ 39068, loc. SIL83; I-K(X0.5): PIMUZ 39069, SIL119; L-N(X0.5): PIMUZ 39070, WIL6; O-Q: PIMUZ 39071, loc. SIL119; R-S(X0.5): PIMUZ 39072, loc. SIL119; T-V: PIMUZ 39073, loc. SIL119; W-Y(X0.5): PIMUZ 39074, loc. SIL119; Z-AA: PIMUZ 39075, loc. SIL119. Scale bar: 1cm

Figure 11: *Hemiprionites typus*. Nodosus morphs. Notice the intra specific variance of the bullae shape. A-C: PIMUZ 39076, loc. SIL83; bullae are the most pronounced around/shortly before mid flank. D-E: PIMUZ 39077, loc. SIL83; bullae start in early ontogenetic stages and are the most pronounced on the umbilical margin and fade away on the flanks. F-H; PIMUZ 39078, loc. SIL119; bullae keep the same intensity along the flank. I-L: PIMUZ 39079, loc. SIL119. Scale bar: 1cm

Figure 12: *Hemiprionites typus*: inner whorls of nodosus morphs. A-C: PIMUZ 39080, loc. SIL119. Despite the outer whorl ornamentation being similar to spec. O-Q, this specimen shows megastriae in its inner whorls. Following specimens show smooth inner whorls without megastriae. D-F: PIMUZ 39081, loc. SIL119; G-J: PIMUZ 39082, loc. SIL83; K-N: PIMUZ 39083, loc. SIL119; O-Q(X0.6): PIMUZ 39084, loc. WIL1. Scale bar: 1cm.

Figure 13: *Hemiprionites slocomi*: A-C: PIMUZ 39085, loc. SIL83; D-F: PIMUZ 39086, loc. SIL83; G-I: PIMUZ 39087, loc. WIL4. Scale bar: 1cm

Biometry

As it can be observed from Fig. 14, intraspecific variation of the *typus* morph overlaps with that of all other morphs identified here for all the parameters considered. Only in the case of the H/U ratio can a difference be documented: Figure 14H shows the *walcotti* morph to generally have the highest H/U ratio of all morphs (exceptions relate to different egression), while both the *slocomi* and *nodosus* morphs display the lowest H/U ratios, reflecting the more evolute umbilicus common to both groups. From Figure 14E, 14F and 14H, it is clear that the *nodosus* morph shows a degree of umbilical variation that overlaps strongly with that of the *typus* morph. Separation between the *walcotti* and *nodosus* morphs is also shown in Fig. 14E and confirmed by Figure 15F-H, where the curves depicting the ontogenetic growth of *nodosus* show a clear departure from those of the *walcotti* morph. The red curve in Fig. 15 represents a specimen of the *typus* morph (Fig. 9H-K), whose inner whorls bear megastriae. This curve reveals that (at least some) megastriae-bearing specimens maintain a more evolute shape throughout ontogeny, compared to smooth specimens of the same morph (black curve in Fig. 15E, F, H), and have even lower H/U ratios than those of the *nodosus* morph (Fig. 15H). The scatterplot of U/D as a function of D (Fig. 14F) matches the findings of Jattiot et al. (2017), where the U/D ratio of the

species recognized as *H. walcotti* is shown to oscillate mostly beneath a value of 0.1, as opposed to that of *H. typus* which generally fluctuates above that value. In short, Fig. 14 shows that the classic biometric parameters and their ratios allow only the *walcotti* and *nodosus* morphs to be distinguished. Both groups, however, overlap more-or-less strongly (depending on the parameter) with the *typus* morph, and each is found to grade into the *typus* morph from the two opposites ends of the *typus* morphological spectrum. Boxplots (see Fig. 16) provided further insights into the biometry of these four morphs. With exception of W/D, the other variable/ratio boxplots did not exhibit high degrees of overlap. Based on H/D, U/D and H/W all four groups displayed different distributions. Specimens assigned to the *walcotti* morph in our sample are here shown to have the highest H/D ratios and to include the most compressed and involute morphologies (i.e., highest H/W and lowest U/D). Specimens assigned to the *nodosus* morph, on the other hand, encompassed the most depressed conch morphologies (lowest H/W), while those assigned to the *typus* morph occupied an intermediate position between the *walcotti* and *nodosus* variation fields. Both the *nodosus* and *slocomi* morphs exhibited the highest U/D values, which confirms these to be the most evolute of the four morphs in our sample.

All sections

Figure 14: Scatter diagrams of the parameters for each considered morphs. D, shell diameter; H, whorl height; W, whorl width; U, umbilical diameter. Walcott and nodosus morphs exhibit a clear separation, while the typus morphs overlaps with the range of intraspecific variation of all other groups.

Figure 15: Ontogenetic curves of 10 specimens from the three main morphs (walcotti, typus, nodosus).

Figure 16: Boxplots of the variable ratios for each morph. Each box spans the interquartile range, from the lower (i.e. 25th percentile) to the upper (i.e. 75th percentile) quartile (Ghasemi and Zahediasl, 2012). The vertical line across the box indicates the position of the median of each distribution. Horizontal lines (whiskers) at both ends of the box indicate the variability of data outside the identified quartiles and connect the data within the box to the extreme, outermost values that are not distant enough to be considered outliers (Frigge et al., 1989). Points at the end of the whiskers represent outliers. Numbers next to each box indicate the amount of specimens included within the box. Note that the *walcotti* morph has the highest H/D ratio and includes the most compressed and involute morphologies (i.e., highest H/W and lowest U/D). The *nodosus* morph, on the other hand, includes the most depressed conch morphologies of all species (lowest H/W), while *typus* morphs spans the gap between these two morphs. The *nodosus* and *slocomi* morphs are the most evolute (highest U/D values).

Figure 17: Probability plots of each variable ratio for each considered morph, with linear trendness that indicate the extent to which the ratio distributions conform to normality.

Linear models and normality tests

Appendix tables A1.1 to A1.2 show results of ordinary least squares linear regressions performed on each parameter in order to determine their growth pattern (isometric/allometric). Tests reported in Table A1.2 were performed on ontogenetic curves of selected specimens from each morph (except *slocomi*; see Fig. 15), while test results reported in Table A1.1 were implemented on the bulk of specimens. Appendix Chapter 2 includes a detailed discussion of these results. Results obtained from the linear regressions performed on the ontogenetic curves (our most reliable evidence, see Appendix) suggest isometric growth for H, U and W parameters of all three morphs. On the other hand, whorl compression (H/W) and degree of involution (H/U) seem to have remained constant through growth for all morphs (with the exception of the *walcotti* morph, which shows a slightly allometric growth pattern in H/W). Distributions of the different parameters did not always exhibit normality. Figure 17 shows the probability plots for our sample with indication of the distributions that conform to normality (according to the Shapiro-Wilk test under a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$). Outliers were concentrated in the upper and lowermost quantiles (caused presumably by juvenile plasticity and egressive coiling of the shell at mature stages) and seem to be the most obvious cause for the occasional deviations from the normal model.

LDA and PCA analyses

Our LDA results (Fig. 18) show a clear distinction between the *walcotti* and *nodosus* morphs, and also between *nodosus* and *slocomi* morphs. The *typus* morph overlaps with all groups, in agreement with the previous analyses. Patterns of variation within these data is expressed almost entirely by the first discriminant axis (LD1), with all LD1 coefficients of the linear discriminant functions carrying similar weights, with the exception of H/W (Table 1).

Further, our LDA results are confirmed by our PCA analysis (Fig. 19). The first PC axis (PC1) accounts for most (60%) of the variation within the data (Fig. 20A). Figure 20B-C provides a graphic visualization of the contribution of each variable to each component. On PC1 W/D shows the lowest loading while all other parameters were assigned similar loadings (note the comparable size of the circles in Fig. 19B). From the PCA scatterplots (Fig. 19) it can be further observed that all data plotted in a single space with no groups being evident on the first three PCA axes. By colour-coding the points of the PCA scatterplot according to our recognized four morphs, it can be noted that the *walcotti* (black) and *nodosus* morphs (red) are mostly grouped on opposite sides with respect to the *typus* morph (blue), and do not exhibit any overlap. The *typus* morph, on the other hand, is scattered across the entire morphospace and overlaps with both the *walcotti* and *nodosus* morphs. Overall, both in the LDA and the PCA results, the *walcotti* and *nodosus* morphs exhibited a clear separation from each other. However, neither of these analyses managed to achieve a complete separation with regard to the other morphs, thus confirming the strongly intergradational character of intraspecific variation in these groups.

Figure 18: Scatter plots of the linear discriminant analysis showing the amount of separation of group centroids in the eigenvalue-scaled space relative to within-group variation. Separation is expressed almost entirely by the first axis (LD1). *H. typus* overlaps with all groups while a separation can be observed between *nodosus* and *walcotti* morphs.

Coefficients of linear discriminants:			
	LD1	LD2	LD3
H/D	22.713756	-94.71326	-140.11892
W/D	-25.135644	169.20963	274.39373
U/D	-23.393227	-24.74147	10.94688
H/W	-2.993895	19.19143	42.43745
Proportion of trace:	0.9206	0.0737	0.0057

Table 1: LDA loadings (weights) on the three linear discriminant functions calculated from the variable ratio data.

Figure 19: Scatterplot of the space defined by A) the first two principal components and B) the three principal components of the variable ratio data with specimens coloured according to the identified morphological groups. Note in Fig. A the walcotti and nodosus morphs groups form distinct fields of variation along the axis (PC1) that represents the direction of greatest pooled-groups variation.

Figure 20: Results of the variable-ratio data PCA. A) Scree plot of the eigenvalues associated with each principal component vector expressed as a percentage of pooled-sample variation. Note the first 2 principal components account for most of the variation. B) and C) represent graphic summaries of the weights assigned by the PCA to each ratio variable. B) Size of the circles indicates the absolute contribution of each parameter to the variation of the data, while colours give a rough approximation of their values. C) Plot of direction of the cosine values expressing the angular relation of each ratio variable to the first two principal components. The colours of the circles in B) and the direction of the arrows in C) show that PC1 score increases with an increase in H/W and H/D, and decreases with decreasing U/D and W/D.

Morphometric analyses

According to our landmark based-morphometric analysis, all specimens have comparable shapes at all ontogenetic stages (notice the absence of outliers in Appendix Fig. A2A). Figure 21 documents the character of shape variation along the axes of the covariance-based PC space for the first few eigenvector axes. The predominant shape-variation mode (PC1) involves a change toward slightly larger whorl height, with shapes projecting to negative positions along this axis (Fig. 22A-B) being the most vertically compressed; i.e., the least elongated. The subdominant patterns of shape variation expressed on both PC2 and PC3 involve an increased degree of whorl compression with increasingly positive values (Fig. 21 and Fig. 22C-D). From this representation, however, it is evident that these changes within our sample are, in fact, minimal in their relative degrees of development.

Within the representation of ontogenetic changes summarized in Figure 22, both *walcotti* morph specimens maintained a more elongated height (e.g. higher PC1 scores) throughout ontogeny (see Fig. 22A). Specimen PIMUZ39042 is the most involute of the two *walcotti* specimens and

maintains a more compressed (i.e., higher PC2 scores) shape throughout growth (Fig. 22A). The ontogenetic shape curve of *walcotti* specimen PIMUZ39092 resembles those of the *typus* morph with the exclusion of specimen PIMUZ39404. Specimen PIMUZ39404 has the coarsest ornamentation of the *typus*-morph specimens selected for this analysis and is the only specimen that exhibited megastriae in its inner whorls (see Fig. 9H-K). Its ontogenetic curve is more comparable to those of the *nodosus* morph (e.g. the curve of specimen PIMUZ39093). All *nodosus* morph specimens exhibit a more depressed (thicker) shape throughout ontogeny (e.g. lower PC2 scores; Fig. 22A,C,E) with most of their ontogenetic stages trending towards the negative range of PC1 (Fig. 22A,B,E), hence toward exhibiting less elongated shapes. Figures 22B to D document a high plasticity of juvenile stages for all morphs. Along PC1 (Fig. 22B) a clear trend towards lower whorl height can be discerned in all specimens, with the exclusion of the last stage of the most involute *walcotti* specimen (PIMUZ39042). Scores on PC2 (Fig. 22C) also document a general trend towards increased whorl depression, once again with the exception of the last whorl of specimen

Figure 21: Landmarks used to represent ontogenetic shape changes in ammonoids' conch morphology with landmark displacement vectors associated to the first three covariance-based Procrustes PCA eigenvectors of the pooled shape-covariance matrix. For each diagram the landmark configuration shown represents that of the lowest projected eigenvector score on the axis in question with the displacement-vector tips indicating direction and relative amount of landmark displacement at the highest eigenvector projected score. Displacement-vector lengths have been exaggerated by a factor of 3.0 to make the pattern of along-axis shape variation obvious. Note distinctly different patterns of shape variation represented by each of these multivariate shape axes.

Figure 22: Ontogenetic shape-variation pathways for 9 specimens of the 3 representative morphs (*typus*, *walcotti*, *nodosus*) based on the pooled Procrustes PCA of the landmark dataset. A) Shape variation in the subspace formed by the first two Procrustes PCA eigenvectors. Note that, in these results the *walcotti* morphotype exhibits greater ultimate chamber elongation normal to the coiling axis (= higher PC-1 scores) and greater compression parallel to the coiling axis (= higher PC-2 scores) relative to the other two morphotypes. B-D) Ontogenetic form-variation within the space formed by the modes of shape variation represented by projected landmark-configuration scores on PC-1 (B), PC-2 (C) and PC-3 (D) and centroid size variation. E) Ontogenetic form-variation pathways plotted in the 3D space formed by the dominant mode of conch shape variation (PC-1), centroid size and whorl number.

PIMUZ39042 which is relatively less depressed than those of previous ontogenetic stages and relative to the last ontogenetic stage of all other specimens. Outline-based morphometric analysis yielded results comparable to those of the landmark-based analysis. In this case as well, all ontogenetic stages of all specimens exhibit highly similar shapes with no outliers evident (Appendix Fig. A3A). Figure 23 documents the predominant aspect of outline-based variation in our sample. PC1 contrasts slender, more elliptical whorl sections (corresponding to negative scores along the PC1 axis in Fig. 24A-B) and more subtrapezoidal whorl sections (corresponding to positive scores along the PC1 axis in Fig. 24A-B). The second PC axis, on the other hand is focused on shape changes in the vicinity of the ventral shoulders, or more generally, of the higher half of the shell flanks (Fig. 23). Specimens with more rounded ventral shoulders and more inflated upper half of the flanks project to score positions along the positive range of this axis (in Fig. 24B-C). Finally, PC3 focused on changes of the overall convexity of flanks (Fig. 23), with positive values representing progressively increased degrees of shell convexity (Fig. 24D-E). Figure 24A documents a dominant growth trend from a highly variable, but overall subtrapezoidal, whorl section in the juvenile stages (negative

scores) toward a more elongated ellipsoidal whorl section of the mature stages (positive scores). A slight positive trend can be observed along PC2 (Fig. 24C), indicating weak development of more broadly rounded ventral shoulders with growth. No obvious trends can be seen along PC3 (Fig. 24E) which indicates constant convexity of the flanks, with a prominent convergence of the more mature whorls (as in PC1). The PC1 vs PC2 plot (Fig. 24B) shows that no linear trend between these two patterns of shape variation was evident, and that the dominant/subdominant aspects of shape variation they capture do not differ strongly from one another. Finally, the PC2 vs. PC3 plot (Fig. 24D) suggests a generally constant convexity of the flanks (slightly oriented towards decreasing convexity in mature stages) was retained along PC3 combined with a tendency towards more rounded ventral shell shoulders with growth.

Figure 23: Landmarks (white icons) and outline semilandmarks (black icons) used to represent ontogenetic shape changes in *Hemipriorites conch* morphology with displacement vectors associated to the first three covariance-based Procrustes PCA eigenvectors of the pooled shape-covariance matrix. Landmarks were used to separate the overall outline into four outline segments and ensure topological correspondence across all specimen outlines at these locations (see MacLeod, 1999). For each diagram the landmark configuration shown represents that of the lowest projected eigenvector score on the axis in question with the displacement-vector tips indicating direction and relative amount of landmark displacement at the highest eigenvector projected score. Displacement-vector lengths have been exaggerated by a factor of 3.0 to make the pattern of along-axis shape variation obvious. Note distinctly different patterns of shape variation represented by each of these multivariate shape axes as well as the more complete and geometric representation of shape variation compared to the landmark dataset (compare with Fig. 11).

Figure 24: Ontogenetic shape-variation pathways for 9 specimens of the 3 representative morphs (*typus*, *walcotti*, *nodosus*) based on the pooled Procrustes PCA of the outline landmark-semilandmark dataset. A) Ontogenetic form-variation pathways within the space formed by projected landmark-configuration scores on PC-1 and centroid size variation. B) Shape variation in the subspace formed by the first two Procrustes PCA eigenvectors. C) Ontogenetic form-variation pathways within the space formed by projected landmark-configuration scores on PC-2 and centroid size variation. D) Shape variation in the subspace formed by the Procrustes PCA eigenvectors 2 and 3. E) Ontogenetic form-variation pathways within the space formed by projected landmark-configuration scores on PC-3 and centroid size variation.

Buckman's law of covariation

Figure 25: Plots giving a visual representation of Buckman's First Law of Covariation. Note how the walcotti and nodosus morphs occupy the extreme ends of the distributions shown in (A) and (B), while typus covers the whole range. The plots show walcotti to be the more slender (A, C, D) and the more involute (C) of the morphs, with the largest H/U ratio (B), i.e. the largest height (B,D). Nodosus is more robust (A,D) and more evolute (B and C) and has the lowest H/U ratio (B), i.e. the smallest height (B,D). These patterns are all consistent with the predictions of Buckman's First Law.

DISCUSSION

Recognized species

Of the four morphs considered only *slocomi* shows morphological differences that, as a group, distinguishes its 5 specimens from all others. In the rest of our sample a complete range of conch geometries intergraded with respect to all measured variables. This pattern conforms to the continuous morphological spectrum predicted by Buckman's Law of Covariation (see Fig. 25). From

the slender, involute, compressed and weakly ornamented forms of *walcotti*, to the robust, more evolute, bullate forms of the *nodosus* morph, all possible intermediates linking the end-variants of this spectrum can be found within our sample for the data we have collected. Morphological, biometric and morphometric analysis all support our view that any attempt to discriminate different species within this continuum on the basis of these characters, dimensions and landmark locations would result in an entirely arbitrary and subjective division. Therefore, we find that two species only

can be distinguished in the early late Smithian (Anasibirites – Wasatchites Zone): *Hemiprionites typus* (Waagen) and *Hemiprionites slocomi* (Mathews).

The name assigned to *H. slocomi* is the one of Matthews' resurrected species, which had been synonymized previously by Brayard and Bucher (2008) with *Hemiprionites typus*. Although the data we collected (Fig. 14) exhibit an overlap with the type species, the morphological traits of its sulcate (almost bicarinate) venter, its pear-shaped cross section and its shallow umbilicus revealing all younger whorls, set it apart from all other specimens, thus justifying its revised status as a separate species.

On the other hand, *H. typus* includes the three main modes of morphological variation previously referred to as *H. walcotti*, *H. typus* and *H. nodosus*. These form a gradient of increasing morphological variation — depression and tuberculation — that can be observed in our boxplot summaries (Fig. 16). The highest H/D and H/W and lowest U/D ratios of *walcotti* put this morph on the one side of the spectrum as the slender, more involute end-variant of this species, almost consistently devoid of ornamentation. On the opposite end, *nodosus* shows the expected lowest H/W and highest U/D typical of the robust and more evolute end-variant predicted by Buckman's Law. The *typus* morph stands in between these two as the average and more common form that includes all the transitional morphologies in between the two extremes. Histograms of the whorl compression and degree of involution (Fig. 25A, B) provide a graphical visualization of Buckman's Law as seen in our data: our sample spans a unimodal distribution, with *walcotti* and *nodosus* being, for the most part, on opposite ends. Scatterplots (Fig. 14, and Fig. 25C-D) also support an interpretation of continuous intra-specific variation of a single species as suggested by the high degree of overlap of *typus* with all other morphs. In agreement with these observations, neither the PCA nor the LDA of the ratio variables revealed the presence of any morphological discontinuities, and cluster analyses applied to the PCA scores only yielded two potential clusters, most likely reflecting the presence of the extreme end-member variants (*walcotti* and *nodosus*). Finally, morphometric analyses of both

geometric landmarks and outlines also did not identify any significant ontogenetic distinctions between these different morphs. While much plasticity was observed in the shapes of the juvenile whorls, mature whorls all tended towards a similar elliptic cross section with rounded ventral shoulders and flat to slightly convex flanks. Our landmark-based analyses showed that the most involute variants of the *walcotti* morph retained the highest whorl height through growth (higher PC1 values, Fig. 22B), while *nodosus* was characterised by more depressed whorls (lower PC2 values, Fig. 22C) with lower whorl height (Fig. 22B), once again, in agreement with Buckman's First Law of Covariation.

Morphological overview of *Hemiprionites*

Based on our observations and analyses, *H. typus* now includes a wide spectrum of morphologies characterized by a tabulate-to-subtabulate venter, moderately compressed conch, subrectangular cross section, a moderately small and deep umbilicus and highly variable ornamentation. It now includes the former species *H. walcotti* as well as the robust and more evolute morphologies referred to previously as *Gurleyites smithi* (*sensu* Brayard et al. 2020) and *Gurleyites* (formerly *Arctoprionites*) *nodosus*. Synonymization of *G. nodosus* with *Hemiprionites typus* supports Frebold's (1930) original placement of *Arctoprionites nodosus* and *Hemiprionites* into the same genus. These more robust morphologies are characterized by coarse, sinuous ribs that may, or may not, develop bullae. Variation in shape and developmental stage of appearance and disappearance of bullae is often observed. Most bullae originate above the umbilical shoulders to become especially prominent near the mid-flank and then fade on the outer flank (Fig. 10T-AA, Fig. 11A-C; Fig. 12D-F, M-Q;). Other specimens exhibit projected bullate ribs that are elongated along the entire flank with the same strength (Fig. 10 O-Q; Fig. 11F-H; Fig. 12A-C). Some specimens exhibit bullae originating from the umbilical margin and fading along the flanks to leave only a slight crenulation along the venter (see Fig. 10F-H; Fig. 11D-E, I-L; Fig. 12K-N). On others a few bullae only are barely visible in lateral view (Fig. 10A-K, R-V; Fig.

12G-J). The ontogenetic stage at which bullae appear seems highly variable. In some instances, bullae show signs of development already in the earlier ontogenetic stages and then fade away on the later whorls (Fig. 11D-E) while, in others, they develop on more mature whorls (Fig. 10A-E, T-AA; Fig. 11A-C; Fig. 12D-J).

Intraspecific variation

From our sample it seems intraspecific variation across these species is driven by two main factors: the morphological variance predicted by Buckman's Law (horizontal variance), and difference in timing, duration or growth rate of the various ontogenetic stages (vertical variance or developmental slack). Several developmental phases can, in fact, be observed, connected by intergrading morphologies. These ontogenetic phases differ mainly on the basis of their sculpture, along the lines observed previously by Mitta (1990) and Bersac & Bert (2012).

1. Phase 1: Specimens exhibit morphological characteristics of the *walcotti* morph and could range up to .ca 70 mm in diameter (e.g. Fig. 5A-E).
2. Phase 2: Specimens exhibit a less compressed and slightly more evolute umbilicus than in Phase 1, with a lower H/D ratio, but still show no sculpture (e.g. Figs 5AC-AE). This phase has been seen on more robust variants as well (e.g. Figs 6I-K).
3. Phase 3: specimens exhibit the same degree of compression as Phase 2, with either the same degree of involution or a slightly more open umbilicus. Ornamentation develops as sinusoidal folds. Crenulation is sometimes visible on the venter (e.g. Figs 8M-O). This ornamentation can develop early in ontogeny, at diameters of c. 20 mm (e.g. Figs 8Z-AB), or much later, at diameters of c. 65 mm, following a much longer persistence of ontogenetic phase 2. Consistent with the previous phase, much variance is observed with regard to whorl compression at this point in the developmental sequence.
4. Phase 4: specimens with bullae appearing either gradually after phases 2 and 3 (Figs 10W-AA; Figs 12D-F, M-Q) or directly after phase 2 (e.g. Figs 10L-Q; Figs 11A-C, F-H; Figs 12G-J).
5. Phase 5: a rarely observed terminal stage which consists of a smooth conch following the disappearance of bullae. This stage has only been observed in a few specimens (e.g. Figs 11D-E, Figs 12A-C) preserving a sufficiently long part of the body chamber.

As noted above, extension of these ontogenetic phases varies greatly across specimens. While large specimens (> 60mm) can still show the characteristics typical of Phase 1, juveniles can be found that display the boundary between phases 2 and 4 already early in ontogeny (Figs 10 O-Q and 11F-H), although smooth inner whorls are a predominant juvenile trait.

Such a high developmental plasticity does not lend itself to the definition of discrete character states commonly used in phylogenetic analyses and the *typus* morph lacks any clear autapomorphy with respects to both morphs *walcotti* and *nodosus*. As a result of the population approach, the definition of a species becomes a 'dynamical' definition (in time and space) best represented by the mean and standard deviation, as well as by ontogenetic curves. Otherwise, for most continuous characters of closely allied species, distinct species can only be recognized if their distributions are disjunct or at least polymodal. In this respect, Figure 25 A & B suggests that *nodosus* and *walcotti* are only end member variants of *typus*..

Intraspecific variability and morphomechanics

How do our observations fit with or differ from the recent morphomechanic generic model of ammonite shells (Moulton et al. 2015; Erlich et al. 2016)? The 'Moulton Model' roots into the commarginal oscillations generated by decreasing tension alternating with increasing compression of the periostracum. Such alternation is initiated by 'the eversion of the periostracum when the mantle

moves slightly beyond the shell edge' (Moulton et al. 2015). This powerful generic mechanistic model was extended by Erlich et al. (2016) so that commarginal oscillations scale with the curvature of the aperture. The intraspecific variation documented here can be described as a 'rifting / subduction' heterochrony, and not only as a persistent and unidirectional trend (peramorphosis or paedomorphosis) as permitted by Moulton's extended model. In other words, starting from a completely ribbed ontogeny, the onset of ribbing can be delayed and its offset can be faster, up to a point that, when both shifts are extreme, ribbing fades away completely and the shell becomes completely smooth during the entire development. These two opposite shifts can act 'symmetrically' with comparable magnitude, but all possible intermediate 'asymmetrical' combinations are also observed. Ribs, bullae or tubercles will eventually disappear on the outer phragmocone. This developmental stage acts as the 'anchoring point' from which ribbing can spread toward younger and older stages. Conversely, it will also act as an anchor point when ribbing retracts until it completely fades away. Such highly labile ribbed stage documented in the intraspecific variation of *H. typus* has not yet been captured by Moulton's extended model.

This model also predicts that the most prominent sculpture (i.e., folding of the mantle) is located within segments of the secreting edge which have the greatest curvature (e.g. at the umbilical shoulder and/or ventral shoulder as seen in many ammonoid species). This prediction also applies to analog models (as opposed to generic) such as reaction-diffusion models (Guex 2016). However, the anchoring point (the 'mid-oceanic ridge' in the rifting / subduction analogy) of the ribbing in *H. typus* culminates typically at or near mid-flank, where curvature is low in comparison with the rest of the whorl section.

These observations do not invalidate Moulton's model, but suggest that the oscillatory mechanics at the mantle edge is only expressed during a certain time interval of growth. The limits of this interval are highly variable, but the spreading and retraction point of this ribbed interval keeps a stable position during ontogeny. In addition, in the case of *Hemiprionites* (and many other genera as well), the position of the largest oscillations around

the aperture is not necessarily subordinated to the strongest curvature. We suspect that some other higher-level developmental constraints (e.g. off/on switches) connected to developmental timing could be superimposed to the generic mechanical oscillations of the aperture. Moreover, the occasional disconnection between curvature of the growing edge and the maximal amplitude of oscillations also suggests that the extended generic model of Erlich et al. (2016) only partly capture the mechanisms contributing to morphogenesis of the ammonoid shell.

Revised literature

Thanks to the large size of our pooled sample, our results provide detailed insight into the patterns of morphological variation linking species placed within the genera *Hemiprionites*, *Arctoprionites* and *Gurleyites*. Mathews (1929) identified *H.* (i.e., *Goniodiscus*) *walcotti* on the basis of its compressed form, narrow, smooth venter with occasional indistinct keels and its involute, deep umbilicus. Later work (e.g. Jattiot et al. 2017) confirmed these traits, in association with a greater whorl height, to be the features that distinguished *H. walcotti* from *H. typus*. As previously discussed – and as shown by our results – these characters merely reflect the morphologies that are expected to be found on one end of the morphological spectrum predicted by Buckmann's Law of Covariation. As such, we do not consider them reliable as traits for identifying these species.

Waagen (1985) and Mathews (1929) both described *H.* (i.e., *Goniodiscus*) *typus* as exhibiting compressed whorls, a tabulate venter, flattened flanks and a comparatively small, deep umbilicus with rounded umbilical shoulders. They reported very weak to almost absent ornamentation throughout ontogeny, consisting of very fine falciform ribs (some more pronounced than others) parallel to occasional growth lines ending in a somewhat clavate shape on ventral shoulders and weak ribs crossing the venter and imparting a crenulation. A pinching or 'bottle neck' was also described below the ventral shoulders (Mathews 1929). Later studies (e.g. Jenks et al. 2010; Jattiot et al. 2017, 2020; Jenks & Brayard 2018) further pointed to an egression of the umbilicus,

characteristic of mature whorls, as well as the presence of a ventral strigation in well preserved specimens (Jattiot et al. 2020).

Similar to the description of *H. typus*, Mathews (1929) described *Gurleyites smithi* as being an involute, somewhat robust species, with egressive coiling, convex flanks, a slightly arched, smooth or crenulated venter with rounded or square shoulders, and a broad, shallow umbilicus with rounded umbilical shoulders. The sculpture of *H. typus* shell consists of a few large, irregular, sigmoidal, radial ribs and auxiliary ribs, with auxiliary ribs terminating on the ventral shoulder, and radial ones being the most prominent there. In their revision of *Gurleyites*, Brayard et al. (2020) described a highly variable ornamentation among specimens and throughout ontogeny, consisting of slightly to strongly bullate, elongated sinuous ribs stemming near the umbilical shoulders, fading toward the venter or crossing it, creating a slight crenulation. These authors also observed a ventral strigation on both the venter and the flanks of particularly well-preserved specimens. Moreover, they pointed out the existence of a specimen exhibiting megastriae-like structures on the inner whorls. Following these observations Brayard et al. (2020) concluded that all *Gurleyites* species previously erected by Mathews (1929) could be synonymized with *Gurleyites smithi*, along with *Arctoprionites resseri*, *Goniodiscus ornatus* and *Goniodiscus (?) varians* (all erected by Mathews 1929). *Arctoprionites nodosus* was also tentatively synonymized within the genus *Gurleyites*, but as a separate species. Brayard et al. (2020) highlighted the differences between *H. typus* and *G. smithi*. While asserting *G. smithi* exhibited a large intraspecific variation that overlapped with *H. typus*, they further claimed that *G. smithi* displaying weak sculpture may be mistaken for some robust specimens of *H. typus* carrying sinuous bullate folds and ventral strigation. This suggests that, according to their observations, *H. typus* might be viewed as a less ornamented species, with little or no sculpture, while *G. smithi* comprised a more pronouncedly ornamented species along with generally being more robust. In terms of robustness, the *typus* morphs in our sample exhibit substantial intraspecific variation that overlaps strongly with variational range observed for the

nodosus morph (see Fig. 14). Neither our observations, nor our results document any morphological distinction between these two groups on the basis of degree of compression. So far as ornamentation is concerned, we have already noted the intergrading character of morphologies in our sample that connect the forms identified in previous works as *H. typus* and *G. smithi*. It is also worth noting that most previous studies have always included specimens exhibiting smooth-to-weak conch sculpture in *H. typus* (Waagen 1985; Jenks et al. 2010; Jattiot et al. 2017, 2020; Jenks & Brayard 2018). Therefore, any form of intraspecific variation has so far been excluded from this designation, limiting *H. typus* exclusively to specimens that look as much like the holotype as possible. We regard this as being in conflict with Buckman's Law of Covariation (Westermann, 1966; Monnet et al. 2005, 2010, 2015) and therefore, with the concept of a population-based approach to taxonomy. While it seems that patterns of morphological variation predicted by Buckman's Law can be accommodated within the revised *G. smithi* species concept of Brayard et al. (2020), assessments of morphological variation have remained absent in the case of *H. typus* (e.g. Jenks et al. 2010; Jattiot et al. 2017, 2020; Jenks & Brayard 2018; Brayard et al. 2020). Moreover, specimens that have been recognized as valid examples of *H. typus* by Brayard et al. (2020) appear identical to smoother specimens that have been included by these same authors within *G. smithi*, (e.g. compare Jenks and Brayard 2018 p. 96, fig. 86 G-I which has been synonymized by Brayard et al. 2020 as *G. smithi*, with Jenks & Brayard 2018 fig. 77 which depicts a valid *H. typus* specimen). It is therefore our opinion that degree of robustness and strength of ornamentation cannot be considered as valid traits for discriminating *H. typus* from *G. smithi*.

Finally, Brayard et al. (2020) observed the presence of megastriae-like structures (see Bucher et al. 1996; Jattiot et al. 2015) on the early whorls of a specimen they assigned to *G. smithi* (Brayard et al. 2020, fig. 9I-J). Megastriae were previously only associated with the genus of *Anasibirites* among the prionitids (Jattiot et al. 2015). Within our sample mechanical preparation of the inner whorls for a few selected specimens has revealed the

presence of occasional megastriae in the inner whorls of both *H. nodosus* and *H. typus*, with no correlation with the ornamentation visible on the outer whorls (see Figs 9 and 12). As evident in figures 9 and 12, both *typus* and *nodosus* morphs can bear megastriae in their inner whorls, independent on whether they have smooth or coarse outer whorls. Therefore, the presence or absence of these structures can also not be considered a diagnostic character of either morph. In the absence of megastriae both morphs present smooth inner whorls and no distinction can be made between them based on their inner whorls only. We therefore advocate synonymization of *H. typus*, *H. walcotti* and *G. smithi* within the single species, *Hemiprionites typus*.

CONCLUSION

Extensive morphological, biometric and morphometric analyses, undertaken on a large sample of late Smithian Prionitidae, indicate that the genus *Gurleyites* (*sensu* Brayard et al. 2020) is a synonym of *Hemiprionites*. Only two valid late Smithian species can be assigned to *Hemiprionites* based on morphological criteria: *H. typus* and *H. slocomi*.

A complete spectrum of morphological variation consistent with Buckmann's First Law of Covariation is documented for *H. typus*. Its end-member variants include, on the one end, smooth, slender and involute forms that have been previously assigned to *H. walcotti*, and on the other end, the coarsely ornamented, thicker and evolute forms previously ascribed to *Gurleyites* (*Arctoprionites*) *nodosus*. Ontogenetic variability in the developmental timing account for most of the 'horizontal' ornamental variation that can be observed at the same shell diameter, thus bringing heterochrony or developmental timing as a basis for Buckman's Law of Covariation. Such ontogenetic slack has contributed substantially to the inflated number of species and a taxonomic conundrum up to the genus level. Last but not least, this revision leads to a substantial reduction of the number of ammonoid taxa that were extant during the first step of the late Smithian extinction.

SYSTEMATIC PALAEOLOGY

Taxonomic descriptions follow the terminology of Arkell et al. 1957 and Klug et al. 2015.

For clarifications regarding the conventional abbreviations used, the reader is referred to Matthews (1973).

The described material is stored in the PIMUZ, Palaeontological Institute and Museum of the University of Zurich, Karl Schmid-Strasse 4, 8006 Zurich, Switzerland.

Order AMMONOIDEA Zittel, 1884

Suborder CERATITINA Hyatt, 1884

Superfamily MEEKOCERATAEAE Waagen, 1895

Family PRIONITIDAE Hyatt, 1900

Genus HEMIPRIONITES Spath, 1929

Type species. *Goniodiscus typus* Waagen, 1895; from the Salt Range, Pakistan

Emended diagnosis. Thickly discoidal, evolute ammonoids, with a moderate to weakly compressed conch and subrectangular whorl section. The venter varies from tabulate with angular ventral shoulders to subtabulate with narrowly rounded shoulders, and can develop a low rounded shape in mature specimens, though not frequently. Tabulate venters can be accompanied by a slight pinching ('bottleneck') just beneath the ventral shoulders. Such depression is sometimes visible on mature specimens and more often on juveniles, though it is commonly lost throughout ontogeny. The flanks are slightly convex and reach maximum whorl width near mid-flank, at about one third of whorl height. The umbilicus is rather small and deep. Sculpture is characterised by a large intraspecific variation, ranging from a complete smooth conch, through low radial and/or sinusoidal folds that can occasionally create a crenulation on the ventral shoulder (at times on the venter), to small bullae. The suture line is ceratitic and highly variable.

Remarks. *Hemiprionites* is here regarded as including three valid species: in the early late Smithian *Anasibirites* zone we find *Hemiprionites* (*Goniodiscus*) *typus* Waagen and *Hemiprionites*

(*Goniodiscus slocomi* Mathews, while *Hemiprionites roberti* Jenks, is found in the late middle Smithian *Owenites* beds of Crittenden Spring (Jenks et al. 2018).

Hemiprionites typus (Waagen, 1895)
Figures 4-13; Fig. 26

- *.1895 *Goniodiscus typus* Waagen, p. 128, pl. 9, figs 7-10
- .1922 *Anasibirites multiformis* Welter, p. 138, pl.17, figs 4-7,11-14
- .1929 *Goniodiscus typus* Mathews, p. 31, pl. 5, figs 12-21
- .1929 *Goniodiscus walcottii* Mathews; p.32, pl.6, figs 1-5
- .1929 *Goniodiscus americanus* Mathews, p. 32, pl. 5, figs 22-27
- .1929 *Goniodiscus utahensis* Mathews, p. 33, pl. 6, figs 29-31
- .1929 *Anasibirites edsoni* Mathews, p.27, pl. 4, figs 29–32
- .1929 *Gurleyites smithi* Mathews, p. 43, pl. 10, figs 1-6
- .1929 *Gurleyites boutwelli* Mathews, p. 45, pl. 8, figs 1-3
- .1929 *Kashmirites resseri* Mathews, p. 38, pl. 8, figs 4-6
- .1929 *Goniodiscus* (?) *varians* Mathews, p. 35, pl. 7, figs 26-39
- .1929 *Goniodiscus ornatus* Mathews, p. 34, pl. 6, figs 6-10
- ? 1929 *Anasibirites bassleri* Mathews, p.28, pl. 4, figs 33–35
- .1929 *Anasibirites mojsisovicsi* Mathews, p. 30, pl. 5, figs 1-3.
- .1929 *Gurleyites bastini* Mathews, p. 44, pl. 10, figs 7-11
- .1929 *Gurleyites chamberlini* Mathews, p. 44, pl. 11, figs 3-5
- .1929 *Gurleyites milleri* Mathews, p. 45, pl. 9, figs 10-12
- .1930 *Goniodiscus nodosus* Frebold, p. 8, pl. 1, figs 1-7; pl. 2, fig. 2
- .1932 *Kashmirites resseri* Mathews; Smith, p. 67, pl. 81, figs 9, 10
- .1932 *Anasibirites mojsisovicsi* Mathews; Smith, p. 73, pl. 80, figs 1-2
- .1932 *Anasibirites ornatus* Mathews; Smith, p. 75, pl. 80, figs 11, 12
- .1932 *Anasibirites bastini* Mathews; Smith, p. 70, pl. 80, figs 3-5
- .1932 *Anasibirites smithi* Mathews; Smith, p. 76, pl. 80, figs 13–15
- .1932 *Anasibirites typus* Smith, p. 76, pl. 80, figs 6-8
- .1932 *Anasibirites utahensis* Smith, p. 77, pl. 80, figs 9, 10
- .1934 *Hemiprionites garwoodi* Spath, p. 336, pl. 16, figs 1; pl. 17 fig. 5
- .1934 *Gurleyites freboldi* Spath, p.339, pl. 15, fig. 1; pl. 14, figs 3, 7
- ?1934 *Arctoprionites* sp. nov. Spath, p.341, pl. 14 fig. 4; pl. 18 , fig. 1
- .1934 *Arctoprionites tyrrelli* Spath, p.342, pl. 14, fig. 5; pl. 17, fig. 6
- .1934 *Arctoprionites nodosus* Frebold, Spath, p.340, pl. 16, fig. 5; pl. 17, fig. 1
- .1934 *Hemiprionites typus* Mathews; Spath, p. 331, figs 114 a,b
- .1934 *Hemiprionites timorensis* Spath, p. 331
- .1934 *Hemiprionites garwoodi* Spath, p. 336, pl. 16, figs 3; pl. 17 fig. 3
- .1961 Prionitid indet. Tozer, pl. 20, figs 1-3
- .1962 *Arctoprionites* sp. indet. Kummel and Steele, p. 699, pl. 101, fig. 2
- .1964 *Hemiprionites shimizui* Bando, p.335, pl. 49, fig. 1,2
- ? 1976 *Gurleyites debilis* Wang and He, p. 296, pl. 7, figs 23-24
- .1994 *Arctoprionites williamsi* Tozer, p. 83, pl. 34, figs 1-4
- .1994 *Arctoprionites nodosus* Frebold; Tozer, p. 83, pl. 34, figs 5-6
- v.2008 *Hemiprionites* cf. *butleri* Mathews; Brayard and Bucher, p.58, pl. 29 figs 1-7
- v.2008 *Hemiprionites klugi* Mathews; Brayard and Bucher, p. 59, pl. 30, figs 1-4
- v p.2012b *Hemiprionites typus* Waagen; Brühwiler and Bucher, p. 103, figs 89A–AH, not F-I
- v 2012b ?*Hemiprionites* sp. indet.; Brühwiler and Bucher, p. 105, figs 89A-AM

v.p.2012b *Anasibirites angulosus* Waagen; Brühwiler and Bucher, p. 103, figs 87E-J, N-P only

v.2012a *Hemiprionites* cf. *butleri* Waagen; Brühwiler et al., p. 33, pl. 19, fig. 9

.2013 *Arctoprionites resseri* Mathews; Brayard et al., p. 198, fig. 67a-c

.2013 *Hemiprionites* cf. *typus* Waagen; Brayard et al., p. 197, fig. 66

.2013 *Arctoprionites resseri* Mathews; Brayard et al., p.198, fig.67 d,e

.2013 *Anasibirites* cf. *angulosus* Waagen ; Brayard et al., p. 195, fig. 65 a,b

?2013 *Wasatchites perrini* Mathews ; Brayard et al., p. 191, fig 59 a,b

.2015 *Arctoprionites nodosus* Frebold; Piazza, p. 52, pl. 2, fig. a-d

.2015 *Arctoprionites resseri* Mathews; Piazza, p. 52, pl. 2, figs e-g

.2017 *Arctoprionites resseri* Mathews ; Piazza et al., fig. 4C-D

? 2017 *Arctoprionites nodosus* Frebold; Piazza, fig 4E

v. 2017 *Arctoprionites resseri* Mathews ; Jattiot et al., p. 34, pl. 12, figs N-X

v. 2017 *Hemiprionites typus* (Waagen); Jattiot et al., p. 31, pl.12, figs A-M; pl.13 A-X

v. 2017 *Hemiprionites walcotti* Mathews; Jattiot et al., p. 34, pl.14, figs A-Y

.2018 *Hemiprionites walcotti* Mathews; Jenks and Brayard 2018, figs 79Q-V

p .2018 *Arctoprionites resseri* Mathews; Jenks and Brayard, p. 92, fig. 86 (not G-I); fig. 87A-H

.2018 *Hemiprionites typus* Waagen; Jenks and Brayard, fig. 77; fig. 78; figs 79

.2018 *Arctoprionites resseri* Mathews; Jenks and Brayard, figs 86, 87

v .2020 *Arctoprionites resseri* Mathews; Jattiot et al., p. 55, pl. 28, figs P-U

2020 *Arctoprionites resseri* Mathews; Jattiot et al., p. 55, pl. 28Q-S.

v.2020 *Hemiprionites typus* Waagen; Jattiot et al., p. 56, pl.29, figs A-AN

v.2020 *Hemiprionites walcotti* Mathews; Jattiot et al., p. 57, pl. 29, figs AO-BG

.2020 *Gurleyites smithi* Mathews; Brayard et al, p.13, figs 6, 7, 8, 10; fig. 9A-J

.2020 *Hemiprionites typus* Waagen; Brayard et al, p.13, figs 9A-I, 10A-H, 12J-S

.2020 *Hemiprionites walcotti* Mathews; Brayard et al, p.20, figs 12 A-D, H-I

.2021 *Hemiprionites walcotti* Mathews; Brayard et al, p.15, figs 17 L-R

.2021 *Gurleyites smithi* Mathews; Brayard et al, p. 9, figs 8, 9A-I

.2021 *Hemiprionites typus* Waagen; Brayard et al, p. 14, figs 9c, 16; figs 17A-K

Emended description. Moderately to weakly compressed, involute to subinvolute prionitid, with slight egressive coiling of mature whorls. Flanks are slightly convex and reach their maximum width around two thirds of whorl height. Weakly sulcate to tabulate or subtabulate venter, rounded in rare instances on some mature specimens. A minute depression is sometimes present right below the ventral shoulders, however it is more commonly observed in early ontogeny before it fades away in the younger whorls. Ventral shoulders are angular, though less abrupt in the absence of this depression. Umbilical shoulders are broadly rounded and generate a moderate to steeply inclined (in the more involute specimens) wall and a moderately deep umbilicus, though specimens with shallower umbilicus have been observed. More slender specimens are characterized by a tighter umbilicus and a generally larger whorl height, while more robust specimens present a lower degree of involution.

Ornamentation is highly variable. Slender specimens are completely devoid of ornamentation. When ornamentation is present, it consists of vague or sometimes more conspicuous radial folds that can occasionally cross the venter to create crenulation. These folds can then develop into bullate structures. Much ontogenetic slack is observed in the timing of their development and in the duration of this ontogenetic stage. In some rarer instances they can develop already on the in the earlier ontogenetic stages to then fade away on the younger whorls, but they are more commonly observed on the more mature whorls.

The shape and position of these bullate structures is very variable. Most bullae originate above the umbilical shoulders, become especially prominent near mid flank and then fade on the outer flank, but

in some instances, they are stretched along the entire flank with the same strength. They have been also been seen to originate from the umbilical margin and fade along the flanks, leaving only a slight crenulation along the venter.

Inner whorls are smooth, except for the occasional presence of megastriae, which, in rare occasions, have been observed up to a diameter of 20 mm. Growth lines parallel to folds and spiral lines along the ventral area can be seen when preservation is adequate.

Suture line ceratitic with a high degree of variation, yet preservation of our specimens makes it difficult to investigate any finer relation between the outer morphology of the shell and the details of the suture line.

Remarks. The middle Smithian *H. roberti* differs from the average smooth variants of *H. typus* mainly by its funnel shaped and narrow umbilicus and its lack of egression, even on larger specimens with complete body chambers (J. Jenks pers. comm. 2022). However, juveniles smooth specimens of *H. typus* can hardly be distinguished from *H. roberti*. *H. roberti* is so far the only representative of this genus occurring in a typical late middle Smithian assemblage of a single section (Jenks et al. 2010). Pending confirmation of the morphological differences and of the unusual stratigraphic position of *H. roberti*, it is kept as a distinct species.

Occurrence: Cosmopolitan species found in Nevada, Idaho and Utah (Mathews 1929; Smith 1932; Kummel and Steele 1962; Jenks et al. 2010; Brayard et al. 2013; Jenks and Brayard 2018), Pakistan (Waagen 1895; Brühwiler et al. 2012b), Timor (Jattiot 2020), South China (Brayard and Bucher 2008), Oman (Brühwiler et al 2012a), Japan (Bando 1964), British Columbia (Tozer 1994), Spitzbergen (Frebald 1930; Weitschat and Lehmann 1978), Canadian Arctic (Tozer 1961,1994), South Prymorie (Shigeta et al. 2009).

Hemiprionites slocomi (Mathews, 1929)

Figure 13

*.1929 *Goniodiscus slocomi* Mathews, p. 34, pl. 6, figs 15-17

.1929 *Goniodiscus shumardi* Mathews, p. 33, pl. 6, figs 11-14

.1929 *Goniodiscus butleri* – Mathews, p. 35, pl. 6, figs 18-20

v .2017 *Hemiprionites typus* (Waagen); Jattiot et al., p. 31, pl. 12, figs A-B

Description. Thin, laterally compressed *Hemiprionites*, characterised by highly developed keels and a shallow umbilicus. The venter is narrow, deeply concave, forming distinct lateral keels. Flanks are convergent and with the sulcate venter they create a *pear-shaped* cross section. The umbilical shoulder is broadly rounded and the umbilicus is shallow and shows the inner whorl of all preceding whorls.

Remarks. *H. slocomi* differs from the type species mainly by its shallow umbilicus, which clearly shows all previous volutions, narrower venter, and its peculiar *pear-shaped* cross-section. As these traits were also observed in Mathews '*Goniodiscus shumardi* and *butleri*, the two species are now synonymized with *H. slocomi*.

Occurrence: Nevada (this work), Utah (Mathews 1929)

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Figure 26: Suture lines. Typus morphs: A: PIMUZ 39094, loc. SIL83; B: PIMUZ 39095, loc. SIL62; C: PIMUZ 39096, loc. SIL83; D: PIMUZ 39097, loc. WIL6; E: PIMUZ 39098, loc. SIL119; F (mirrored image): PIMUZ 39099, loc. SIL119. Walcott morphs: G: PIMUZ 39041, loc. SIL83; H (mirrored image): PIMUZ 39033, loc. SIL119; I (mirrored image): PIMUZ 39076, loc. SIL83. Nodosus morphs: J: PIMUZ 39078, loc. SIL119; K (mirrored image): PIMUZ 39077, loc. SIL83; L: PIMUZ 39079, loc. SIL119. Slocomi morphs: M (mirrored image): PIMUZ 39087, loc. WIL4; N (mirrored image): PIMUZ 39086, loc. SIL83. Scale bars: all 1 cm

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Chapter II

The late Smithian (Early Triassic) ammonoid fauna of the *Anasibirites* beds of north-east Nevada

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“The late Smithian (Early Triassic) ammonoid fauna of the *Anasibirites* beds of north-east Nevada”

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ABSTRACT

Late Smithian (Early Triassic) blocks from Silver Creek and Crittenden Springs, in North-East Nevada, yielded an exceptionally rich and complete record of the oldest late Smithian ammonoid fauna (*Anasibirites* zone). The large size of the retrieved samples allowed the implementation of a population approach, which provided an improved assessment of the large intraspecific variation present in most prionitids. Our biometric and morphological analyses combined with an attentive comparison of our material with precedent work, led to the synonymisation of many previously typologically defined species. A new genus, *Eowasatchites arcuatus*, was found at the base of the *Anasibirites* zone, directly overlaying middle Smithian strata. The genus *Anawasatchites* McLearn is here synonymised with *Wasatchites* Mathews. A first occurrence of *Aspenites* within the *Anasibirites* fauna is reported. Comparison of our material with findings from both high and low latitudes contribute to a better understanding of the late Smithian cosmopolitanism at the species level. Moreover, the obtained data have a direct impact on the estimation of the magnitude of the late Smithian extinction, and also provide new insights for further phylogenetic and biogeographical research. In addition, it is here first recognized that the fossiliferous “blocks” yielding Smithian ammonoids in this area are in fact olistoliths embedded into the lower part of the Thaynes Fm. during the early Spathian.

Key Words: North East Nevada, late Smithian olistoliths, late Smithian extinction, late Smithian ammonoid cosmopolitanism, *Anasibirites* ammonoid fauna, *Eowasatchites* gen. nov., taxonomy.

INTRODUCTION

The Early Triassic is a time of climatic, environmental and biological extreme instability in the wake of the Permian/Triassic mass extinction (~252 Ma; Baresel et al., 2017). It is associated with fluctuations in oceanic temperatures, with a protracted disequilibrium state of the global carbon cycle and with extinction-diversification cycles of the marine nekton in pace with ecological swaps of terrestrial plants (Payne et al., 2004; Galfetti et al., 2007a,b; Horazec et al., 2007; Hermann et al., 2012; Romano et al., 2013; Hochuli et al., 2016; Goudemand et al., 2019; Thomazo et al., 2019; Widmann et al., 2020). The late Smithian witnessed the most severe extinction of the nekton of the entire Triassic (Brayard et al., 2006; Orchard et al., 2007). It was a stepwise extinction that unfolded in the time span of ca. 600 ky (Widmann et al., 2020) with a magnitude comparable or even higher than that of the Permian-Triassic boundary. The causes of the extinction are still unresolved (e.g., Goudemand et al., 2019; Widmann et al., 2020). The *Anasibirites/Wasatchites* Zone (the oldest of the late Smithian zones, i.e. the early late Smithian, ca. 249.5 Ma) marks the first step of the extinction (Widmann et al., 2020). It was characterized by the predominance of newly evolved prionitids taxa. The oldest prionitids date back to the middle Smithian and include the genera *Prionites* Waagen, *Meekoceras* Hyatt, *Stephanites* Waagen, *Punjabites* Brühwiler and Bucher (see Brühwiler et al., 2012b) and presumably *Hemiprionites* Spath. None of these survived into the late Smithian, with the possible single exception of the middle Smithian *Hemiprionites roberti* (Jenks et al., 2010, but see Locatelli et al., *submitted*). Newly evolved prionitids of the late Smithian typically include *Anasibirites* Mojsisovics, *Hemiprionites* Spath (*sensu* Locatelli et al., *submitted*), *Wasatchites* Mathews and *Anawasatchites* McLearn. Other higher taxa crossing the middle-late Smithian boundary are rare and are restricted to the long ranging sageceratids, palaeophyllitids and proptychitids. Rare xenoceltitids are also found in association with the newly developed prionitids, although xenoceltitids reached their abundance peak in the

next younger late Smithian *Glyptopliceras/Xenoceltites* zone (e.g. Brühwiler et al., 2010, 2012a,c). The collapse of ammonoid taxonomic richness that took place in the *Anasibirites* Zone coincided with the emergence of cosmopolitanism, observed at least at the genus level (Tozer 1967, 1971, 1981, 1984; Brayard et al., 2006). The shift from a latitudinally restricted distribution to a cosmopolitan ammonoid geographic distribution predates the climatic shift from a warm middle Smithian and early late Smithian to a cool late late Smithian and early Spathian (Brayard et al., 2006; Goudemand et al., 2019; Widmann et al., 2020), thus obscuring a direct correlation between temperature and patterns of ammonoid geographic distributions. Ammonoid cosmopolitanism at the species level still has to be assessed. In order to achieve a better understanding of processes underlying cosmopolitan distributions a well-grounded taxonomy that takes into consideration intraspecific and ontogenetic variation is needed. Compilations of primary literature mostly rely on a largely typologically based taxonomy, in which species were defined based on few individuals that showed the most morphological similarities. This kind of approach comes at the expense of an accurate representation of the natural variation within taxa, as neither intraspecific nor ontogenetic variation are taken into account. In contrast, the modern taxonomical population approach (*sensu* Monnet et al., 2010; see also Tozer 1961, 1971) is based on the notion that the morphology of most living species is characterized by various levels of intra-specific morphological variation, which is presumably expressed by a continuous Gaussian distribution between end-member variants (see Monnet & Bucher 2005, Monnet et al., 2010 and Locatelli et al., *submitted* for a thorough explanation). It follows that this type of approach often leads to the synonymisation of many typologically defined species. Thus, a lack of taxonomic reassessment of literature-based compilations that heavily relies on a typological kind of approach, introduces a bias in the description and interpretation of biotic processes, such as the origin of the late Smithian

cosmopolitanism, as well as in the evaluation of the extinction intensity. This bias is exacerbated when dealing with low diversity faunas.

Recent work has started a thorough review of Early Triassic ammonoids (e.g. Guex et al., 2010; Shigeta et al., 2014; Dai et al., 2023). Smithian ammonoids, in particular, have been under careful examination in a wide range of locations, such as South China (Brayard & Bucher, 2008), South Primorye (Zakharov et al., 2021), South Tibet (Brühwiler et al., 2010), Salt Range (Brühwiler et al. 2012c), Oman (Brühwiler et al., 2012b), Spiti (Brühwiler et al., 2012a), West Timor (Jattiot et al., 2020). Exceptional records of Early Triassic ammonoids have been recognized within the Sonoma Foreland Basin of the Western USA since the first pioneer descriptions of Hyatt and Smith (1905), Mathews (1929), Smith (1932) and later Kummel & Steele (1962). Much recent work (e.g., Brayard et al., 2013, 2020, 2021; Guex et al., 2005, 2010; Jattiot et al., 2017; Jenks 2007; Jenks et al., 2010, 2013; Jenks & Brayard, 2018; Locatelli et al., *submitted*) has focused on the abundant and well preserved Smithian ammonoid fauna of the Lower Triassic Thaynes Group. The exceptionally complete ammonoid record of this area is associated with the peculiar tectonic setting found at this time in the Sonoma Basin, where high subsidence and high sedimentation rates compensate for the late Smithian global glacio-eustatic sea level fall and the associated depositional hiatus (see Widmann et al., 2020). A recent field investigation carried out in the Crittenden Springs area (NE Elko County, Nevada)

yielded unprecedented large samples of early late Smithian (*Anasibirites/Wasatchites* zone) ammonoid fauna from exotic blocks belonging to the Lower Triassic Thaynes Group. Based on these samples, Locatelli et al. (*submitted*) was able to carry out an in-depth taxonomical review of the genera *Hemiprionites* Spath, *Arctoprionites* Spath and *Gurleyites* Mathews. Their analyses allowed the synonymisation of the genera *Arctoprionites* and *Gurleyites* with *Hemiprionites*, thus pointing to a reduction of both ammonoid genera and species during the first phase of the late Smithian extinction that was larger than previously thought.

This work aims to conclude the thorough revision of the ammonoid fauna of the *Anasibirites* zone of NE Nevada initiated by Locatelli et al. (*submitted*), on the basis of the same exceptional ammonoid samples. The variety of genera found within the available samples shows what seems to be a remarkably complete ammonoid record of the oldest late Smithian zone. Such comprehensive record can help achieve a better understanding of the ammonoid fauna that makes up the *Anasibirites* zone, which therefore allows a better comparison and correlation between low and high latitudes. This in turn can provide a better understanding of the biotic processes of that time: it can shed light on the spreading of cosmopolitanism at the species level and not only at the genus level and it can improve our knowledge of the actual intensity of the first phase of the late Smithian extinction.

Figure 1: Early Triassic Pangea showing the paleoposition of the Sonoma Basin. Map courtesy of Christian Verard (after Locatelli et al. *submitted*).

GEOLOGICAL CONTEXT

Smithian deposits in the Sonoma Basin

In the Early Triassic the Sonoma Basin (Western USA) was located at a near-equatorial position on the western margin of Pangea (Fig. 1). The Sonoma Basin is a pull-apart basin belonging to an active tectonic margin, and it originated around the Permian-Triassic boundary from the emplacement of the Golconda allochthon during the Sonoma orogeny. Basinal deposits cover a large area that comprises today's eastern Nevada, western Utah, SE Idaho and parts of Wyoming (Dickinson, 2013; Ingersoll, 2019; Caravaca et al., 2017). Smithian and Spathian marine deposits are found in the Thaynes Group, and are known for an exceptionally well preserved ammonoid succession as well as for occasional mass occurrences of ammonoids (see e.g. Kummel & Steele 1962; Brayard et al., 2009a; Guex et al., 2010; Jenks, 2007; Jattiot et al., 2017; Jenks et al., 2010, 2013; Jenks & Brayard, 2018; Stephen 2010). Regional maximal onlap of the Thaynes Group was reached in the late Smithian *Anasibirites-Wasachites* and *Xenoceltites-Glyptohiceras* zones (Carr & Paull 1983; Paull & Paull 1993; Lucas et al., 2007; Brayard & Bucher 2015; Brayard et al., 2013, 2020, 2021). Smithian marine deposits from the Lower Triassic Thaynes Group, reveal relatively shallow epicontinental depositional areas (Brayard et al., 2013; 2020; 2021; Olivier et al., 2018). All Smithian ammonoids from the Crittenden Springs area, including those of our samples, were found within reworked limestone blocks embedded in wedges of polygenic breccia that originated from synsedimentary block faulting and are linked to subaerial erosion and brecciation that took place in the early Spathian (Bucher, personal observations). The *Anasibirites-Wasatchites* zone is usually found within a thin layer (max. 30 to 40 cm) of dark grey, micritic limestone packed with shells that are occasionally imbricated. Late Smithian strata generally show a relatively darker colour, compared to the grey middle Smithian strata, which suggests an increasing content of organic matter during the late Smithian. Preservation varies from block to block; different layers of a single block also display changing preservation conditions, indicating

possible changes in the early diagenetic conditions. Dense shell accumulations characteristic of many beds point to mechanical sorting by currents.

Samples were collected by H. Bucher and R. Jattiot from various localities in the area of Silver Creek (SIL 119, SIL 83, SIL 62, WIL 1, WIL 2, WIL 4, WIL 6, WIL 10, WIL 11, WIL 100) and Crittenden Springs (CS 33, see Fig. 2). A single specimen of *Anasibirites* from Northern Pequop Range (NPQ1) was also included in the analysis.

Localities and facies description

In the Crittenden Springs area, the depositional setting and geological context in which meter scale exposures or "blocks" that yielded the classic Smithian ammonoid faunas are found has remained obscure. Smithian ammonoids have been described as originating from "jumbled" or "faulted" and condensed beds, with both normal and reverse polarity. In their recent monographic treatment, Jenks & Brayard, (2018, p. 5) wrote that "the exact tectonic setting of the area thus remains to be determined" and Maekawa & Jenks (2021, p. 205) wrote that "deciphering the tectonic forces that caused the disorganized and sometimes chaotic outcrop pattern of overturned fossiliferous blocks in this largely unconsolidated interval ... is far beyond the scope of this paper".

The lack of clear and continuous exposures has been a major hindrance for the understanding of the depositional context of these "faulted or jumbled blocks". Jenks & Brayard, (2018) provided a very useful historical background on the research history of this area, to which the reader is referred to for detailed information. Maekawa & Jenks (2021) also presented a first attempt at the detailed mapping of the area. Here, we very briefly report on new field observations (by HB) made in the Silver Creek area (see Fig. 2), 5 to 6 Km to the NNE of the classic area situated on the northern side of Long Canyon (Jenks & Brayard, 2018). A detailed account of these new observations will be published elsewhere.

In the Silver Creek area, the upper part of the Dinwoody Fm. is dominated by silty shales with subordinate thin-bedded, medium grey limestone and brown weathering, dark grey shaly and silty limestone. The latter limestone contains linguloid

brachiopods in mass abundance. The Thaynes Fm. typically starts with dark, very finely laminated carbonate shales whose thickness locally reaches ca. 36m. Pluri-decimeteric slumps locally occur in these rocks. The upper part of the Thaynes Fm. consists of at least 40 m of light brownish weathering, finely laminated, platy and shaly calcareous dark limestone. The transition between the Dinwoody and the Thaynes formations is here newly observed as being a sharp erosional surface, locally enriched with bright, red weathering iron oxides or underlined by reworked metric blocks of Dinwoody rocks. This observation diverges from a gradational transition between these two formations as usually reported in earlier works. All the light to medium grey limestone metric “blocks” yielding the classic Smithian ammonoid faunas are embedded within the anoxic to sub-oxic finely laminated shaly part of the base of the Thaynes Fm., a lithological unit here interpreted as a lateral equivalent of the Lower Shales in the Bear Lake area (e.g., see Brayard et al., 2019). It is noteworthy that this succession differs from most expanded sections as exposed in the Bear Lake area, SE Idaho (e.g., Brayard et al., 2019, Schneebeli-Hermann et al 2020) and Palomino Ridge (Jattiot et al., 2017), in that the *Meekoceras* Limestone normally found at the base of the Thaynes is missing (i.e., the Lower Limestone of the Bear Lake area). In Long Canyon and Silver Creek, the missing *Meekoceras* Limestone is in fact exclusively represented by reworked blocks within the lower part of the Thaynes Fm. These occur either in channelled olistostromes up to two meters thick or as isolated pluri-metric olistoliths beneath and/or above the channelled olistostromes. Reworked blocks of the *Meekoceras* Limestone sampled a vast array of facies ranging from medium grey micritic limestone with sparse shells to shell hashes showing occasional in situ syndepositional breccias and partial dolomitization, thus illustrating the different water depths at which deposition took place in this area. Illustrations of the discontinuous deposition within some of these blocks were noticed by Maekawa & Jenks (2021, figs 5 & 6). This facies differentiation partly echoes the differences already noted by Jattiot et al. (2018) at the scale of the Sonoma Basin. Late Smithian ammonoid faunas were known to occur within a few

decimeters at the stratigraphic top of metric blocks of *Meekoceras* limestone, or as completely dismembered small blocks (e.g., Maekawa & Jenks, 2021, fig. 3). Late Smithian facies typically differ from those of middle Smithian age by their darker colour, thus indicating a higher organic matter content. The newly sampled olistoliths reported here include much more expanded strata of late Smithian age than the blocks described by Maekawa & Jenks (2021). This is especially relevant with regard to any potential reworking and condensation when addressing intraspecific variation of ammonoid species, and biostratigraphy as well. It also highlights that fossiliferous sediments of late Smithian age were deposited at different water depths, thus reflecting a contrasted paleotopography.

In Silver Creek, two successive olistostromes were recognized. The lower one occurs ca. 18 m above the erosive base of the Thaynes Fm. The second one occurs ca. 12 m above the first one. Intervening ammonoid bearing early diagenetic dark carbonate concretions within the dark shales indicate that both olistostromes were deposited during the basal early Spathian. Underlying horizons of fossiliferous concretions indicate that the Smithian-Spathian boundary is within the dark shales, ca. 6-7 m beneath the base of the first olistostrome, or ca. 15 m above the erosional basis of the Thaynes Fm.

As a first preliminary conclusion, it is established here that syndepositional block faulting was already active in this area from the end-Dienerian onward, and that it intensified dramatically during the early Spathian until the *Meekoceras* limestone was completely dismembered and redeposited as olistoliths in adjacent troughs or downthrown blocks.

Figure 2: Figures A and B show the location of the olistoliths in North-eastern Nevada from which our specimens were collected. Fig. B shows the location of the sections that yielded the most abundant samples. Figures C and D show the biostratigraphic composition of the thickest late Smithian blocks from Crittenden Spring (CS33) and from Silver Creek (SIL83). Scale represents 50 cm. Stratigraphic polarity is always towards the top. Fig. C: ammonoid found in CS33A include the new late Smithian genus of *Eowasatchites arcuatus*. Layer CS33B contains only fragmented or very poorly preserved specimens. A single specimen of *Xenoceltites* was retrieved from CS33C. Fig. D: throughout the section the typical *Anasibirites* fauna is to be found, including *Hemiprionites*, *Anasibirites*, *Wasatchites* and rare *Xenoceltites* (from SIL83B and SIL83C). Layer SIL83A is almost devoid of ammonoids, with the exception of a few fragments or poorly preserved specimens. Throughout the underlying layers, well preserved ammonoids are found among a high abundance of ammonoid shell fragments. Coordinates of all locations shown on the map and mentioned in the text: CS33 = 41°33'58.00"N, 114° 8'11.60"W; SIL119 = 41°34'31.7"N, 114°07'39.3"W; SIL 83 = 41°35'58.6"N, 114°08'31.3"W; SIL62 = 41°35'59.2"N, 114°08'30.9"W; WIL1 = 41°36'1.5"N, 114°08'19.2"W; WIL2 = 41°36'0.8"N, 114°08'18.4"W; WIL4 = 41°36'1.5"N, 114°08'18.6"W; WIL6 = 41°36'2.1"N, 114°08'19"W; WIL11 = 41°36'2.2"N; 114°08'18.3"W; NPQ1 = 40°42'37.5"N, 114°34'52.11"

METHODS

The bulk of our material consists of 317 measurable *Anasibirites* Mojsisovics specimens, 121 measurable *Wasatchites* Mathews specimens, 302 measurable specimens of *Eowasatchites* gen. nov. and 10 *Xenoceltites* Spath specimens collected from the *Anasibirites-Wasatchites* Zone of late Smithian olistoliths from NE Elko County (Nevada). Alongside these genera, additional 720 measurable specimens of *Hemiprionites* Spath are to be found within our collection, which have been analysed separately in a distinct work (Locatelli et al. *submitted*).

Where enough specimens were available, such as in the case of *Anasibirites* and *Eowasatchites*, in order to determine the number of species present in each genus, specimens were first split into empirical morphological groups based on the strength of ornamentation and on the overall shell geometry (see supplementary material). Biometric analyses were based on shell diameter (D), whorl height (H), whorl width (W) and umbilical diameter (U). These parameters were then plotted as ratios of the diameter (H/D, W/D, U/D) in order to eliminate the influence of growth (Monnet et al., 2010) to assess how they vary within and across the groups. The ratios H/W and H/U were also calculated to quantify whorl compression resp. involution throughout ontogeny. Morphological groups were then compared by means of scatterplot and boxplots in order to quantify between-group differences. Provided enough samples were present, a linear discriminant analysis (LDA) was also implemented to determine how and if morphological groups could be discriminated on the basis of the calculated ratios (H/D, W/D, U/D, H/W). The scatterplots and boxplot presented in the manuscript illustrate the quantitative morphological range defined by each species (where enough samples were available) once taxonomical assignment was determined.

SYSTEMATIC PALEONTOLOGY

Taxonomic descriptions follow the terminology of Arkell et al., 1957 and Klug et al., 2015. For clarifications regarding the conventional

abbreviations used, the reader is referred to Matthews (1973).

Order AMMONOIDEA Zittel, 1884

Suborder CERATITINA Hyatt, 1884

Superfamily MEEKOCERATAEAE Waagen, 1895

Family PRIONITIDAE Hyatt, 1900

Discussion: Prionitidae first occurred in the middle Smithian. Their oldest representatives include: *Prionites* Waagen (1895), *Meekoceras* Hyatt (1879), *Stephanites* Waagen (1895), and *Punjabites* Brühwiler et al. (2012c). None of these genera, however, survived into the late Smithian. All late Smithian prionitids were newly evolved, and the only known exception seems to be the middle Smithian *Hemiprionites roberti* (see Jenks et al., 2010, but see Locatelli et al., *submitted*). Early late Smithian prionitids now include *Hemiprionites* Spath (*sensu* Locatelli et al., *submitted*), *Anasibirites* Mojsisovics 1896, *Wasatchites* Mathews 1929 and *Anawasatchites* McLearn (1945). The last three genera were originally placed in a different family (Sibiritidae) by Spath (1934) and Kummel (1957) but they were later grouped within the family of Prionitidae by Tozer (1961), because of their homogeneity. Tozer (1961) stressed that the taxonomy of Prionitidae is an unusually difficult matter, due to the fact that most of the species included into these genera are remarkably variable. He considered it an “arbitrary” taxonomy and observed that most species were linked “by forms with intermediate morphologies”, of which “many may be morphotypes of a smaller number of unusually variable species” (Tozer, 1994, p. 78).

Occurrence: cosmopolitan family, found in Afghanistan (Kummel & Erben, 1968), British Columbia (e.g. McLearn 1945; Tozer 1967, 1994), Canadian Arctic (e.g., Tozer 1961, 1962, 1967, 1994), Japan (Bando 1964), Nevada (e.g., Jenks et al., 2010; Jattiot et al., 2017; Jenks & Brayard, 2018; Locatelli et al., *submitted*; this work), Oman (Brühwiler et al., 2012b), Salt Range (e.g., Brühwiler et al., 2012c), Siberia (Dagys & Ermakova 1990), South China (e.g. Brayard & Bucher, 2008), South Primorye (e.g. Shigeta et al., 2009), Spiti (Brühwiler et al., 2012a), Spitzbergen (e.g., Frebald 1930; Spath 1934; Piazza et al., 2017), Tibet (Brühwiler et

al., 2010), Timor (Nakazawa & Bando 1968; Jattiot et al., 2020), Utah (e.g. Mathews 1929; Brayard et al., 2013, 2020, 2021).

Genus ANASIBIRITES Mojsisovics, 1896

Type species. *Sibirites kingianus* Waagen, 1895; from the Salt Range, Pakistan.

Remarks: The reader is referred to Jattiot et al., 2015 for a comprehensive review of the genus.

Anasibirites multiformis (Welter, 1922)

(Figs 3-9A-B, N-T)

.1895 *Sibirites tenuistriatus* Waagen, p. 124, pl. 9, figs 1–2.

*p. 1922 *Anasibirites multiformis* Welter, p. 138, pl. 16, figs 9–13, 16–19; pl. 17, figs 1–3, 8–10 only.

.1929 *Anasibirites salisburyi* Mathews, p. 9, pl. 1, figs 27–29; pl. 2, figs 1–2.

.1929 *Anasibirites johannseni* Mathews, p. 12, pl. 1, figs 34, 36–37.

.1929 *Anasibirites whitei* Mathews, p. 12, pl. 1, fig. 35; pl. 2, figs 15–16.

.1929 *Anasibirites blackwelderi* Mathews, p. 13, pl. 2, figs 10–14.

.1929 *Anasibirites blackwelderi* Mathews, p. 13, pl. 2, figs 10–14.

.1929 *Anasibirites emmonsii* Mathews, p. 14, pl. 2, figs 20–26.

.1929 *Anasibirites welleri* Mathews, p. 14, pl. 2, figs 17–19.

.1929 *Anasibirites powelli* Mathews, p. 15, pl. 3, figs 1–5.

.1929 *Anasibirites whitfieldi* Mathews, p. 16, pl. 3, figs 6–8.

.1929 *Anasibirites whitfieldi* Mathews, p. 16, pl. 3, figs 6–8.

.1929 *Anasibirites veranus* Mathews, p. 17, pl. 3, figs 18–23.

.1929 *Anasibirites perrini* Mathews, p. 18, pl. 3, figs 34–36.

.1929 *Anasibirites ketchumi* Mathews, p. 18, pl. 3, figs 12–17.

.1929 *Anasibirites weaveri* Mathews, p. 19, pl. 3, figs 10–11, 32–33.

.1929 *Anasibirites wardi* Mathews, p. 19, pl. 2, figs 27–29.

.1929 *Anasibirites clarki* Mathews, p. 25, pl. 4, figs 26–28.

.1929 *Anasibirites bretzi* Mathews, p. 25, pl. 4, figs 14–18; pl. 7, fig. 13.

.1929 *Anasibirites vanbuskirkii* Mathews, p. 26, pl. 4, figs 36–38.

.1929 *Anasibirites rollini* Mathews, p. 27, pl. 1, figs 30–33; pl. 4, figs 10–13.

.1932 *Anasibirites hircinus* Waagen; Smith, p. 72, pl. 79, figs 11–12.

.1932 *Anasibirites emmonsii* Mathews; Smith, p. 71, pl. 79, figs 22–24.

.1994 *Anasibirites crickmayi* Mathews; Tozer, p. 78, pl. 28, fig. 1a–b.

.2008 *Anasibirites multiformis* Welter; Brayard & Bucher, p. 56, pl. 28, figs 1–6, text-figs 48–49.

p.2013 *Anasibirites kingianus* Waagen; Brayard et al., p. 195, fig. 62a–d, j–k only.

p.2013 *Anasibirites multiformis* Welter; Brayard et al., p. 195, fig. 64a–d only.

.2015 *Anasibirites multiformis* Waagen; Jattiot et al., p. 30, figs 10 N–S, 21–23.

.2017 *Anasibirites multiformis* Welter; Jattiot et al., p. 30, pl. 11, figs G-AA.

?2018 *Anasibirites multiformis* Welter; Jenks & Brayard, p. 73, figs. 74A-C.

.2018 *Anasibirites multiformis* Welter; Jenks & Brayard, p. 79, figs 74D-F, G(4,5), 75.

.2020 *Anasibirites multiformis* Welter; Brayard et al., fig. 11.

.2021 *Anasibirites multiformis* Welter; Brayard et al., p.14, fig. 14.

.2021 *Anasibirites multiformis* Welter; Maekawa & Jenks 2021, p. 209, fig. 8(4a-c).

Emended description from Jattiot et al. (2015): The inner whorls are characterized by a tabulate to subtabulate venter which may become slightly more rounded on mature whorls. Shoulders are angular to subangular all throughout growth. The shell is moderately involute, with a fairly shallow umbilicus, rounded umbilical shoulders and an oblique umbilical wall. Flanks are slightly convex and flatter in the inner whorls. Overall, the whorl shape stays more compressed throughout all growth stages and is generally more subrectangular than that of *A. kingianus*. Shell ornamentation usually consists of regular and dense megastriae of lower magnitude than those of *A. kingianus*. Moreover, megastriae persist throughout ontogeny. Rare specimens exhibit megastriae of

slightly higher magnitude in their inner whorls. The coarser forms of *A. multiformis* display strong ribs, especially on adult stages. Suture line ceratitic, showing saddles slightly narrower than lobes.

Occurrence. Cosmopolitan species in the lower latitudes: found in Nevada (e.g., Jattiot et al., 2017; Jenks & Brayard, 2018; this work), Utah (e.g. Brayard et al., 2013, 2020, 2021), British Columbia (Tozer 1994), Timor (Welter 1922; Jattiot et al., 2015, 2020), Salt Range (Waagen 1895), Kashmir (RJ unpub. Data in Jattiot et al., 2015), South China (e.g. Brayard & Bucher 2008). So far not reported from the Boreal Realm.

Discussion: Specimens of *A. multiformis* have been found in all our analysed localities (for a total of 317 specimens; see Fig. 3), with a predominance in SIL119 (192 specimens), followed by SIL83 (61 specimens). Biometric analysis on specimens from loc. SIL119 can be found in the supplementary material (figs S1-S3). All specimens consistently present an homogeneous morphology characterised by low magnitude megastriae throughout all ontogenetic stages. According to Jattiot et al., 2015, low magnitude megastriae are a diagnostic feature that distinguishes this species from the type species *A. kingianus*. Our findings support the existence of two species only of *Anasibirites* as suggested by the thorough revision of Jattiot et al. (2015). Although only 4 juvenile specimens of *A. kingianus* were found within the entirety of our material, their biometric parameters clearly set them apart from specimens identified as *A. multiformis* (see Fig. 4 and Fig. 5A). Values observed in our boxplot (figs 4 and 6) are in agreement with those of Jattiot et al. (2015). Combining our data with those provided to us by Jattiot et al. (2015, 2017) from different latitudes (figs 5B and 6) shows that while there is in fact some degree of overlap between the two species (as expected from their high level of intraspecific variation, see Jattiot et al., 2015), the biometric parameters of *A. multiformis* and of *A. kingianus* provide a clear separation between the two species, whatever the paleolatitudes from which the sample originates. Our analyses confirm that the main differences between the two species are: 1) the degree of whorl compression (*A. multiformis*

retains more compressed whorls throughout ontogeny than *A. kingianus*, which has a more quadratic whorl section, see H/W ratio in Fig. 6);

2) the presence of finer and more closely spaced megastriae throughout all growth stages (figs 7, 8, 9A-B). Jattiot et al. (2015) obtained an almost isometric growth as diagnostic trait for *A. multiformis*, opposed to the allometric growth of *A. kingianus*. We tested allometry/isometry by means of linear models in R. While our linear models did confirm isometric growth for the specimens of Jattiot et al. (2015), when all our specimens were added, growth deviated from isometry. The difference likely relates to the 3D preservation which is less optimal in the Nevadan material.

Within our specimens we have observed some morphologies that are defined as *rare* by Jattiot et al. (2015). Such an example is represented by Fig. 8 I-K, and Fig. 8 O-P, both of which resemble Jattiot et al.,'s (2015) fig. 23C: all these specimens show true ribs on the outer whorls. Another example is the more extreme and coarser morphology of Fig. 8 Q-V; Fig. 8 Q-S, in particular, strongly resembles *A. kingianus*. However, due the high degree of whorl compression, its subrectangular whorl section and the regular low magnitude megastriae present on all whorls, we are fairly confident of its placement within *A. multiformis* (which is also confirmed by the biometric parameters of our analysis). While such coarser morphologies might indeed be rare within *A. multiformis*, morphologies such as illustrated in Fig. 8L-N, which are intermediates between the coarser and the smoother forms are not quite as uncommon within our sample. This leads us to agree with Jattiot et al. (2015) in that rare morphologies might be attributed to a wide intraspecific variation (not unusual within prionitids, see Locatelli et al., *submitted*). Still it remains a fact, that intraspecific variation makes it sometimes difficult to distinguish between the two closely allied species.

Our large sample shows that specimens of *A. multiformis* represent 99% of all the *Anasibirites* found in NE Nevada, confirming this species to be the predominant one within the Sonoma basin (see also Brayard et al., 2020, 2021).

A. multiformis

Figure 3: Scatterplots for *Anasibirites multiformis* from Silver creek and Crittenden Springs (NE Elko Co.) and from the Northern Pequop Range.

Figure 4: Boxplot of all *Anasibirites* specimens sampled in this study. Numbers next to each box indicate the amount of specimens measured for each sample. Note that specimens of *A. kingianus* consistently plot far from all other boxes. All specimens of *A. multiformis* overlap with each other. Our values agree with those obtained by Jattiot et al. (2015).

Figure 5: Linear discriminant analysis showing both *A. multiformis* and *A. kingianus* in A) North Eastern Nevada (Silver Creek and Crittenden Springs) and B) different latitudes (data courtesy of Jattiot et al. 2016, 2017). A clear distinction between the two species can be seen from our samples in fig A, along the LD1 axis. Although in fig B, much overlap is visible when specimens from all latitudes are combined (due to the high intraspecific variation characteristic of both species), it can still be observed that the bulk of each species is well separated on the LD1 axis.

Figure 6: A clear distinction between the two species, *A. multiformis* (in grey) and *A. Kingianus* (in red), is visible in this boxplot, which includes specimens from different latitudes (data courtesy of Jattiot et al. 2015, 2017). The overlap of the boxes' whiskers relates to the high intraspecific variability, typical of almost all prionitids. Only 4 specimens assigned to *A. kingianus* were found in NE Elko Co., all of them representing juvenile stages and showing all a similar robust ribbing and a quadratic whorl section.

Anasibirites kingianus (Waagen, 1895)
(Figs. 4-6 and 9C-M)

- *.1895 *Sibirites kingianus* Waagen, p. 108, pl. 8, figs 1–2.
p.1922 *Anasibirites multiformis* Welter, p. 138, pl. 15, figs 9–27; pl. 16, figs 1–10, 14, 15 only.
.1922 *Anasibirites robustus* Welter, p. 144, pl. 17, figs 15–17.
.1929 *Anasibirites kingianus* Waagen; Mathews, p. 8, pl. 7, figs 14–22.
.1968 *Anasibirites kingianus* Waagen; Kummel & Erben, p. 135, pl. 22, figs 12–17; pl. 23, figs 1–18.
?1990 *Anasibirites ochotensis* Bytschkov; Dagys & Ermakova, p. 47, pl. 13, figs 2–5.
.1994 *Anasibirites robustus* Welter; Tozer, p. 78, pl. 28, fig. 2a–b.
.2008 *Anasibirites nevolini* Zakharov; Brayard & Bucher, p. 57, pl. 28, fig. 7–9, text-fig. 49.
.2012a *Anasibirites kingianus* Waagen; Brühwiler et al., p. 155, figs 31O, 32AA–BD.
p.2012c *Anasibirites kingianus* Waagen; Brühwiler et al., p. 101, figs 84E–L, 84R–U only.
p.2012c *Anasibirites angulosus* Waagen; Brühwiler et al., p. 103, figs 84V–AA, 86A–U, 87A–D, K–M only.
.2015 *Anasibirites kingianus* Waagen; Jattiot et al., p. 29, figs 4, 6–9, 10A–M, 12, 15–18.
.2017 *Anasibirites kingianus* Waagen; Jattiot et al., p. 29, pl. 11 figs A–F.
.2017 *Anasibirites kingianus* Waagen; Piazza et al., fig. 4F–I.
.2021 *Anasibirites nevolini* Zakharov, fig. 2.3 - 2.4

Emended description from Jattiot et al. (2015): Inner whorls are characterized by a quadratic to a (more rarely) subrectangular whorl section, an evolute coiling and megastriae of highly variable magnitude. Conspicuous ribs usually immediately precede megastriae of high magnitude. Whorl section becomes more compressed with growth and megastriae acquire a lower magnitude until they fade away almost completely at maturity, when growth lines become more pronounced. Some robust specimens can develop ribs on mature whorls which become more pronounced on the venter. Ventral shape of juveniles is mostly tabulate with angular shoulders, while in mature specimens it is highly variable and ranges from tabulate with

angular shoulders to more rounded, with rounded shoulders. The umbilicus is moderately deep with oblique walls and rounded shoulders. Suture line is ceratitic (not preserved in our specimens) with broad saddles and deep lateral lobes.

Occurrence: Cosmopolitan species found in Nevada (e.g., Jattiot et al., 2015, 2017; this work), Utah and Idaho (e.g. Mathews 1929; Brayard et al., 2021), British Columbia (Tozer 1994), Spiti (Brühwiler et al., 2012a), Salt Range (Waagen 1895; Brühwiler et al., 2012c), Oman (according to Jattiot et al., 2015), Timor (Welter 1922; Jattiot et al., 2015), Kashmir (according to Jattiot et al., 2015), Afghanistan (Kummel & Erben, 1968), South China (Brayard & Bucher, 2008), South Primorye (e.g. Zakharov 2021), Japan (Bando 1964), Siberia (Dagys & Ermakova 1990), Spitzbergen (Piazza et al., 2017),

Discussion: Only four juvenile specimens of *A. kingianus* were found within our samples, three from loc. SIL83 (Fig.9 C–J) and one from loc. CS33C (Fig. 9 K–M). These exhibit the typical morphological features of the species, such as the quadratic whorl section, more depressed than any of the specimens of *A. multiformis* (see H/W ratio in Fig. 4), the highly variable megastriae and the more evolute character of the umbilicus (see U/D ratio in Figs. 4 and 6). All these characters make them easily distinguishable from the juveniles of *A. multiformis* (Fig. 7 A–O). For further considerations and a comparison with *A. multiformis*, see *Discussion* of *A. multiformis*.

Figure 7: *Anasibirites multiformis*: A-C: PIMUZ39596 loc. SIL83D; D-F: PIMUZ39597, loc. SIL83D; G-I: PIMUZ39598, loc. SIL83D; J-L: 39599, loc. WIL6; M-O: PIMUZ39600, loc. SIL119; P-R: PIMUZ39601, loc. WIL6; S-U: PIMUZ39602, loc. SIL119; V-X: PIMUZ39603, loc. SIL119; Y-AA (X0.5): PIMUZ39604, loc. SIL119; AB-AC: PIMUZ39605, loc. SIL119; AD-AE: PIMUZ39606, loc. SIL119

Figure 8: *A. multiformis*. A-B: PIMUZ39607, loc. WIL6; C-E: PIMUZ39608, loc. SIL119; F-H: PIMUZ39609, loc. WIL6; I-K: PIMUZ39610, loc. WIL6; L-N: PIMUZ39611, loc. SIL119; O-P: PIMUZ39612, loc. SIL119; Q-S: PIMUZ39613, loc. SIL119; T-V (x0.5): PIMUZ39614, loc. SIL119;

Figure 9: A-B: *A. multiformis* PIMUZ39615, loc. SIL119; *A. kingianus*: C-E: PIMUZ39616; loc. SIL83B; F-G (X2): PIMUZ39617, loc. SIL83B; H-J (x2): PIMUZ39618, loc. SIL83; K-M (X2): PIMUZ39619, loc. CS33C. Vertical scalebar for specimens' size =1 cm. N-T: Suture lines of *A. multiformis*. N: PIMUZ 39613, loc. SIL119; O: PIMUZ 39612, loc. SIL119; P: PIMUZ39610, loc.SIL119 (mirrored); Q: PIMUZ39607, loc.SIL119 (mirrored); R: PIMUZ39604, loc SIL119; S: PIMUZ39596, loc SIL83D (mirrored); T: PIMUZ39620, loc SIL83D (Diameter = 13 mm). Horizontal scale beneath each suture line = 0.5 cm.

Genus *Wasatchites* Mathews, 1929
Type species. *Wasatchites perrini* Mathews, 1929;
from Utah.

Wasatchites perrini (Mathews, 1929)
(Figs 10-12A-N; Fig.13)

- *.1929 *Wasatchites perrini* Mathews, p. 40, pl. 9, figs 1-9.
.1929 *Wasatchites meeki* Mathews, p. 41., pl. 7, figs 1-3, pl. 8, figs 11-14.
.1929 *Wasatchites magnus* Mathews, p. 41, pl. 11, figs 1, 2.
.1929 *Wasatchites quadratus* Mathews, p. 42, pl. 7, figs 23-25.
.1929 *Kashmirites wasatchensis* Mathews, p. 37, pl. 6, figs 26-28.
.1929 *Kashmirites thornei* Mathews, p. 38, pl. 6, figs 22-25.
.1929 *Kashmirites gilberti* Mathews, p. 38, pl. 7, figs 4-9.
.1929 *Keyserlingites seerleyi* Mathews, p. 39, pl. 8, figs 8-10.
.1932 *Kashmirites meeki* Mathews, Smith, p. 67, pl. 81, figs 1, 2.
.1932 *Kashmirites wasatchensis* Mathews, Smith, p. 69, pl. 81, figs 3-5.
.1932 *Kashmirites perrini* Mathews, Smith, p. 67, pl. 81, figs 6-8.
.1932 *Kashmirites seerleyi* Mathews, Smith, p. 68, pl. 81, figs 11, 12.
.1934 *Wasatchites tridentinus* Spath, p.22, pl. 15, figs 2a-c; pl. 16 figs 2a,b, 4
.1934 *Wasatchites orientalis* Spath, p. 351, fig. 118
.1945 *Wasatchites canadensis* McLearn, p. 9, pl. 2, figs 1-3.
.1945 *Wasatchites deleeni* McLearn, p.10, pl. 2, figs 4-6
.1945 *Wasatchites procurvus* McLearn, p. 10, pl.2, fig. 7
.1945 *Anawasatchites tardus* McLearn, p. 9, pl. 3, figs 1-2
.1945 *Anawasatchites merrilli* McLearn, p.9, pl. 3, figs 3-5.
.1961 *Wasatchites tardus* McLearn, Tozer, p. 71, pl. 19, figs 1-3
.1962 *Wasatchites tardus* McLearn, Tozer, pl. 4, figs 1-2
.1967 *Wasatchites tardus* McLearn, Tozer, pl. 5, fig.3a-c
p.1978 *Wasatchites tridentinus* Spath, Weitschat & Lehman 1978, p. 94, pl. 10 figs 4-5
.1994 *Wasatchites tridentinus* Spath, Tozer, p. 80, pl.28, figs 4,5,8,9
.1994 *Wasatchites deleeni* McLearn, Tozer, p. 80, pl. 28, figs 3,6,7,10; pl. 32 figs 4
.1994 *Wasatchites procurvus* McLearn, p. 80, pl. 29, figs 1-3.
.1994 *Wasatchites macconnelli* Tozer, p. 81, pl. 34, figs 7-8.
.1994 *Wasatchites perrini* Mathews, Tozer, p. 79, pl. 29, figs 5a-c; pl. 35, figs 2-4.
.1994 *Anawasatchites tardus* McLearn, Tozer, p. 81, pl. 30, figs 2, 3; pl. 31, figs 3a-c, pl. 32, figs 5a, b; pl. 35, figs 1a, b; p. 408 Fig. 23b
.1994 *Anawasatchites merrilli* McLearn, Tozer, p. 81, pl. 30, fig. 1a-c; pl. 32, fig. 1a-c; p. 408, fig. 23a.
.1994 *Anawasatchites kindlei* Tozer, p. 82, pl. 30, fig. 4a-b.
.1994 *Anawasatchites spathi* Tozer, p. 82, pl. 31, figs 2a-c; pl. 32, figs 2a-c.
.1994 *Anawasatchites dawsoni* Tozer, p. 82, pl. 31, figs 1a-c; pl. 32, figs 3,6
.2010 *Wasatchites perrini* Mathews, Stephen et al., fig. 7c.
.2013 *Wasatchites perrini* Mathews, Brayard et al., p. 191, figs 13d, 59a-k.
.2015 *Wasatchites tridentinus* Spath, Piazza et al., p.61, figs 5a-i
.2017 *Wasatchites perrini* Mathews, Jattiot et al., p. 28, pl. 10, figs A-L.
.2018 *Wasatchites perrini* Mathews, Jenks et al., p.87, Fig. 83
.2020 *Wasatchites perrini* Mathews, Brayard et al., p.18, Fig. 9K-L
.2021 *Wasatchites perrini* Mathews, Brayard et al., p.12, Fig. 11

Figure 10: *Wasatchites perrini*. A-C: PIMUZ39621, loc. CS33C; D-E: PIMUZ39622, loc. SIL83C; F-G: PIMUZ39623, loc. SIL83B; H-I: PIMUZ39624, loc. SIL83; J-L: PIMUZ39625, loc. SIL83B; M: PIMUZ39626, loc. SIL83B; N-O: PIMUZ39627, loc. CS33C; P-Q: PIMUZ39628, loc. SIL83B; R-T: 39629, loc. WIL4; U-W: PIMUZ39630, loc. SIL83B; X-Y: PIMUZ39631, loc. CS33C; Z-AB: PIMUZ39632, loc. SIL83; AC-AE: PIMUZ39633, loc. SIL83B. AF: suture line of PIMUZ39621. AG: suture line of PIMUZ 39633. Horizontal lines beneath the suture lines correspond to 1 cm.

Figure 11: *Wasatchites perrini*. A-C: PIMUZ39634, loc. SIL83B; D-E: SIL PIMUZ39635, loc. SIL83D; F-H: PIMUZ39636, loc. SIL83E; I-K: PIMUZ39637, loc. SIL83C; L-N: PIMUZ39638, loc. SIL83D; O-Q: PIMUZ39639, loc. SIL83; R-S: PIMUZ39640, loc. SIL83E; T-V(X0.5): PIMUZ39641, loc. SIL83D. Scale bar for ammonoids: 1 cm. W: suture line of specimen PIMUZ39642, D = 45 mm; horizontal line beneath suture line corresponds to 1cm.

Figure 12: *Wasatchites perri*: A-B: PIMUZ39643, loc. SIL83; C-E: PIMUZ39644, loc. SIL83; F-I: PIMUZ39645, loc. SIL83D; horizontal line beneath suture line corresponds to 1 cm. J-L: PIMUZ39646, loc. SIL83; M-N (X0.5): PIMUZ39647, loc. SIL119; O-Q: *Wasatchites cf. distractus*: PIMUZ39648, loc. SIL83D. R-U: *Wasatchites indet.*: PIMUZ39649, loc. SIL83; horizontal line beneath suture line corresponds to 1 cm. Vertical scalebar for ammonoids: 1 cm.

Description (based on present specimens): Fairly evolute shell with convex flanks and a trapezoidal whorl section. Ventral shoulders are bluntly angular and venter ranges predominantly from tabulate to subtabulate, though it can become slightly arched on some mature whorls. The umbilicus is deep, with rounded shoulders. Ornamentation shows a large intraspecific variation. Juveniles can range between an almost smooth shell to a shell with highly pronounced ornamentation with ribs of alternating intensity. Smoother juveniles are more compressed, with folds barely visible on the flanks

that can become more pronounced on the venter, which they cross in a straight line. Smoother inner whorls have been observed up to a diameter of 30 mm, after which ribs and tubercles start to develop gradually. On the inner whorls, ribs arise from the umbilical shoulder, they become slightly projected when they cross the ventral shoulders, where they form minute nodules, and then become very pronounced on the venter, which they cross straight. On the coarser specimens, tubercles are already visible on the umbilical shoulders of the inner whorls and they rapidly become more distant

with growth, while at the same time they gradually turn into higher, more robust, bullate-like tubercles on the outer whorls. Mature whorls are always characterised by a very pronounced ornamentation, consisting of both tubercles and ribs of alternating intensity. Ribs of mature specimens usually bifurcate from the tubercles and arise from the umbilical shoulders between tubercles. They are usually faint on the flanks, but gain strength on the ventral shoulder, where they slightly project forward before crossing the venter perpendicularly. Tubercles and ribs become less closely spaced with growth. Suture line ceratitic with broad and tapered saddles.

Occurrence: Utah (Mathews 1929; Brayard et al., 2013; Brayard et al., 2020, 2021); British Columbia (McLearn 1945; Tozer 1962, 1967, 1994); Canadian Arctic (Tozer 1961, 1994); Nevada (Jattiot et al., 2017; Jenks & Brayard, 2018; this work); Spitzbergen (Spath 1934; Weitschat & Lehman 1978; Piazza et al., 2015)

Discussion: Out of the 119 specimens of *W.perrini* found in NE Nevada, 98 conformed to the morphological characteristics commonly recognized as the type species. The other specimens showed smoother inner whorls, that are sometimes ascribed to the genus *Anawasatchites* McLearn 1945 (e.g. Fig. 10 A-I). *Anawasatchites* was originally defined as a prionitid that acquires *Wasatchites*-like ornamentation at mature stages, at around 50 mm diameter, with tubercles on the umbilical shoulders (like *W. perrini*) while its inner whorls are more compressed and smooth, with only faint folds visible (McLearn 1945). Our sample allowed us a large enough overview on the genus, so that we could observe many transitional morphologies between smooth inner whorls and the coarser ones (see e.g. Figs 10A-C, F-O and R-Y and Fig. 12 A-H). We find ourselves in agreement with Tozer's (1961) original view on *Anawasatchites*, when he claimed it to be a synonym of *Wasatchites*. Tozer (1961, p. 70) stated in fact that some juveniles of *Wasatchites* also lacked prominent sculpture until about 25 mm and, as we could observe ourselves, he observed that the contemporaneous genera of *Wasatchites* and *Anawasatchites* were in fact linked by transitions. In

his later work, however, Tozer (1994) went back to consider *Anawasatchites* a valid genus, with no explanation on the matter. Supporting Tozer's first line of thinking, we here synonymise the genus of *Anawasatchites* with *Wasatchites*. In particular, we synonymise all species of *Anawasatchites* previously erected (*A. tardus* McLearn 1945, *A. merrilli* McLearn 1945, *A. kindlei* Tozer 1994, *A. spathi* Tozer 1994, *A. dawsoni* Tozer 1994) with *Wasatchites perrini*, based on their morphological similarities. The biometric parameters plotted in Fig. 13 support our hypothesis and show that the smoother forms of our sample are end member variants of a single species, *W. perrini*. These smoother *Anawasatchites*-like specimens (red colour in Fig. 13) show in fact a strong overlap with the coarser specimens of *W. perrini*, but compared to their coarser counterpart they are characterized by relatively lower values of U and U/D (figs 13E-F), indicating a higher degree of involution, higher H/D values (Fig. 13B), which indicates a higher whorl height, and higher H/W values (Fig. 13G), pointing to a greater compression degree. This stand in accordance with Buckmann's Law of covariation (Westermann 1966), according to which, smoother variants of a species are also more involute and more compressed and show higher whorl height. We further synonymise the species *W. tridentinus* Spath (1934), *W. deeleni* McLearn (1945) and *W. procurvus* McLearn (1945), within the type species. Earlier authors have also suggested such synonymisation (Dagys & Ermakova 1990; Piazza et al., 2015; Jenks & Brayard, 2018). *W. tridentinus* supposedly differs from the type species for having tubercles starting only at a diameter of 25 mm (Spath 1934; Weitschat and Lehman 1978), on half the whorl of the phragmocone (Tozer 1994). We have observed this characteristic within our sample too, and we have seen many morphologies that resemble Spath's holotype of *W. tridentinus* (Spath 1934 Plate XVI Fig. 4), showing tubercles that start later in growth (e.g., Fig. 10 P-Q, Z-AE, or Fig. 11L-N). Our specimens show that this can be explained by ontogenetic slack: when comparing specimens of the same size, it is clear that the inception of the tuberculate stage is variable as a function of diameter. This is a clear example where the developmental morphological sequence generates morphological variability.

W. deeleni, on the other hand, is said to differ from *W. perrini* by having fewer bullae on the phragmocone and a more ovoid whorl section at maturity (Tozer 1994). We regard this as the result of intraspecific variation and see no obvious difference in morphology between McLearn's holotype (1945, Pl. II, figs 4, 5, 6) and some of the specimens of our sample (e.g. Fig. 10P-Q); we thus consider our synonymisation justified. Finally, *W. procurvus* supposedly differs from *W. perrini* by having ribs crossing the venter with a projected curvature (Tozer 1994). Only four specimens of *W. procurvus* are documented in the literature, three from Tozer (1994), and one being McLearn's (1945) holotype. While a slight projection of the ribs on the venter can be seen on two of Tozer's well preserved specimens, all other morphological characteristics (their subtabulate venter, their trapezoidal whorl shape and the close position of the tubercles to the umbilical shoulder) conform to those typical of the type species. Thus, it would be reasonable to assume that this slight projection of the ribs might also be the result of intraspecific variation visible on the coarsest specimens. As such, we treat *W. procurvus* as a synonym of *W. perrini*, until proved otherwise.

Wasatchites cf. distractus

Figs 12O-Q; Fig. 13

.2015 *Wasatchites cf. distractus* Waagen, Piazza et al., p. 59, pl. 4, figs a-d.

. 2017 *Wasatchites cf. distractus* Waagen, Piazza et al., fig. 5L-M.

p.2018 *Wasatchites cf. distractus* Waagen, Jenks & Brayard, p. 89, D-F and I-N only.

Description: moderately involute shell with subtrapezoidal whorl section and slightly convex flanks. Venter is rounded with rounded ventral shoulders. The umbilicus is deep, with rounded shoulders. Ornamentation consists of prominent tubercles positioned at mid-flanks, from which straight ribs develop and become more prominent when crossing the venter. Suture line not preserved on our specimen.

Occurrence: Nevada (Jenks & Brayard, 2018; this work) and Spitzbergen (Piazza et al., 2015).

Discussion: Only one such specimen was found within our collection and its morphology matches the one of some specimens assigned to *W. cf. distractus* found by Jenks & Brayard (2018, fig. 84 D-F, L-P) in Crittenden Springs, and by Piazza et al. (2015, pl. 4 figs. a-d), in Spitzbergen.

The two main characteristics that distinguish it from our specimens of *W. perrini* are the more rounded venter, and the position of the tubercles at mid-flanks, as opposed to the umbilical position of the tubercles in *W. perrini*. Both these characteristics are typical of *W. distractus* (Waagen), a species typical of lower latitudes, such as Spiti (Brühwiler et al., 2012a) and Salt Range (Pakistan; Brühwiler et al., 2012c). *W. distractus*, however, usually has much more strongly convex flanks on the outer whorls, and a more prominent ornamentation compared to our specimen. While our specimens could be considered part of intraspecific variation of *W. distractus*, a single specimen does not allow any firm conclusion for such highly variable species.

Wasatchites sp. indet

Figs 12R-U

Description: moderately involute shell with subtrapezoidal whorl section and slightly convex flanks. Venter is rounded with rounded ventral shoulders. The umbilicus is deep, with rounded shoulders. The shell has barely any visible ornamentation, consisting of low intensity straight ribs only visible on the venter. A faint tubercle is visible just below mid flanks at a diameter of ca. 40mm.

Occurrence: NE Nevada (this work).

Discussion: Only one such specimens was found within our sample. Its subtrapezoidal whorl section and arched venter recall the morphological features observed on *W. cf. distractus*; this specimen could thus be considered a smooth variant of that morphology. However, its preservation, and the fact that only one such specimen was found, poses difficulties to any well-grounded comparison. As such, it is here left in open nomenclature.

Wasatchites, NE Nevada

Figure 13: Scatterplot of *Wasatchites* found in NE Elko Co. The red colour corresponds to the smooth specimens of *Wasatchites perrini*.

Eowasatchites gen. nov.

Type species: Eowasatchites arcuatus sp.nov.

Composition of the genus: Type species only.

Genotype: Fig. 14I-K

Diagnosis: Weakly compressed and moderately involute Prionitidae with an ovoid whorl section, broadly rounded venter and rounded ventral shoulders. Deep umbilicus with oblique walls.

Variable ornamentation ranging from a smooth shell with smooth or lightly ribbed venter to tuberculate mid flanks with a lightly to strongly ribbed venter. Faint tubercles can develop already at a diameter of 25mm. Suture line ceratitic with broad saddles.

Eowasatchites arcuatus n.sp.

Figs. 14-18

v. 2017 Prionitidae indet. 2 Jattiot et al., p. 37, pl. 16, figs I-L

v. 2010 *Wasatchites distractus* Waagen, Brühwiler et al., p. 423, fig. 15(1) only

Holotype: Fig. 14I-K

Description: Weakly compressed, moderately involute shell with slightly convex flanks. The venter is very broadly rounded with rounded shoulders. The umbilicus is deep with rounded shoulders and an oblique wall. Ornamentation shows much intraspecific variation conforming to Buckman's First Law of covariation (Westermann 1966). Inner whorls smooth or with very subdued folds, slightly more pronounced on venter than on flanks. Weak folds are slightly projected on flanks.

On many specimens tubercles are observed to develop mid-flanks, and they gradually become more pronounced with growth. The development of tubercles shows much ontogenetic slack: they can develop as early as 25 mm, yet the smooth ontogenetic stage has been observed to persist up to a diameter of 65 mm. Coarser tuberculate specimens rarely exhibit a completely smooth venter, rather they are usually characterised by more or less pronounced ventral ribs that cross the venter with a slight forward projection. The strength of the ventral ribs, however, does not necessarily correlate with the strength of the ornamentation visible on the flanks, and much intraspecific variability is seen in relation to the ventral ornamentation. Suture line ceratitic with broad saddles.

Occurrence: Nevada (in Palomino, Jattiot et al., 2017; Crittenden Springs area, this work), Tulong, South Tibet (Brühwiler et al., 2010).

Discussion: Three specimens of this species have been found in previous works, two in NE Nevada (Jattiot et al., 2017), and one in South Tibet (Brühwiler 2010), and they remained either unidentified or misidentified, due to the scarcity of available material. This is the first time that this form was recovered in such great quantity (ca. 300 measurable specimens from CS33A, see Fig. 2C).

figs S4-S7 in the supplementary material show the biometric analyses performed on the sample CS33A. Colours indicate morphological groups based on the strength of ornamentation. These analyses confirm the presence of a single species within the sample, with coarser specimens being more evolute in agreement with Buckman's law of covariation (Westermann 1966). In addition to these analyses, linear regressions were performed on the biometric parameters (H, W and U) to assess isometric or allometric growth. Both whorl width (W) and umbilical diameter (U) follow an isometric growth, while whorl height (H) shows an allometric growth (as visible also in Fig. S5, supplementary material).

The sample was recovered from the base of the *Anasibirites* zone of the exotic block CS33 of Crittenden Springs (Fig. 2C), in a single layer directly overlying the boundary with middle Smithian (identified by a single large specimen of *Tchurkites*). This layer (CS33A) is dominated by *Eowasatchites* and only rare *Wasatchites* and *Anasibirites* are found in association with it. This association allows us to assign this genus to the late Smithian. The two specimens found in Palomino (Jattiot et al., 2017) were also recovered from beds at the base of the *Anasibirites* fauna.

While the lateral tubercles and the many ventral ribs (in submature and mature stages) in combination with the rounded venter may be reminiscent of the ornamentation of *Wasatchites* cf. *distractus*, the overall whorl shape differs remarkably from it, being more ovoid, more compressed (see Fig. 18G, D) as well as more involute (Fig. 18 E,F,H).

Figure 14: *Eowasatchites arcuatus* gen. nov. from loc. CS33A. Smooth specimens showing a smooth venter. A-C: PIMUZ39650; D-F: PIMUZ39651; G-H: PIMUZ39652; I-K: Genotype and holotype; PIMUZ39653; L-M: PIMUZ39654; N-P: PIMUZ39655; Q-S: PIMUZ39656; T-U: PIMUZ39657; V-X: PIMUZ39658; Y-AA: PIMUZ39659; AB-AD: PIMUZ39660; AE-AG: PIMUZ39661; AH-AI: PIMUZ39662; AJ-AL: suture lines from non-figured specimens. Horizontal scale bar beneath each suture line represents 1cm. AJ: PIMUZ39663; smooth specimen with smooth venter; D = 27mm. AK: PIMUZ39664; smooth specimen with smooth venter; D = 28mm. AL: PIMUZ39665; smooth specimen with ribbed venter; D = 32 mm.

Figure 15: *Eowasatchites arcuatus* gen. nov. from loc. CS33A. Smooth to weakly ornamented specimens showing a smooth to lightly ribbed venter. A-B (X0.5): PIMUZ39666; C-E (X0.5): PIMUZ39667; F-H: PIMUZ39668; I-K: PIMUZ39669; L-N: PIMUZ39670; O-P: PIMUZ39671; Q-S: PIMUZ39672; T-V: PIMUZ39673; W-Y: suture lines from non-figured specimens. Horizontal line beneath each suture line corresponds to 1cm. W: PIMUZ39674; specimen with a few weak tubercles on the flanks and smooth venter; D = 46 mm. X: PIMUZ39675 (mirrored); specimen with a few weak tubercles on the flanks and smooth venter; D = 39mm. Y: PIMUZ39676 (mirrored); specimen with a few weak tubercles on the flanks and ribbed venter; D = 49mm.

Figure 16: *Eowasatchites arcuatus* gen. nov. from loc. CS33A. Weakly ornamented specimens with strongly ribbed venter. A-D: PIMUZ39677; E-G: PIMUZ39678; H-J: PIMUZ39679, VL be; K-M: PIMUZ39680; N-O: PIMUZ39681; P-Q: PIMUZ39682; R-T (X2): PIMUZ39683; U-W: PIMUZ39684. Vertical scale bar = 1 cm. X-Z: suture lines from non-figured specimens. Horizontal scale bar beneath each suture line = 1 cm. X: PIMUZ39685 (mirrored); specimen with a few weak tubercles on the flanks and ribbed venter; D = 41 mm. Y: PIMUZ39686 (mirrored); coarse ornamented specimen with ribbed venter; D = 52 mm. Z: PIMUZ39687; coarse ornamented specimen with ribbed venter; D = 46 mm.

Figure 17: *Eowasatchites arcuatus* gen. nov. from loc. CS33A. Coarsely ornamented specimens with ribbed venter. A-C: PIMUZ39688; D-F: PIMUZ39689; G-I: PIMUZ39690; J-K (X0.5): PIMUZ39691

Wasatchites vs. *Eowasatchites*

Figure 18: Scatterplot comparing biometric parameters of *Wasatchites* versus *Eowasatchites arcuatus*. Note the distinct separation between the two genera: *Eowasatchites* is overall more involute (figs. E, F, H) and more compressed (fig. G).

Family Dieneroceratidae Kummel, 1952

Genus *Dieneroceras* Spath, 1934

Type species: *Ophiceras dieneri* Hyatt & Smith,
1905

Dieneroceras sp. indet.

Fig. 19V-X

Description. Serpenticonic, evolute, laterally compressed shell with a subtabulate to tabulate venter and a quadratic whorl section. Flanks are slightly convex with moderately angular ventral shoulders. Umbilicus is shallow, with rounded shoulders and steeply inclined umbilical wall. Ornamentation of our specimen is smooth. Suture line not preserved.

Occurrence: Genus typically occurring within the middle Smithian's *Owenites* beds. It is found in the middle Smithian of both low and higher latitudes, e.g. in: Idaho (Hyatt & Smith, 1905), Timor (Jattiot et al., 2020), Timor Leste (Nakazawa & Bando 1968), Afghanistan (Collignon 1973), Nevada (Jenks et al., 2010; Brayard et al., 2013), Oman (Brayard et al., 2012), South China (Brayard & Bucher, 2008), Siberia (Dagys & Kostantinov 1984). Our unique specimen was found in the *Anasibirites* zone (SIL83B).

Discussion. Only a single small specimen (D= 13 mm) belonging to this genus was found within our samples. Its small size prevents a definite species assignment, as juveniles of the same genus tend to converge. The reader is referred to Brayard et al. (2013) for a detailed discussion on this genus.

Family INYOITIDAE Spath, 1934

Genus SUBVISHNUITES Spath, 1930

Type species. *Subvishnuites welteri* Spath, 1930 (= *Vishnuites* spec. Welter, 1922).

Subvishnuites posterus Brühwiler et al., 2012a

Figs 19R-U

. 2012b *Subvishnuites* sp. indet., Brühwiler et al., p. 36, pl. 21, fig. 14

.2012a *Subvishnuites posterus* Brühwiler et al., p. 163, fig.37 AQ-BK

.2020 *Subvishnuites* cf. *posterus* Brühwiler et al., Jattiot et al., p. 43, pl. 22, figs AT-AU

Description. Serpenticonic, moderately compressed shell. Convex flanks, subparallel on the inner half and converging towards the venter. Venter is narrowly rounded and narrowly arched. Shallow, wide umbilicus with rounded umbilical shoulders. On our specimen ornamentation consists of very weak ribs that tend to cross the venter. Suture line ceratitic with long and narrow saddles.

Occurrence: To date, this younger species of *Subvishnuites* has only been reported from the low paleolatitudes: in Spiti (Brayard et al., 2012a), where it is found in the *Subvishnuites posterus* beds that overly the *Wasatchites* beds, in Timor (Jattiot et al., 2020), in Oman (Brühwiler et al., 2012b), and in Nevada (this work, loc. SIL119). In the last three areas it was found in association with the *Anasibirites* fauna.

Discussion: *S. posterus* is the only species of *Subvishnuites* to be found in the late Smithian. Occurrences of this species in association with the *Anasibirites* fauna are rare, and have insofar been reported only from Oman (Brühwiler et al 2012b), Timor (Jattiot et al., 2020) and NE Nevada (this work). Only one specimen of this genus was found within our samples and although slightly deformed, it is morphologically very similar to the typical representatives of *S. posterus*.

The other two species included in this genus, *S. welteri* and *S. stokesi*, are of middle Smithian age.

Superfamily SAGECERATACEAE Hyatt, 1884

Family ASPENITIDAE Spath, 1934

Genus ASPENITES Hyatt & Smith, 1905

Type species. *Aspenites acutus* Hyatt & Smith,
1905.

Aspenites sp. indet.

Figs 19Y-AA

Description. Extremely involute and compressed shell with a lanceolate whorl section. Flanks are slightly convex and the venter is characterised by an acute keel. The umbilicus is occluded. The surface of our single specimen is completely smooth. Suture line not preserved on our specimen.

Occurrence. Our single specimen was found in association with the typical *Anasibirites* fauna of loc. SIL83B. This is the first recorded occurrence of this genus in the late Smithian. *Aspenites* typically occurs in the middle Smithian of the lower latitudes, such as Nevada (e.g. Jattiot et al., 2017, Jenks & Brayard, 2018), Utah (Brayard et al., 2013), Timor (e.g. Jattiot et al., 2020), South China (Brayard & Bucher, 2008), Oman (Brühwiler et al., 2012b), Spiti (Brühwiler et al., 2012c), Vietnam (Shigeta et al., 2014), south-central Alaska (Nichols & Silberling, 1979), Tibet (Brühwiler et al., 2010).

Discussion. Only a single small (D = 13 mm) specimen was found in our samples. Its small size and its poor preservation preclude a definite assignment at the species level. This genus has so far been documented to range from the early to middle Smithian. To our knowledge, this is the first record of it from the late Smithian *Anasibirites* fauna.

Superfamily Xenodiscaceae Frech, 1902

Family Xenoceltitidae Spath, 1930

Genus *Xenoceltites* Spath 1930

Type species: *Xenoceltites subevolutus* =
Xenodiscus cf. *comptoni* (non Diener) Frebold,
1930

Xenoceltites subevolutus Spath, 1934
Figs 19 A-Q

- .1929 *Ophiceras matheri* Mathews, p. 4, pl. 1, figs. 38–40.
- .1929 *Xenodiscus douglasensis* Mathews, p. 5, pl. 1, figs. 5–7.
- .1930 *Xenodiscus* cf. *comptoni* Diener; Frebold, p. 14, pl. III, figs. 1, 2, 2a, 3.
- .1930 *Lecanites* cf. *ophioneus* Waagen; Frebold, p. 12, pl. III, figs. 4, 4a, 5.
- .1934 *Xenoceltites subevolutus* Spath, p. 130, pl. II, fig. 2; pl. VIII, fig.2; pl. IX, fig.4; pl.XI, fig.2
- . 1934 *Xenoceltites gregoryi* Spath, p. 129, pl. VI, fig. 4,5; pl. XI, figs 3,4,6
- . 1934 *Xenoceltites spitsbergensis* Spath, p. 128, pl. 9, figs 1, 2; pl. 11, figs 5, 7, 8.
- .1961 *Xenoceltites subevolutus* Spath, Tozer, p. 53, pl. XVI, fig. 1a,b

- .1978 *Xenoceltites spitsbergensis* Spath, Weitschat & Lehmann, p. 94, pl. 11, figs 3b, 4, 5
- .1978 *Xenoceltites subevolutus* Spath, Weitschat & Lehmann, p. 95, pl. 11, figs 1, 2, 3°
- .1990 *Xenoceltites subevolutus* Spath, Dagys & Ermakova, p. 23, pl. 5, fig. 4
- .1990 *Xenoceltites matheri* Mathews, Dagys & Ermakova, p. 24, pl. 5, figs 5-10
- . 1994 *Xenoceltites subevolutus* Spath, Tozer, p. 52, pl. 36, figs. 3–8.
- . 2010 *Xenoceltites* sp. – Stephen et al., fig. 7 d.
- . 2013 *Xenoceltites* sp. indet. A, Brayard et al., p. 160, fig. 19a-c
- . 2015 *Xenoceltites subevolutus* Spath, Piazza et al., p. 48, Pl. I, figs a-c
- . 2017 *Xenoceltites subevolutus* Spath, Jattiot et al., p. 10, pl. 1, figs P-AD
- .2017 *Xenoceltites subevolutus* Spath, Piazza, p. 110, fig. 4a, b.
- . 2018 *Xenoceltites subevolutus* Spath, Jenks & Brayard, p. 21, fig. 21
- . 2021 *Xenoceltites subevolutus* Spath, Brayard et al., p. 5, fig. 4A-P

Description: Evolute *Xenoceltites*, moderately compressed, with rounded venter, rounded ventral shoulders and slightly convex flanks. Umbilicus wide, moderately shallow, with oblique walls and rounded umbilical shoulders. Ornamentation observed on our specimens ranges from predominantly smooth shells to weakly ornamented shells with faint ventral constrictions that extend on the flanks. These constrictions are already visible on the inner whorls and can either maintain the same intensity or, more often, become less pronounced on the outer whorls. Suture line only partially preserved on one of our 11 specimens.

Occurrence: Utah (Mathews 1929; Brayard et al., 2013; Brayard et al., 2021); British Columbia (Tozer 1994); Canadian Arctic (Tozer 1961, 1994); Nevada (Jattiot et al., 2017; Jenks & Brayard, 2018; this work); Spitzbergen (Spath 1934; Weitschat & Lehman 1978; Piazza et al., 2015, 2017); Siberia (Dagys & Ermakova 1990)

Discussion: The genus *Xenoceltites* is found in most abundant quantities in the late Smithian boreal *Tardus* zone (Tozer 1994) and in the low latitudes *Glyptophysceras/Xenoceltites* zone. However, in the low latitudes it makes its first appearance in the younger early late Smithian *Anasibirites/Wasatchites* zone, although in very poor quantities. Our material from NE Elko County includes only 10 measurable specimens, and 5 very poorly preserved ones. Our specimens clearly include a single *Xenoceltites* species that carries an identical morphology to those found by Jattiot et al. (2017) in Palomino Ridge, which they attributed to *X. subevolutus*. Following a written communication of Weitschat (1994, to HB, see Jattiot et al., 2017 p. 11) Jattiot et al. (2017) synonymized the three species *X. subevolutus*, *X. spitzbergensis* and *X.*

gregoryi originally erected by Spath (1934) into one single species, *X. subevolutus*. Like them, other previous authors have attempted to synonymize these species (e.g. Dagys & Ermakova 1990, Piazza et al., 2015) based on their morphological similarities and their overlapping intraspecific variation recognised within the more abundant Boreal specimens. On the basis of our limited material and comparing it to previous literature, we agree with this interpretation. However, larger samples are needed in order to validate this hypothesis.

Figure 19: *Xenoceltites subevolutus*: A-B: PIMUZ39692, loc. SIL119. C-E: PIMUZ39693, loc. SIL83. F-G: PIMUZ39694, loc. SIL119. H-I: PIMUZ39695, loc. SIL83B. J-L: PIMUZ39696, loc. SIL83B. M: PIMUZ39697, loc. SIL83B. N-P: PIMUZ39698, loc. WIL6. Q: PIMUZ39699, loc. CS33C. R-U: *Subvishnuites posterus*; PIMUZ39700, loc. SIL119. V-X: *Dieneroceras* sp. indet. (X2) PIMUZ39701, loc. SIL83B. Y-AA: *Aspenites* sp. indet. (X2) PIMUZ39702, loc. SIL83B. Vertical scale bar represents scale for ammonoid specimens and corresponds to 1 cm. Horizontal scale bar beneath suture lines represents scale for suture lines only and correspond to 1 cm.

CONCLUSION

Combining analyses conducted on our Nevadan material with careful comparisons of previous works has allowed us to synonymise the genus *Anawasatchites* McLearn with *Wasatchites* Mathews. Within the genus *Wasatchites* the species *W. tridentinus* Spath (1934), *W. deeleni* McLearn (1945) and *W. procurvus* McLearn (1945) were here synonymized with the type species *W. perrini*.

Analyses implemented on our collection of *Anasibirites* Mojsisovics, in combination with data provided by R. Jattiot from global locations have allowed us to add to the review on the genus conducted by Jattiot et al., 2015 and further validate its results.

A new genus, *Eowasatchites arcuatus* is here reported for the first time and in great quantities from the base of the early late Smithian. Moreover, we report a first occurrence of *Aspenites* within the *Anasibirites* fauna.

Comparison of our material with previous work from various paleolatitudes, has allowed us to establish that early late Smithian cosmopolitanism was in fact widespread at a species level too, and not only at a genus level. For most species recognized within our Nevadan collection, i.e. *Anasibirites kingianus* Waagen, *Wasatchites perrini* Mathews, *Wasatchites cf. distractus* Waagen, *Xenoceltites subevolutus* Spath and *Heminprionites typus* Waagen (see Locatelli et al., *submitted* for the latter), correlatives could be found both in high and low paleolatitudes. To the present day, *Anasibirites multiformis* Welter, only shows a cosmopolitanism limited to the low paleolatitudes and has not yet been reported from the Boreal Realm. *Eowasatchites arcuatus sp.nov.* has also only been recovered from the low latitudes, specifically from South Tibet and NE Nevada; the latter is probably due to the peculiar tectonic settings of the area that allow the preservation of an exceptionally complete Smithian ammonoid record that is usually not found in any other place. Finally, *Subvishnuites posterus* Brühwiler et al., seems to be restricted to a few localities within the low paleolatitudes and has yet to be found in the Boreal realm.

The taxonomical synonymisations that were made possible from our unprecedentedly large collection in

this work and in Locatelli et al. (*submitted*) indicate a severe reduction of early late Smithian available species names. This points to what is probably a much more severe first phase of the late Smithian extinction than previously assessed.

DECLARATIONS

AVAILABILITY OF DATA AND MATERIAL

The described material is stored in the PIMUZ, Paleontological Institute and Museum of the University of Zurich, Karl Schmid-Strasse 4, 8006 Zurich, Switzerland. All self-acquired data analysed during this study are included in the supplementary information files. Sources of data from other studies are mentioned in the article and in the reference list.

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AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

LL partially prepared the material of our Nevadan collection, generated most measurements data, implemented the analyses, interpreted the results and executed most of the writing. TB prepared the bulk of the specimens used for our study and aided in the taxonomical interpretations. RJ assisted with the recovery of our collection from the field. HB supervised this project, collected the used samples from the field, aided in the taxonomical interpretation and in the interpretation of all implemented analyses, provided and wrote the geological description of the surveyed area of this manuscript and gave an overall major contribution in the writing of this manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Chapter III

The Late Smithian (Early Triassic) genus *Xenoceltites*: a new collection from Spitzbergen

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“The Late Smithian (Early Triassic) genus *Xenoceltites*: a new collection from Spitzbergen”

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ABSTRACT

The genus *Xenoceltites* Spath is one of the main components of the ammonoid fauna of the late Smithian boreal *tardus* zone. In the low latitudes it makes its first appearance in the early late Smithian *Anasibirites/Wasatchites* zone and it becomes a dominant species in the younger *Glyptophyseras/Xenoceltites* zone. *Xenoceltites* is one of the cosmopolitan genera that developed in the wake of the late Smithian extinction, and, as such, it can aid in the development of a better correlation of late Smithian ammonoid fauna across paleolatitudes. In order to achieve this, though, it must be rooted in a robust taxonomy which has so far been hindered by the lack of sufficiently big samples. This study aims to add to our current understanding of the genus with the analysis of a new collection of ninety-one well preserved specimens of *Xenoceltites* recovered from three sections from Spitzbergen (STC1, STA2 and WALD2). Implementing a quantitative population-based approach, with emphasis on intraspecific and ontogenetic variation, we could affirm the presence of only one species of *Xenoceltites* within our collection, i.e. *X. subevolutus*. Based on our biometric analyses and our empirical morphological observations we were able to identify the morphological characteristics on which *X. gregoryi* Spath and *X. spitzbergensis* Spath were grounded within the intraspecific variation of our sample and we thus support the synonymisations of Spath's *X. gregoryi* and *X. spitzbergensis* with *X. subevolutus*. Through an attentive comparison of our specimens with *Xenoceltites* found in previous work, we were also able to recognize *X. subevolutus* both in the higher and in the lower paleolatitudes (where it can be found in both the *Anasibirites* and the *Glyptophyseras* zone) thus confirming its cosmopolitan character.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Xenoceltites* Spath (1930) is one of the main constituents of the late Smithian (Early Triassic) boreal *tardus* zone (Tozer, 1994) and of the low latitudes *Glyptophyseras/Xenoceltites* zone, although in the low latitudes it makes its first appearance in the early late Smithian *Anasibirites/Wasatchites* zone. The ammonoid fauna of the *Anasibirites* Zone defines the first step of the late Smithian extinction, an extinction which spanned ca. 600 kyr and severely decimated nekto-pelagic organisms (Brayard et al., 2006; Orchard, 2007; Widmann et al., 2020). The associated collapse of ammonoid taxonomic richness was accompanied by the emergence of ammonoid cosmopolitanism (Tozer, 1971; Brayard et al., 2006; Locatelli et al., *submitted*). *Xenoceltites* Spath is one of the genera of the *Anasibirites* zone that has been reported both from high and low latitudes, alongside the other genera of this fauna, specifically: *Anasibirites* Mojsisovics, *Hemiprionites* Spath (*sensu* Locatelli et al. *submitted*) and *Wasatchites* Mathews (*sensu* Locatelli et al. *in prep.*). These genera facilitate correlation of late Smithian ammonoid fauna across paleolatitudes despite the uncertainties that still persist when correlating high and low paleolatitudes at the zone level. The genus *Xenoceltites* was originally found in the high latitudes of Spitzbergen (Friebold, 1930; Spath, 1934), where it is also the most abundant. In his first definition Spath (1934) recognized three main species recovered from layers overlying the *Anasibirites* beds: *X. spitsbergensis*, *X. gregoryi* and *X. subevolutus*. Later on, Weitschat & Lehmann (1978) collected over 200 specimens of *Xenoceltites* from Spitzbergen, within which they could distinguish two main coexisting morphologies only: *X. spitsbergensis*, a relatively evolute, slightly ribbed form and *X. subevolutus*, which they recognised as bearing a more compressed and nearly smooth morphology. Years later, in a written communication, Weitschat (1994 to HB in Jattiot et al., 2017, p. 11) went back on his initial observations, claiming that in fact all three species originally identified by Spath (1934) likely constitute a wide intraspecific variation of the single species *X.*

subevolutus. This interpretation was supported by later studies: Brayard and Bucher (2008), for example, emphasized that all species of *Xenoceltites* morphologically overlap, due to the broad range of intraspecific variation reflected both in whorl shape and ornamentation. However, they refrained from synonymisation. Jattiot et al. (2017) was the first to formally synonymise *X. spitsbergensis* and *X. gregoryi* with *X. subevolutus* and to this day, of Spath's original three species, only *X. subevolutus* is now considered as valid (e.g. see Jenks & Brayard, 2018; Brayard et al., 2021), both for the high and low latitudes.

Another species of *Xenoceltites*, *X. variocostatus*, has been recognized by Brayard and Bucher (2008) from early diagenetic limestone nodules of the *Anasibirites* beds of South China. According to their observations, the variocostate ribbing on the innermost whorls and the variable coiling geometry at different ontogenetic stages distinguish *X. variocostatus* from the type species *X. subevolutus*. Controversy around this species is still ongoing: Jattiot et al. (2017) suggested that *X. variocostatus* should in fact be assigned to a different genus, based on its larger whorl thickness. Jenks & Brayard 2018, on the other hand, described this species as an intermediate morphology between *Condencoceras youngi* Jenks & Brayard and *X. subevolutus*. While they consider it a valid taxon, they claim that more material is needed to draw well-grounded conclusions, adding that "the difficulty encountered in differentiating and setting taxonomic boundaries between widespread late Smithian xenoceltitid species, e.g., *X. subevolutus*, *C. youngi* n. gen., *X. variocostatus* and *G. sinuatum*, leads one to contemplate whether all of the specimens involved may possibly belong to one large, all-encompassing genus with extremely wide intraspecific variation" (Jenks & Brayard 2018, p. 24). The hypothesis of a possible morphological/evolutionary continuum among all these species is shared by Brayard et al., 2021. Yet, as rightfully mentioned by Jenks & Brayard (2018) this could only be proven with sufficiently abundant and well-preserved specimens from different locations, which are often unavailable. Species, especially those which include large intraspecific variance, are in fact best identified when the full

range of variation is evident in a single assemblage of coexisting ammonoids Tozer (1971, p. 999). This view reflects what is referred to today as a population-based approach to taxonomy, which rests on the notion that most living species are characterized by various levels of intra-specific and ontogenetic morphological variation likely expressed by a continuous Gaussian distribution between end-member variants (see e.g. Monnet & Bucher, 2005, Monnet et al., 2010 and Locatelli et al. *submitted*). The aim of this work is to add to our current understanding of the genus *Xenoceltites* and thus to contribute to the improvement of correlation of late Smithian ammonoid fauna across latitudes. Ninety-one well preserved specimens of *Xenoceltites* from three sections from Spitzbergen (STA2, STC1 and WALD2) allowed the implementation of a quantitative, population-based approach, with emphasis on intraspecific and ontogenetic variation. The specimens are herein analysed on the base of their biometric parameters and taxonomical results are then compared with specimens found in previous work from different localities.

GEOLOGICAL SETTING

In the eastern and central parts of Spitzbergen (where our sections are located, Fig. 1) Early Triassic strata are included within the Vikinghøgda

Formation (part of the Sassendalen Group; Mork et al. 1999). Three members can be distinguished within the Vikinghøgda Formation: the Deltadalen Member, deposited during the Griesbachian and Dienerian and corresponding to the Vardebukta Formation in the west of Spitzbergen; the Lusitaniadalen Member deposited during the Smithian and corresponding to the Iskletten Member of the Tvillingodden Formation in western Spitzbergen; and the Vendomdalen Member dating back to the Spathian and corresponding to the Kaosfjellet Member of the Tvillingodden Formation (Mork et al., 1999). While the Vikinghøgda Formation represents deposition on an offshore shelf at progressively deeper transgressional settings, the Vardebukta and the Tvillingodden Formations correspond to a coastal to shallow marine depositional setting (Mork et al., 1999; Wignall et al., 2016).

It is estimated that the Smithian and Spathian boundary lies somewhere close to the lithological boundary of the Lusitaniadalen and the Vendomdalen Members (Hammer et al., 2019). However, it is obscured by the global sedimentological gap that characterises the late Smithian, which has an earlier onset in the Boreal record with respect to the Tropics (Hammer et al., 2019). This gap contributes to the difficulties faced when attempting biostratigraphic correlations between low and high paleolatitudes. In fact, in the lower latitudes, the late Smithian is defined by the

Figure 1: A) Map of Svalbard showing the location of the sections from which our collection was recovered. Coordinates of the studied sections: STA: 78°17'02.8"N; 017°42'20.1"E; STC: 78°16'59.8"N; 017°44'22.5"E; WALD: 78°13'12.5"N; 017°54'42.7"E. Modified after Hansen et al., 2020. B) Paleoposition of Svalbard in the Early Triassic. Paleomap courtesy of Christian Verard.

older *Anasibirites* Zone overlaid by the youngest *Glyptophyceras sinuatum* zone (see e.g. Brühwiler, Bucher, Brayard, et al., 2010; Jattiot et al. 2017; Jenks and Brayard 2018) and possibly by a third zone of which trace has been found only in the peculiar tectonic settings of the Western US Sonoma Basin and seems to have been obscured by the late Smithian hiatus at most latitudes (see Widmann et al. 2020). Due to the earlier onset of the sedimentological gap in the boreal realm, the only zone preserved in the Lusitaniadalen Member is the early late Smithian *W. tardus* zone, a correlative of the low latitudes *Anasibirites* zone (Hammer et al. 2019).

Specimens analysed in this work were recovered from the late Smithian *tardus* zone of two sections at Stensiöfjellet (STC1 and STA2, whose proximity and similar development allowed them to be sampled - and represented - as a single section, see Hansen et al. 2020) and one sections at Wallenbergfjellet (WALD2; see Fig. 2). *Xenoceltites* were found in association with *Hemiprionites* (*sensu* Locatelli et al. submitted) and *Wasatchites* in

early diagenetic carbonate concretions. The uncertainty of the position of the late Smithian sedimentary gap makes it impossible to understand whether STA2/STC1 and WALD2 occur at the same stratigraphic position or whether one of these beds is older than the other. The reader is referred to Hansen et al. (2020) for a comprehensive description of these sections.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Our material consists of 91 specimens of which 64 well preserved ones were recovered from Stensiöfjellet STA2, 22 specimens were found in Stensiöfjellet STC1 (also in well preserved conditions) and 5 poorly preserved ones were recovered from Wallenbergfjellet section WALD2. Specimens were divided into empirical morphological groups based on overall shell geometry and strength of ornamentation. Biometric analyses were based on shell diameter (D), whorl width (W), whorl height (H) and umbilical diameter (U). To determine how these parameters

Figure 2: Lithostratigraphic logs of the investigated sections, showing the layers from which our *Xenoceltites* were recovered (STA2 i.e. STC1 which were sampled as a single section due to their proximity and similar lithological development, and WALD2). Position of *Arctoceras* ammonoid genus according to Hansen et al. (2020). Modified after Hansen et al. (2020).

differ within and across the groups, they were plotted as ratios of the diameter (H/D, W/D, U/D) to eliminate the influence of growth (Monnet et al., 2010). The ratios H/W and H/U were also calculated to quantify whorl compression resp. involution throughout ontogeny. Based on the shell parameters and the constructed ratios morphological groups were then compared by means of scatterplot and boxplots in order to quantify between-group differences. Where enough specimens were present, a linear discriminant analysis (LDA) was implemented to assess how and if the recognized groups could be discriminated on the basis of the calculated ratios (H/D, W/D, U/D, H/W). Finally, once the specimens had been taxonomically defined, allometric growth patterns of each parameter were tested by means of linear models. Growth patterns of specimens with a diameter < 20 mm were tested separately from those of specimens > 20 mm, as juveniles often show more plasticity, compared to the more mature specimens. Our collection was then compared with material recovered from NE Nevada and Palomino (data from Jattiot et al., 2017).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Upon first notice, specimens from sections STA2 and STC1 present little intraspecific variance. The main feature allowing us a distinction into morphological groups was the ornamentation visible on the shell's surface (although sometimes obscured by recrystallisation). Figure 3A shows that the coarser the ornamentation the more depressed the conch (lower H/W) and the more evolute the umbilicus (higher U/D). This in turn implies that whorl height (H/D) increases slightly in the less ornamented specimens which, as a result, present a more elliptical whorl section (as opposed to the coarsest specimens, which are characterised by a more circular whorl section, i.e. H/W values closer to 1, Fig. 3A). These observations stand in agreement with Buckmann's first law of covariation which predicts that the morphological range described by the intraspecific variation of ammonoid taxa ranges between slender, involute, compressed and weakly ornamented forms to the extreme robust, more evolute, depressed end member variants with coarser ornamentation

Figure 3: A) Boxplots showing the ornamentation-based morphological groups recognized in each of our Spitzbergen section. Notice how the same morphological groups from STC1 and STA2 overlap in most cases. B) Comparison of the different sections. Notice the overlap between STA2 and STC1.

(Westermann, 1966). Figures 3 and 4 also show that, as expected, specimens recovered from both sections STA2 and STC1 must belong to the same species: in the boxplots, in fact, each morphological group of the one section overlaps with the corresponding one of the other section. In the LDA (Fig. 4B), the two groups corresponding to the specimens of the two sections overlap. Specimens recovered from the further section WALD2 appear to stand out when compared to the smooth ones of the other two sections (figs 3 and 4). While these specimens could simply represent extreme slender member variants, in accordance with Buckmann's Law of covariation, they could also represent a distinct species. However, these specimens are very badly preserved and are too few in number to allow us to draw any sound conclusion. Moreover, as previously mentioned, the late Smithian sedimentary gap visible in all sections does not allow us to define with certainty whether STA2/STC1 and WALD2 occur at the same stratigraphic position or whether one of these beds is older than the other, thus potentially carrying any ancestral or a derivative species. In the absence of

more material, we here consider these specimens as part of the intraspecific variation of *X. subevolutus*, although additional material is needed to verify this claim.

When comparing our collection from Spitzbergen with the material we recovered from NE Elko County (NE Nevada, Locatelli et al. in prep), it becomes apparent that the Nevadan *Xenoceltites* do not differ from those recovered from Stensiöfjellet, as no distinction can be made based on their biometric parameters (see figs 5 and 6). Figure 5A shows that material recovered in Palomino plot in between specimens from Stensiöfjellet /NE Elko County and WALD2. Considering the morphological similarities visible between the less well-preserved Palomino material (Jattiot et al., 2017, pl. 1 figs P-AD) and specimens from NE Elko County/Stensiöfjellet, it would be reasonable to assume that material from Palomino represent the same species as the one from Stensiöfjellet /NE Elko County. As such, this could potentially support the claim that specimens from WALD2 do in fact simply represent intraspecific variation of *X. subevolutus*.

Figure 4: Linear discriminant analysis of: A) the ornamentation-based morphological groups recognized in each of our Spitzbergen sections; B) material from each section.

Figure 5: A) boxplot and B) linear discriminant analysis comparing material from our Spitzbergen sections with material recovered from Elko County (NE Nevada, Locatelli et al. in prep.) and from Palomino (data from Jattiot et al., 2017)

All these observations lead us to conclude that only one single species can in fact be recognized among our *Xenoceltites* specimens, and this species is to be found both in the high latitudes of Spitzbergen, as well as in the lower latitudes of NE Nevada. Linear models implemented on our entire Spitzbergen collection reveal that this species is characterised by an allometric growth, although juveniles with a diameter < 20 mm show an isometric growth for H and U, while more mature specimens ($D > 20$ mm) show an isometric growth for the umbilical width (U). A comparison with previous work allows us to identify this species as *Xenoceltites subevolutus* (*sensu* Jattiot et al., 2017). We agree with the latest synonymisations of Spath's original species (*X. gregoryi* and *X. spitzbergensis*) with the type species *X. subevolutus*; in fact, *X. gregoryi* was defined on the grounds of being more depressed and more evolute than *X. subevolutus*, with constrictions resembling crenulations, while *X. spitzbergensis* was originally said to resemble *X. gregoryi* but with coarser ornamentation and less compressed whorls (Spath, 1934). We observe an intergradation of all these morphologies within our sample and see them as part of the intraspecific variation explained by Buckmann's Law of

covariation and thus support Weitschat's more recent view of Spath's original species (in Jattiot et al., 2017).

Comparing our juvenile specimens to those of *X. variocostatus* ours present quite a different morphology, being consistently more serpenticonic, and presenting a less elliptical whorl section in combination with a more compressed and more evolute conch, even when equally coarsely ornamented. We therefore agree with Jenks & Brayard's (2018) hypothesis to maintain *X. variocostatus* as a separate taxon which, as postulated by Jattiot et al. (2017), might even be considered an entirely different genus, given the morphological differences with any known late Smithian *Xenoceltites*. However, as mentioned by Jenks & Brayard (2018), additional material is needed to draw sound conclusions on this taxon.

Figure 6: Scatterplot comparing our Spitzbergen collection with material from NE Elko County and Palomino Ridge (NE Nevada).

SYSTEMATIC PALEONTOLOGY

Taxonomic descriptions follow the terminology of Arkell et al., 1957 and Klug et al., 2015. For clarifications regarding the conventional abbreviations used, the reader is referred to Matthews (1973).

Order AMMONOIDEA Zittel, 1884
 Suborder CERATITINA Hyatt, 1884
 Superfamily Xenodiscaceae Frech, 1902
 Family Xenoceltitidae Spath, 1930

Genus *Xenoceltites* Spath, 1930

Genotype and type species: *Xenoceltites subevolutus*, Spath = *Xenodiscus cf. comptoni* (non Diener) Frebold, 1930, p. 14, pl. iii, figs. 1 (lectotype), 2, 3.

Xenoceltites subevolutus Spath, 1930 (Plate 1, Figs. P-AD)
 (Figs. 7-10)

- ?1929 *Ophiceras matheri* Mathews, p. 4, pl. 1, figs. 38–40.
- ?1929 *Xenodiscus douglasensis* Mathews, p. 5, pl. 1, figs. 5–7.
- .1930 *Xenodiscus* cf. *comptoni* Diener; Frebald, p. 14, pl. III, figs. 1, 2, 2a, 3.
- .1930 *Lecanites* cf. *ophioneus* Waagen; Frebald, p. 12, pl. III, figs. 4, 4a, 5.
- .1934 *Xenoceltites subevolutus* Spath, p. 130, pl. II, fig. 2; pl. VIII, fig.2; pl. IX, fig.4; pl.XI, fig.2.
- . 1934 *Xenoceltites gregoryi* Spath, p. 129, pl. VI, fig. 4,5; pl. XI, figs 3,4,6.
- . 1934 *Xenoceltites spitsbergensis* Spath, p. 128, pl. 9, figs 1, 2; pl. 11, figs 5, 7, 8.
- .1961 *Xenoceltites subevolutus* Spath, Tozer, p. 53, pl. XVI, fig. 1a,b.
- .1978 *Xenoceltites spitsbergensis* Spath, Weitschat & Lehmann, p. 94, pl. 11, figs 3b, 4, 5.
- .1978 *Xenoceltites subevolutus* Spath, Weitschat & Lehmann, p. 95, pl. 11, figs 1, 2, 3.
- .1990 *Xenoceltites subevolutus* Spath, Dagys & Ermakova, p. 23, pl. 5, fig. 4.
- .1990 *Xenoceltites matheri* Mathews, Dagys & Ermakova, p. 24, pl. 5, figs 5-10.
- . 1994 *Xenoceltites subevolutus* Spath, Tozer, p. 52, pl. 36, figs 3–8.
- . 2010 *Xenoceltites* sp., Stephen et al., fig. 7 d.
- ? 2010 *Xenoceltites* cf. *variocostatus* Brayard & Bucher, Brühwiler, Bucher, & Goudemand, p. 411, Fig. 7(1,2).
- v. 2012 *Xenoceltites* cf. *variocostatus* Brayard & Bucher, Brühwiler et al., p. 34, fig. 24A-AG.
- . 2013 *Xenoceltites* sp. indet. A, Brayard et al., p. 160, fig. 19a-c.
- . 2015 *Xenoceltites subevolutus* Spath, Piazza, p. 48, Pl. I, figs a-c.
- . 2017 *Xenoceltites subevolutus* Spath, Jattiot et al., p. 10, pl. 1, figs P-AD.
- .2017 *Xenoceltites subevolutus* Spath, Piazza et al., p. 110, fig. 4a, b.
- . 2018 *Xenoceltites subevolutus* Spath, Jenks & Brayard, p. 21, fig. 21.
- . 2021 *Xenoceltites subevolutus* Spath, Brayard et al., p. 5, fig. 4A-P.

Occurrence: This species is very common in the high palaeolatitudes where it is found in what is today recognized as the *tardus* zone (Tozer, 1967). Our collection was found in association with a

prevalence of *Wasatchites* and *Hemiprionites*. *X. subevolutus* has been observed in Spitzbergen (Spath 1934; Frebald 1930; Weitschat & Lehmann, 1978; Piazza, 2015, Piazza et al., 2017; this work), in the Canadian Arctic (Tozer 1961; 1994) and in Siberia (Dagys & Ermakova 1990). It has also been found in the lower latitudes, in both late Smithian zones, i.e. in the *Anasibirites* zone (though in much poorer quantities) and in the *Glyptophyseras/Xenoceltites* zone of: Utah (Mathews 1927, Stephen et al. 2010, Brayard et al. 2013, 2021), NE Nevada (Jattiot et al. 2017; Jenks & Brayard 2018; Locatelli et al. *in prep*) and potentially Salt Range (Brühwiler et al. 2012) and South Tibet (Brühwiler et al. 2010).

Description: Serpenticonic, evolute *Xenoceltites*, moderately compressed with moderately embracing whorls. Whorl section ranges from circular to ovoid/sub-rectangular. The conch features a rounded venter, rounded ventral shoulders and slightly convex to parallel flanks. The umbilicus is wide, moderately shallow, with oblique walls and rounded umbilical shoulders.

Ornamentation observed on our specimens shows markedly projected constrictions that can be more (e.g. Fig. 7F-H) or less (e.g. Fig. 7S-T) pronounced on juveniles and fade away on the more mature whorls, which often appear almost completely smooth. Faint distant radial to prosiradiate ribs are visible on the inner whorls and on some mature specimens (e.g. Fig. 8 Q-S). Sometimes ribs on the smaller specimens can be very pronounced, giving the juvenile an almost “bumpy” appearance (e.g. Fig.7 AD-AF), while other times they are barely visible, so that juveniles can appear almost smooth (e.g. Fig. 9 D-G).

Suture line ceratitic with broad and rounded saddles. Lobes are rarely well preserved.

Figure 7: A-BN: *Xenoceltites subevolutus*; all specimens recovered from STA2. A-C: STA 2-43; D-E: STA 2-48; F-H: STA 2-16 (suture line mirrored); I-J: STA 2-13; K-L: STA 2-37; M-N: STA 2-25; O-R: STA 2-45; S-T: STA 2-4; U-W: STA 2-42; X-AA: STA 2-34; AB-AC: STA 2-52; AD-AF: STA 2-51; AG-AI: STA 2-14; AJ-AK: STA 2-36; AL-AO: STA 2-23; AP-AR: STA 2-41; AS-AU: STA 2-26; AV-AX: STA2.22 (suture line mirrored); AY-AZ: STA 2-12; BA-BB: STA 2-5; BC-BD: STA 2-39; BE-BF: STA 2-32; BG-BH: STA 2-40; BI-BL: STA 2-35b; BM-BN: STA 2-8. Vertical scale = 1 cm. Horizontal scale beneath each suture line corresponds to 5 mm.

Figure 8: A-AD: *Xenoceltites subevolutus*; all specimens from STA2, except AE-AF. A-B: STA2.3; C-F: STA2.1; G-I: STA 2-18; J-L: STA2.2; M-P: STA2.9 (mirrored suture line); Q-S: STA2.6; T-W: STA2.19; X-Y: STA2.10; Z-AB: STA2.11; AC-AD: STA2.29; AE-AF: STC1.18 (from section STC1). Vertical scale = 1 cm. Horizontal scale beneath each suture line corresponds to 5 mm

Figure 9: A-AQ: *Xenoceltites subevolutus*; all specimens recovered from STC1. A-C: STC 1-22; D-G: STC 1-13 (suture line mirrored); H-I: STC1.11; J-L: STC1.12 (suture line mirrored); M-O: STC1.3; P-R: STC1.20; S-T: STC1.9; U-W: STC1.10; X-Z: STC1.16; AA-AB: STC1.8; AC-AE: STC1.4; AF-AI: STC1.5 (suture line mirrored); AJ-AK: STC1.6; AL-AN: STC1.17; AO-AQ: STC1.1. Vertical scale = 1 cm. Horizontal scale beneath each suture line corresponds to 5 mm.

Figure 10: A-O: *Xenoceltites subevolutus*. All specimens recovered from WALD2. A-D: WALD2.1 (suture line mirrored); E-G: WALD2.2; H-J: WALD2.3; K-M: WALD2.5. Vertical scale = 1 cm. Horizontal scale beneath each suture line corresponds to 5 mm.

CONCLUSION

Ninety-one well preserved specimens of *Xenoceltites* from three sections from Spitzbergen were analysed in this work, in order to add to the current understanding of the genus and therefore bring a contribution to the correlation of late Smithian ammonoid zones across latitudes.

Our analyses revealed the presence of only one species of *Xenoceltites* within our collection, i.e. *X. subevolutus*. The few specimens from section WALD2 could potentially represent another species, as their biometric parameters seem to set them aside from the rest of our specimens. However, their small number and their bad preservation do not allow us enough evidence to support this claim and they have thus been considered as part of the intraspecific variation of *X. subevolutus*. We agree with previous works that have supported the synonymisation of Spath's *X. gregoryi* and *X. spitzbergensis* with *X. subevolutus*, as we were able to identify the morphological characteristics that defined *X. gregoryi* and *X. spitzbergensis* within the intraspecific variation of our sample. A comparison of our specimens with *Xenoceltites* found in previous work, allows us to recognize the presence of these species both in the higher and the lower paleolatitudes (where it can be found in both the *Anasibirites* and the *Glyptophyseras* zone) thus allowing us to establish

its cosmopolitanism. Additional analyses that take into account all known xenoceltitids, i.e. *X. subevolutus* Spath, *X. variocostatus* Brayard & Bucher, *C. youngi* Jenks and Brayard, and *G. sinuatum* Waagen are needed in order to allow for global biostratigraphical correlations rooted in a well-grounded taxonomy.

DECLARATIONS

AVAILABILITY OF DATA AND MATERIAL

The described material is stored in the PIMUZ, Paleontological Institute and Museum of the University of Zurich, Karl Schmid-Strasse 4, 8006 Zurich, Switzerland. All self-acquired data analysed during this study are included in the supplementary information files.

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AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

LL collected measurements data, implemented the analyses, interpreted the results and executed most of the writing. HB supervised this project, collected the material from the field and aided in the

taxonomical interpretation. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Chapter IV

Ammonoid size variation during the Smithian-Spathian (Early Triassic)
climatic upheavals

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Ammonoid size variation during the Smithian-Spathian (Early Triassic) climatic upheavals

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Abstract.—The Smithian-Spathian time interval was a time of major climatic upheavals which climaxed during an extinction event in the late Smithian (.ca 249 Ma) that profoundly impacted nekto-pelagic organisms. Biotic crises associated with strong climatic changes are normally accompanied by significant changes in size, as a result of the associated biotic and abiotic stressors. Body size is in fact affected by a wide array of environmental parameters and plays a fundamental role in the shaping of the ecosystem, as it impacts the physiology, ecology and evolution of organisms. This study aims to investigate for the first time the global response of ammonoids' body size through the Smithian and the Spathian, on the basis of revised published and unpublished material that is grounded into a robust stratigraphy. A statistically significant size decrease was detected between the Smithian and the Spathian, mostly concentrated in the latest Smithian through the middle Spathian. Contrary to expectations, no direct correlation with temperature could be established for the observed size patterns. The statistically significant size decrease of the early Spathian, conforms to the assumption that taxa tend to arise at sizes smaller than their optimum after an extinction. Interspecific competition associated with the explosive radiation of ammonoids that took place in the Spathian may have contributed to the lack of recovery to bigger sizes during that time, as a consequence of the lower energetic demands of smaller species. Changing predation pressure from Smithian to Spathian, possibly associated to bacteria-dominated primary productivity during the Smithian, may also have influenced size changes at the stage level. While the impact of changing environmental conditions cannot be excluded, our results seem to support a predominantly biotic driven evolution of ammonoids' body size throughout the considered time interval.

Key words: Smithian, Spathian, climatic upheavals, late Smithian extinction, body size, ammonoids

I. INTRODUCTION

The Early Triassic (251.902-247.2 Ma; Cohen *et al.*, 2013- updated-) was a time of faunal recovery following the Permian-Triassic boundary mass extinction (PTBME, 252 Ma; Burgess, Bowring & Shen, 2014), which led to the loss of 79% of marine invertebrate genera during the Changhsingian (Payne & Clapham, 2012) and an estimate of 81% marine species (Stanley, 2016). For many benthic organisms, biotic recovery was moderate during the Early Triassic and accelerated at the beginning of the Middle Triassic (e.g. Hallam, 1991; Senowbari-Daryan *et al.*, 1993; Flügel, 1994; Retallack, 1995; Benton, Tverdokhlebov & Surkov, 2004; Payne *et al.*, 2004; Hautmann, 2007; Hofmann, Hautmann & Bucher, 2015; Friesenbichler, Hautmann & Bucher, 2021); in contrast, the first diversification pulses of nektonic organisms such as ammonoids (Brayard *et al.*, 2006, 2009b; Brühwiler *et al.*, 2010a) and conodonts (Orchard, 2007) occurred within the first 1.5 Myr after the extinction (but see Altiner *et al.*, 2021, where patterns of extinction and recovery of benthic foraminiferas were reported to resemble those of nektonic organisms). The distinct recovery dynamics between nektonic and benthic groups may be a consequence of the higher interspecific competition proper of nektonic forms, particularly if interspecific competition was the main driver of diversification during the early stages of community restoration (Hautmann *et al.*, 2015). On the other hand, the rapid recovery of diversity in ammonoids has also been interpreted to result from their exploitation of a wide range of trophic resources and niches (Brayard *et al.*, 2009b). The presence of multi-level trophic networks in the Early Triassic (Scheyer *et al.*, 2014) is consistent with this hypothesis.

Nevertheless, ammonoid recovery was interrupted in the late Smithian (*ca.* 2.5 Myr after the PTBME; Ovtcharova *et al.*, 2006; Widmann *et al.*, 2020), when severe climate changes associated with perturbations in the carbon cycle led to an extinction that caused the biggest recorded ammonoid turnover of the Early Triassic (Brayard, A., & Bucher, 2015). This stepwise extinction spanned 600 kyr (Widmann *et al.*, 2020) and decimated nekto-pelagic organisms, with a magnitude comparable to that of the PTBME

(Orchard 2007; Brayard *et al.*, 2006, 2009b). Only four ammonoid lineages survived, represented by a limited number of species: xenoceltitids (the potential ancestor of most Spathian taxa; Galfetti *et al.*, 2007a), sageceratids, palaeophyllitids and proptychitids (Brayard, A., & Bucher, 2015). Cosmopolitanism increased (Tozer, 1981; Brayard *et al.* 2013) in association with the ammonoid diversity collapse that took place at the Smithian/Spathian boundary (SSB, *ca.* 249 Ma; Widmann *et al.*, 2020), whilst in the earliest Spathian diversity levels started to increase again alongside a renewed endemism accompanied by a shift from suboxic to more oxic conditions (Brayard *et al.*, 2006; Galfetti *et al.*, 2007a). The cause of the late Smithian extinction pulse is still under debate (Widmann *et al.*, 2020; H. Bucher ongoing work). The late Smithian to early Spathian time interval is distinguished by a global, positive C-isotope excursion (622 ± 137 kyr long; Widmann *et al.*, 2020) associated with a cooling event that started during the early late Smithian and peaked at the Smithian-Spathian boundary (SSB). This was accompanied by a matching positive oxygen isotope peak measured in biogenic phosphate (Galfetti *et al.*, 2007b; Romano *et al.*, 2013; Goudemand *et al.*, 2019). While the middle Smithian was a time characterized by a thermal maximum and humid conditions (and a spore dominated vegetation), the late Smithian-early Spathian saw a shift to dryer and cooler conditions (and to a gymnosperm-dominated palynoflora) associated with a more homogeneous Spathian climate (Hochuli & Vigran 2010; Hermann *et al.*, 2011; Romano *et al.*, 2013; Hochuli *et al.*, 2016; Goudemand *et al.*, 2019). A global heterochronous sedimentary gap straddling the SSB in shelf environments suggests that the cooling may have built up to a short ice age and a subsequent glacio-eustatic regression (Widmann *et al.*, 2020). However, as indicated by the oxygen isotopic record, the onset of the nektonic extinction in the early late Smithian *Wasatchites* Zone, preceded the cooling phase of the late late Smithian. This indicates that while cooling may have had a strong impact on the Smithian-Spathian biotic crisis, it was likely not the trigger for it (Goudemand *et al.*, 2019).

A common repercussion of mass extinctions is the smaller size of surviving species (e.g. Twitchett 2007; He *et al.*, 2010; Metcalfe, Twitchett & Price-Lloyd, 2011; Payne *et al.*, 2011; Song, Tong & Chen,

2011; but see Brayard *et al.*, 2010, 2015; Schaal *et al.*, 2016), usually referred to as the *Lilliput effect* (Urbanek 1993). This effect is usually interpreted as a consequence of the environmental biotic and abiotic disturbances associated to climatic changes, such as temperatures maxima, salinity fluctuations, oxygen depletion, acidification, or primary productivity disturbances (Kinne 1970, 1971; Urbanek 1993; Twitchett 2007; Harries & Knorr 2009; He *et al.*, 2010; Schaal *et al.*, 2016) for which size reduction is the normal phenotypic response to unfavourable growth conditions (Urbanek 1993). Body size is in fact controlled by many such environmental parameters, among which temperature (Rosa *et al.*, 2012), oxygen availability (Atkinson & Sibly, 1997), food availability (Wood & O'Dor, 2000; Rosa *et al.*, 2012) and calcium carbonate saturation level (Gazeau *et al.*, 2007; Fabry *et al.*, 2008) are the prominent ones affecting marine organisms.

A better understanding of the relationship between body size and environmental factors evolution can lead to a better understanding of the ecosystem response to the ongoing climate change. The pattern towards smaller body size observed in the fossil record during times of environmental stress is in fact also observed today as a consequence of the current climate change. Recent studies on extant organisms have observed the development of smaller body size widespread across different taxa in response to the changing of environmental conditions caused by global warming (Loehr, Hofmeyr & Henen, 2007; Jokieli *et al.*, 2008; Daufresne, Lengfellner & Sommer, 2009; Ries, Cohen & McCorkle, 2009; Shi *et al.*, 2010; Gardner *et al.*, 2011; Sheridan & Bickford, 2011). Changes in the development and growth of organisms can easily trigger trophic cascades that will influence the ecosystem, the global ecology, and, in turn, the related anthropogenic activities. It is therefore of fundamental importance to reach a better understanding of the interaction between climate change and the different taxa and the impact that heterogeneous size change may have across trophic levels (Sheridan & Bickford, 2011).

Body size plays a key role in the evolution, the ecology and the physiology of organisms (Schmidt-Nielsen, 1984). One of the most important aspects is the influence of size over trophic relations of organisms and over the structure of food webs (Warren *et al.*, 2005; Woodward *et al.*, 2005; Arim

et al., 2010). Size is related to a species' productivity, its energetic demands, life history traits, longevity, spatial use of resources, biomass abundance or interactions with the other components of the food web, such as prey and predators (Woodward *et al.*, 2005). For some marine organisms such as ammonoids, body size has also been interpreted as an important determinant of swimming speed (Jacobs & Chamberlain, 1996), which affects predatory strategies as well as their escape abilities and vulnerability with respect to predators (Greene, 1986). As such, body size influences the position that species occupy in the trophic pyramid (Elton, 1927; Sholto-Douglas *et al.*, 1991; France, Chandler & Peters, 1998; Warren *et al.*, 2005; Trebilco *et al.*, 2013). Because morphological development hoists most aquatic species up the trophic chain during their ontogeny, ecological comparisons among species are best made at the comparable maturity life stage or at "*a fixed proportion of maximum body size*" (Jennings 2002, p. 88).

Maximal size measurements can thus be used as a proxy to infer changes of trophic level of a clade through time and, more generally, to evaluate the impact of unstable environments on the clade (which, in turn, allows a better understanding of the related palaeoenvironmental and climatic drivers). Size changes among Early Triassic clades have been the object of discussion by many previous studies. While some have observed a reduction of size in various clades following the PTBE (Twitchett 1999, 2007; Fraiser & Bottjer, 2004; Pruss & Bottjer 2004; Fraiser, Twitchett & Bottjer, 2005; Payne, 2005; He *et al.*, 2007, 2010, 2016; Metcalfe *et al.* 2011; Payne *et al.*, 2011; Chen *et al.*, 2013; Leu, Bucher & Goudemand, 2019), others (Brayard *et al.*, 2010, 2015) report new evidence that speaks against the global Early Triassic size decrease supported by previous studies (Fraiser & Bottjer 2004; Fraiser *et al.*, 2005; Payne, 2005; Twitchett, 2007). Brayard *et al.*, (2010, 2015) and Schaal *et al.*, (2016) bring evidence of a Lilliput effect that did not extend up to the Smithian and the Spathian and both Schaal *et al.*, (2016) and Leu *et al.*, (2019) report clade-specific size responses to the environmental pressures of the extinction aftermath. Most of these studies, however, focus on the main marine invertebrate clades (such as bivalves, brachiopods, gastropods or conodonts) in a lower resolution time frame and commonly in the immediate aftermath of

the PTBME; Leu *et al.*, (2019) analysed conodonts size variation at a much higher resolution through the Smithian-Spathian boundary (SSB).

In the wake of such pioneer research, this study aims to investigate for the first time the response of ammonoids to climatic disturbances at the finer time resolution of Smithian and Spathian substages. Through an attentive review of published material and the inclusion of unpublished available data the evolution of ammonoid body size will be analysed on a global scale, based on the most recent zonations available, and taking recent or new taxonomic synonymisations into account (to minimize taxonomic oversplitting). Statistically significant changes in body size will be discussed in the context of the climatic upheavals and the paleoecology of the late Early Triassic, and an attempt to understand the relative impact of abiotic and biotic changes on ammonoids' size evolution will be made.

II. PALEOGEOGRAPHICAL SETTINGS

The Early Triassic is characterised by a relatively simple and stable Pangean palaeogeography (Fig. 1; see also Brayard *et al.*, 2009a). The oceanic domain of Panthalassa (i.e. the Palaeopacific), constituted roughly 90% of the end-Permian ocean, while the remaining 10% was occupied by the Tethyan oceanic domain, centred on the Equator,

encroached in the crescent-shaped Pangea and connected to the East with Panthalassa (Scotese & Schettino, 2017). Rifting phases that progressed from the Late Carboniferous throughout the Triassic led to the gradual opening of the Neotethys and the simultaneous northward subduction of the Palaeotethys below the Eurasian margin, which was completed in the Middle Triassic. Throughout the Early Triassic, several microcontinents and terranes drifted across the Tethys (Sengör, 1984) and the Panthalassa, moving towards convergence zones (e.g. see Nichols and Silberling, 1979; Tozer 1982; Kojima, 1989; Natal'in, 1993; Parfenov *et al.*, 1993; Belasky *et al.*, 2002; Yancey *et al.*, 2005; Scotese & Schettino, 2017). Following the rifting phases within the Tethyan area, an almost continuous belt of northward-drifting continental blocks separated from the northern Gondwana margin, known as Cimmerian microcontinents, which encompassed today's Iran, parts of Afghanistan and Tibet and western Indochina (Şengör, 1979, 1984; Stampfli, Marcoux & Baud, 1991; Metcalfe, 1996; Besse *et al.*, 1998; Stampfli and Borel, 2002).

Drifting on the eastern edge of the Tethyan domain was the Cathaysian microcontinent (Metcalfe, 1996, 1999), encompassing the South China block, most of Indochina and East Malaya (Sengör 1979, 1984; Metcalfe, 1996; Xu *et al.*, 2015), while on the western side of the Pangea the Chulitna terranes

Figure 1: Early Triassic Pangea. Red dots show the paleolocations from which the specimens included in the dataset were recovered. Map courtesy of Christian Verard.

(part of today's Alaska) were drifting in the Panthalassa in a sub-equatorial position.

III. MATERIAL AND METHODS

(1) Dataset

The original database on which global analyses are based includes both published and, in smaller amount, unpublished material (the latter stored in the Paleontological Institute and Museum of Zurich). The data were mostly drawn from relatively recent monographs, journal articles and research papers grounded in a detailed stratigraphy. Up to date taxonomical synonymisation of older monographs found in recent works or specifically attempted for the purpose, where preservation allowed, (H. Bucher and T. Brühwiler, pers. Comm., indicated in the dataset) was also taken into account. Where a taxonomic identification was only possible at the genus or family level, the taxon was left in open nomenclature.

The locations from which measurements were collected and the relative references are given in Table 1. From each considered location, the biggest specimen for each occurring species was recorded and both the phragmocone diameter (where available) and the maximal shell diameter were measured. In specific cases, an estimation of the maximal size that the species likely reached was either given by the author or could be estimated from the illustrations in the plates or from the available material; the value was then included in the dataset.

Statistical analyses were performed on a species level: only taxa in non-open nomenclature were considered and because the analyses were done on a global scale, each species is kept only once. This leaves us with an effective dataset of 514 specimens, of which 316 are Smithian taxa and 198 are Spathian taxa. For the analyses, the largest of the above-mentioned diameter measurements is considered. Although each sample in the dataset has been provided with the zone in which it was recovered, a global correlation at the zone level for both Smithian and Spathian has not yet been properly developed (Brayard *et al.*, 2006, H. Bucher, personal communication). Hence, the size analyses were implemented at the substage level (Smithian and Spathian, according to Tozer's (1967)

subdivision) which were in turn divided in the smaller time bins recognized by the most recent literature (e.g. Brühwiler *et al.*, 2012c; Brühwiler, Bucher & Krystyn, 2012b; Jattiot *et al.*, 2017) i.e. early, middle, late Smithian/Spathian

(2) Analysis of maximal size through time

To investigate size change throughout the considered time bins, the size data were converted to a logarithmic scale (base 10). This is a conventional approach when analysing evolution of body sizes, as it often allows to obtain normal distributions that stand in accordance with the geometric normality of biological variation (Gingerich 2000). All analyses were implemented in R-Studio (Version 1.0.153). Normality was checked by means of a Shapiro test. Size changes between two chronologically subsequent distributions were investigated by means of a two-sample t-test (or Welch test, in case of samples with non-equal variances), assessing whether the two univariate samples are derived from populations with equal means (Hammer & Harper 2006). To better evaluate the power of the t-test, i.e. to better estimate the ability of the test to reject the null hypothesis given the size of each considered sample, the influence of sample size on the width of the resulting confidence intervals was also inspected.

IV. RESULTS

When analysing the evolution of body size within the smaller time bins (early, middle, late Smithian/Spathian), the hypothesis that each set of data has been drawn from a Gaussian distribution could not be rejected. Also for the late Smithian, whose histogram shows a more predominantly right skewed distribution (Fig. 2C; skewness 0.78) the assumption of a normal distribution could not be disproven. Due to the absence of normality violations, we find the implementation of a parametric two-sample t-test or that of a Welch test justified and suitable to obtain reliable results. The t-test reveals a significant size decrease between the late Smithian and the early Spathian, between the early and the middle Spathian and between the Smithian and the Spathian taken as a whole. A closer analysis into the width of the 95% confidence

Figure 2: Histograms of the ammonoids' size distribution in each considered time bin. Notice the more prominently right skewed distribution of the late Smithian. All distributions are normal according to the Shapiro-test.

intervals (CIs; Fig. 3) around the mean values of the distributions adds further insight on the output of the test. As seen in Fig. 3 all CIs are relatively large; this brings further validation to our results. In fact, for those cases for which the null hypothesis was rejected (late Smithian-early Spathian, early-middle Spathian, Smithian and Spathian) large CIs indicate that the means difference is large enough to be differentiated already with the provided sample size (and a bigger sample size could only further corroborate the results). On the other hand, for the cases where the null hypothesis is not rejected (i.e.

where no statistically significant size change can be affirmed – between early Smithian-Middle Smithian, middle Smithian-late Smithian and middle Spathian-late Spathian) large confidence intervals support the claim that a trend in size change cannot be corroborated with the data at our disposal. In fact, in these cases, large CIs likely result from the combination of small sample sizes with a small mean size differences. This goes to reiterate that a non-rejection of the null-hypothesis does not disprove the actual existence of significant size

Figure 3: On the y axis the 95% CIs around the means' difference of each samples pair (see legend) is given. The x axis gives the size of the smaller sample of each pair. All CIs are relatively large. For the two cases where the null hypothesis is rejected and a statistically significant size change is detected (green and light blue lines) large CIs indicate that the means difference is large enough to be differentiated already with the provided sample size and there is thus a very large probability for the trend observed to be indeed significant. The large CIs of the black, pink and orange cases, for which the t-test gives a non-significant result, i.e. where the null hypothesis is NOT rejected large CIs likely result from the combination of small sample sizes with a small mean size differences. They thus support the claim that a trend in size change cannot be proven by the data at our disposal.

changes, but no certain claim can be made in that regard with the data at our disposal.

Boxplots (Fig. 4) reveal that size distribution in the middle Smithian holds the broadest size disparity while the late Smithian, on the other hand, displays the lowest size variance, and holds the largest median among the samples. Middle Spathian shows the second lowest size disparity, though with the lowest median among all time bins. A direct correlation between taxonomic richness and size disparity is further validated by the increase in width of the lower and upper quartile with increasing number of taxa (Fig. 5). Overall, Smithian

time intervals show much more disparity in the width of the lower and upper quantiles, while quantile width throughout the Spathian seems to display higher stability.

V. DISCUSSION

On evolutionary timescales body size changes are commonly viewed as a consequence of both changes within species following natural selection and differences in speciation and extinction rates of large and small species. In turn, extinction and speciation are normally driven by ecological processes that affect the ecological niches of organisms and, as a consequence, the ecological failure or success of different species (Maurer, Brown & Rusler, 1992). Ecological processes include an abiotic (environmental) and a biotic component, both of which have been shown to directly impact body size on a smaller timescale (e.g. Ansell, 1968; Adams, 1980; Rosa *et al.*, 2012). Among the environmental parameters that can affect body size, temperature has so far been proven to have the biggest influence on extant cephalopods (Wood & O'Dor, 2000; Rosa *et al.*, 2012). In comparison, net primary productivity, resource availability, seasonality and competition only seem to play a limited role (Rosa *et al.*, 2012). Rosa *et al.* (2012) observed a strong negative correlation between temperature and extant cephalopods' body size, in agreement with Atkinson's (1994) "temperature-size rule", according to which lower temperatures result in lower growth rates and delayed maturation, but also in larger body sizes.

Impact of temperature on ammonoids' body size throughout Smithian and Spathian cannot be excluded from our results, however no direct correlation can be established either. As previously mentioned the Smithian- Spathian transition time is characterized by 1) a cooling interval in the early Smithian; 2) a thermal maximum in the middle Smithian (contrary to Sun *et al.*'s (2012) assertion of a late Smithian Thermal Maximum) with warm temperatures persisting until the early late Smithian; 3) a second cooling interval in the late late Smithian-early Spathian; 4) mid-Spathian temperatures comparable to those of mid-Smithian time; 5) renewed cooling around the late Spathian (Romano *et al.*, 2013; Song *et al.*, 2014; Goudemand *et al.*, 2019). According to Atkinson's rule, we would expect a trend towards decreased body size

Figure 4: Boxplots of the analysed distributions for the different time bins. Arrows indicate the time intervals for which a statistically significant size change could be detected (by means of a two-sample t-test or Welch test).

between the early and the middle Smithian and between the early and the middle Spathian, as well as an increased body size in the late Smithian and late Spathian. Even though medians of both the late Smithian and late Spathian do show a slight increase in their value (Fig. 4), no statistical significance could be established in these cases. On the other hand, our analysis does show a statistically significant size reduction between the early and middle Spathian. While the warmer temperatures of the middle Spathian with its smallest observed median size would seem to agree with expectations, it is worth mentioning that field research carried out by the authors (unpublished) has shown this to be a time when a new significant intra Spathian ammonoid turnover takes place. This makes it difficult to isolate temperature as being the predominant driver of body size. In fact, in the presence of a faunal turnover new taxa tend to originate at smaller sizes. This claim would seem to agree with the statistically significant size decrease detected between the late Smithian and the early Spathian. Development of smaller sizes stands in obvious disagreement with expectations of a temperature driven body size evolution. However, it conforms to

the empirical observation that after an extinction new taxa tend to arise at sizes smaller than their optimum. This is commonly explained by the constraints that apply to larger, more structurally complex and specialized species which have lower adaptability and thus represent unsuitable ancestral species (Stanley, 1973a). Moreover, our results give what seems to be a statistically well-grounded absence of size change between early and middle Smithian, when temperatures reached their maximum. Surprisingly, this time also corresponds to ammonoids' greatest taxonomic richness and size disparity and includes some of the largest sizes of our dataset (Fig. 4; see also Brayard *et al.*, 2006 and Bucher *et al.*, 2013). All things considered, there does not seem to be enough evidence to support a temperature control over size changes.

A comparison on the substage level reveals a statistically significant size decrease in the Spathian. The absence of a recovery to bigger sizes throughout Spathian is paradoxical to say the least. The Spathian substage not only has a duration of *ca.* 2.5 to 3 Myr (more than half of the duration of the entire Early Triassic; Ovtcharova *et al.*, 2006), but it is also characterised by relatively more stable

Figure 5: The taxonomic richness per quantile in each time interval (denoted by different symbols) is here plotted against the width of the different quartiles (indicated by the different colours). The graph shows that the larger the taxonomic richness, the larger the size variation in the lower (0%-25%, yellow line) and upper (75%-100%; blue line) quartile.

environmental conditions compared to the Smithian (Romano *et al.*, 2013; Goudemand *et al.* 2019). As predicted by classical r-K selection theories, times of stable environmental conditions normally lead to populations composed of larger individuals (Pianka, 1970; Adams, 1980). The effect of stable environmental conditions appears to be reflected in the relatively stable width of the quartiles throughout the Spathian. However, the consistently smaller size maintained all through the duration of this substage would seem to contradict expectations of an environmental control on size as seen from extant cephalopods (Rosa *et al.*, 2012). It is therefore plausible that biotic factors may have played the preponderant control over ammonoid body size throughout the considered time interval. The Spathian substage is characterised not only by a smaller ammonoids' body size, but also by a return to generic endemism, following the predominantly cosmopolitan distribution of the Smithian (Brayard *et al.*, 2006). A potential explanation to the change

observed in the biogeographic pattern, which may also have had an impact on the smaller Spathian body size of ammonoids, may be found in the biotic component of interspecific competition. An explosive radiation of new species such as the one seen at the base of the Spathian (Brayard *et al.*, 2006) may have led at first to a quick saturation of the niches left vacant from the late Smithian extinction (Valentine, 1971). Once the environmental niches were filled a gradually increasing intraspecific competition would have quickly led to further speciation. Intraspecific competition is in fact considered one of the main driver of diversification, as it promotes further niches differentiation (Stanley 1973b, Schluter, 1994, Emerson & Kolm, 2005, Bailey *et al.*, 2013, Hautmann *et al.*, 2015) thus increasing endemism and creating the biogeographical pattern of ammonoids' distribution detected in the Spathian. In presence of high intraspecific competition, it would then be reasonable to assume that a generally smaller size would be maintained throughout the Spathian despite the relatively more stable environment of this stage, as smaller sizes need less energy intake to sustain themselves in the highly competitive environment (Elton, 1927).

In addition to this, research on extant cephalopods has shown that predation affects body size a lot more than food availability (Dawe & Brodziak, 1998; Wood & O'Dor, 2000). According to Wood & O'Dor (2000) there exists a trade-off in coleoids between maturing early at a smaller size, and maturing late at a larger size. The earlier coleoids mature, the more prone they are to avoid predation and thus increase their fitness; thus, the lower the abundance of predators, the larger the size coleoids can develop. Since phylogenetic studies have suggested coleoids to be a more appropriate model than the *Nautilus* to interpret ammonoids' mode of life (Jacobs & Landman, 1993), it may be assumed that for ammonoids as well a larger size might speak for a relaxation of predators' induced stress. Of course, prey vulnerability is impacted by many different variables that rely on the predator's predatory strategies as well as on preys' and predators' swimming abilities, but, although simple, this remains a viable hypothesis. In the aftermath of the Permian-Triassic extinction and throughout the Early Triassic evidence can be found in the fossil record of a marine ecosystem which did not consist of primary producers only, rather included enough

trophic levels that could allow the proliferation of large aquatic predators (Scheyer *et al.*, 2014). Scheyer *et al.* (2014) report the findings of large top carnivores and piscivorous taxa, such as Trematosauroida, throughout Smithian and Spathian, from lower to higher latitudes, as well as of lower latitudes Spathian Sauropterygia and Thalattosauria and of globally spread Spathian Ichthyopterygia. The latter, in particular, included species provided with the crushing dentition typical of durophagous organisms and with the specialization needed for manoeuvrable swimming and cruising in a pelagic marine environment (e.g., *Grippia longirostris*, *Utatusaurus* and Omphalosauria; Buffrénil, Mazin & De Ricqles, 1987; Massare, 1987; Motani, 1997; Sander & Faber, 2003; Nakajima, Houssaye & Endo, 2014), characteristics that made them likely ammonoid predators. Furthermore, Nakajima & Izumi (2014) recently found various coprolites in the Spathian of the Osawa Formation (Japan). They suggested that the size variation observed in these coprolites may be an indication of the presence of a hierarchy of marine carnivores, the larger ones having been probably excreted by large fishes or marine reptiles akin to the basal Ichthyosaur *U. hataii*. Further marine fish and reptile assemblages from the Chaohu locality (South China) dating back to Smithian-Spathian times are also reported by Benton *et al.* (2013). In addition, Brayard *et al.*, (2017) brought to light a complex, phylogenetically diverse marine ecosystem from the early Spathian of Idaho (North America), which incorporates a trophically complete ecosystem, from lower-level primary producers to top predators (such as Ichthyosauria or Chondrichthyans).

Overall, while the Smithian is mainly dominated by the diversification of sparse survivors and some disaster taxa of osteichthyan, (remnants of the Permian extinction; Tintori *et al.*, 2014), the Spathian witnessed a first radiation of marine reptiles (the first representative being top predators such as Ichthyosauria and Nothosauria) accompanied by the potential onset of the appearance of several new osteichthyan taxa characterised by a wider variety of trophic and swimming specialisation (Jiang *et al.*, 2012; Kelley *et al.*, 2014; Tintori *et al.*, 2014; Romano *et al.*, 2016). This supports the existence of a complex trophic structure that is more developed in Spathian times compared to the Smithian. In turn, it substantiates

the hypothesis of a predation pressure on ammonoids that was much more intense during Spathian rather than during Smithian times, which might contribute to explain the observed size decrease at the substage level.

It is also worth mentioning that in addition to the fossil evidence found in the Spathian in support of a complex trophic structure, high levels of primary production have been postulated during Smithian (Meyer *et al.*, 2011). This potentially sustained anoxic and sulfidic conditions (Meyer, Kump & Ridgwell, 2008; Meyer *et al.*, 2011) and may have led, at least on a local scale, to a protracted predominance of the bacteria-dominated primary productivity, as observed in the southern Tethys in the aftermath of the Permian extinction (Grice *et al.*, 2005; Xie *et al.*, 2005). Such primary productivity is known to hold low nutrient value for higher trophic levels (Von Elert, Martin-Creuzburg & Le Coz, 2003; see also Payne & Van de Schootbrugge, 2007), thus not only potentially reducing predation stress on ammonoids during Smithian, but also setting an energetic limit to their body size. Prolonged low oxygen levels and poor food quality levels supporting low predation stress might then contribute to explain the absence of size changes throughout the Smithian and the overall smaller sizes at the substage level. However, the nature of primary productivity through our considered interval of time has yet to be established on a global scale, and any such hypothesis can only remain putative.

VI. CONCLUSION

- (1) The purpose of this study was to investigate how ammonoids' body size reacted to the climatic upheavals that took place during the Smithian and Spathian time. Statistical tests have revealed a clear decrease in size from Smithian to Spathian, mostly concentrated in the latest Smithian through mid Spathian.
- (2) No correlation between temperature and body size could be established. Contrary to expectations, the thermal maximum of the middle Smithian does not correspond to a decrease in size, and it is in fact the time of greatest size disparity and taxonomic richness of ammonoids when compared to the other time bins.

Data Location	References
Afghanistan	Collignon, 1973; Kummel, 1968a; Kummel & Erben, 1968
Albania	Arthaber, 1911
Canada BC Arctic Canada	Tozer, 1961, 1962, 1963*, 1965, 1967, 1984*, 1994
Chulitna Terranes (Alaska)	Nichols & Silberling, 1979
Chios Island (Greece)	Renz & Renz, 1948
Mangyshlak	Shevyrev, 1968
N.W. Caucasus	Shevyrev, 1995
Oman	Brühwiler <i>et al.</i> , 2012a
Siberia	Dagys & Ermakova, 1988, 1990
Timor	(Wanner, 1911; Welter, 1922; Kummel, 1968b; Nakazawa & Bando, 1968; Jattiot <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Jattiot, Bucher & Brayard, 2020)
Salt Range (Pakistan)	De Koninck, 1863a*, 1863b*; Mojsisovics, Waagen & Diener, 1895; Waagen, 1895; Noetling, 1905; Spath, 1934; Kummel, 1966; Guex, 1978; Pakistani-Japanese Research Group, 1985; Brühwiler <i>et al.</i> , 2011, 2012a
South China Block	(Chao, 1950*, 1959*; Tong & Zakharov, 2004; Tong, Zakharov & Wu, 2004; Brayard & Bucher, 2008; Monnet <i>et al.</i> , 2013; Shigeta <i>et al.</i> , 2014; Ji <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
South Primorye	Shigeta <i>et al.</i> , 2009; Shigeta & Kumagae, 2016
Spiti	(Diener, 1897; Krafft & Diener, 1909; Krystyn, Bhargava & Richoz, 2007a; Krystyn, Richoz & Bhargava, 2007b; Brühwiler <i>et al.</i> , 2010c, 2012b)
Spitzbergen	(Frebald, 1930; Spath, 1934; Kummel, 1961*; Weitschat & Lehmann, 1978; Mørk <i>et al.</i> , 1999; Weitschat, 2008; Piazza, 2015; Piazza, Hammer & Jattiot, 2017)
Tulong (Tibet)	Brühwiler, Bucher & Goudemand, 2010b
Western U.S. Basin (Sonoma Basin; Star Peak Group; California)	Smith, 1932; Kummel & Steele, 1962; Silberling & Wallace, 1969; Jenks, 2007; Brayard <i>et al.</i> , 2009a, 2013; Guex <i>et al.</i> , 2010; Jenks <i>et al.</i> , 2010, 2013; Stephen <i>et al.</i> , 2010; Monnet <i>et al.</i> , 2013; Jattiot <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Jenks & Brayard, 2018

Table 1: Localities and relative references from which dataset specimens were measured. References marked with a star indicate work that is not referenced in the dataset, which was however checked for synonyms and/or for the presence of bigger specimens.

- (3) The statistically significant size decrease of the early Spathian, agrees with the expectation that taxa tend to arise at sizes smaller than their optimum after an extinction event, due to the constraints that apply to larger, more structurally complex and less adaptable species.
- (4) The absence of a recovery to bigger sizes throughout the Spathian contradicts expectations of classical r-K selection theories that would predict larger individuals to predominate in the comparatively more stable environmental conditions of the Spathian substage.
- (5) When taking into account the change in the biogeographic patterns observed in Spathian ammonoid distribution, it is plausible that this may have been triggered by the gradually increasing interspecific competition that developed as a consequence of the explosive radiation of ammonoids after the late Smithian extinction. Intense intraspecific competition maintained throughout the Spathian would naturally lead to a predominance of smaller sizes during this substage, due to the lower energetic demands of smaller species, thus representing a plausible explanation to the maintenance of a smaller size.
- (6) An increase in predation stress in the Spathian may also have contributed to an overall smaller size compared to the Smithian.
- (7) All things considered, while the changing environmental conditions of this time certainly impacted body size changes, our results point to what seems to be a predominantly biotic driven size evolution.

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Conclusions

CONCLUSION

This dissertation provided new insights into the complex and mostly typologically based taxonomy of the pivotal early late Smithian *Anasibirites* ammonoid fauna. The *Anasibirites* fauna defines the first step of the late Smithian extinction and corresponds to the biggest intra-Triassic extinction-diversification cycle after the Permian. A sound taxonomy that takes into consideration both intraspecific and ontogenetic variation is fundamental to obtain a clear understanding of the processes that unfolded during the late Smithian extinction event and it will hopefully represent a stepping-stone for the development of sound biostratigraphical correlations across latitudes.

Based on an extensive and relatively well preserved collection from Nevada, we significantly reduced the number of extant species within the *Anasibirites* fauna: the genus *Gurleyites* Mathews (*sensu* Brayard et al. 2020), was recognised as a synonym of *Hemiprionites* Spath, and two valid late Smithian species are identified in the latter: *H. typus* and *H. slocomi*. Former *H. walcotti* has been identified as the smoother end member variant of the intraspecific variation of the type species *H. typus*, with which it has now been synonymized. *Gurleyites smithi* and *G. nodosus* have both been synonymised with *H. typus*, of which *G. nodosus* and the coarser specimens of *G. smithi* represent the coarser end member variants. A complete spectrum of morphological variation consistent with Buckmann's First Law of Covariation has now been documented for *H. typus*.

Furthermore, the controversial genus of *Anawasatchites* McLearn has been synonymised with *Wasatchites* Mathews, and within *Wasatchites* the species *W. tridentinus* Spath (1934), *W. deeleni* McLearn (1945) and *W. procurvus* McLearn (1945) were synonymized with the type species *W. perrini*. A new genus, *Eowasatchites*, so far including only one (type) species, i.e. *E. arcuatus*, is here reported in great quantities from the base of the early late Smithian. To this date, this genus has only been recovered from the low latitudes, specifically from South Tibet and NE Nevada. The large quantities retrieved from NE Nevada probably relate to the peculiar tectonic settings of the area, which are more likely to allow the preservation of an exceptionally complete Smithian ammonoid record compared to other locations. A first occurrence of *Aspenites* within the *Anasibirites* fauna has also been documented.

Finally, a smaller collection of *Xenoceltites* from Spitzbergen allowed us to present new material that proved to be composed solely of the single species *X. subevolutus* Spath. These specimens allowed us to confirm previous attempts of synonymisation of Spath's original *Xenoceltites* species *X. gregoryi* and *X. spitzbergensis* with *X. subevolutus*.

The taxonomical synonymisations that our unprecedentedly large collection of early late Smithian ammonoids allowed us to achieve, and the following reduction of early late Smithian valid species names point to what is likely to have been a much more severe first phase of the late Smithian extinction than previously assessed. In addition, comparison of our collective material with previous work from various paleolatitudes has allowed us to shed light onto the cosmopolitan character of the *Anasibirites* fauna at the species level (whilst previous studies had restricted their observations at the genus level). Our observations indicate that for most species recognized within our Nevadan collection cosmopolitanism was widespread at a species level too, and not only at a genus level. Correlatives of *Anasibirites kingianus* Waagen, *Wasatchites perrini* Mathews, *Wasatchites cf. distractus* Waagen, *Xenoceltites subevolutus* Spath and *Hemiprionites typus* Waagen, could be found both in high and low paleolatitudes. Exceptions to this are given by the three low latitudes species *Anasibirites multiformis* Welter, *Subvishnuites posterus* Brühwiler et al. and *Eowasatchites arcuatus* sp. nov. which, to this day, have yet to be reported from the Boreal Realm.

In the last additional chapter of this thesis a statistically significant decrease in ammonoids' size from Smithian to Spathian, mostly concentrated in the latest Smithian through mid Spathian was detected. Results point to

what seems to be a predominantly biotic driven size evolution, decoupled from the temperature patterns observed during this time. The absence of a recovery to bigger sizes during the Spathian contradicts expectations of classical r-K selection theories and is here explained by the combined effect of an increased predation stress during the Spathian and an increasingly intense intraspecific competition throughout this time. The latter would naturally lead to a predominance of smaller sizes during this substage due to the lower energetic demands of smaller species.

APPENDIX: SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Supplementary Material: Chapter I

The late Smithian (Early Triassic) ammonoid extinction: revision of *Hemiprionites* Spath, *Gurleyites* Mathews and *Arctoprionites* Spath (Prionitidae) based on new data from north-eastern Nevada

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“The late Smithian (Early Triassic) ammonoid extinction: revision of *Hemiprionites* Spath, *Gurleyites* Mathews and *Arctoprionites* Spath (Prionitidae) based on new data from north-eastern Nevada.”

Supplementary Material:

1. Growth analysis: a linear model

In order to test for isometric or allometric growth of each parameter a linear model is implemented on the log transformed data as a function of diameter. The fitting of each model was established by means of the reduced χ^2 value and double-checked through analysis of the plots autogenerated from the function (*autoplot()*) internal to the R library of *ggfortify*.

In order to understand how a simple regression can give us information on allometric or isometric growth, it should be kept in mind that an isometric curve is only a special case of the allometric curve (i.e. $y = b * x^a$) where the allometric exponent $a = 1$. In other words, the logarithmic transformation of an allometric curve (i.e. $\log(y) = \log(b) + a * \log(x)$) represents an isometric curve when the slope $a = 1$.

A linear model tests the null hypothesis that the slope $a = 0$. A significant p-value (i.e., p-value < 0.05) allows us to reject the null hypothesis. This basic knowledge can now be implemented in two ways. When considering the simple parameters U, H and W versus D, $a \neq 0$ indicates that there is in fact growth of the parameter in question with diameter. Once the p value is confirmed to be < 0.05, we can make use of the standard error and the slope values given by the output of the linear model to check for isometric or allometric growth. If the sum of the slope and of two times the standard error (2σ) yields a value still smaller than 1, we can assume that we have allometric growth, as the probability that growth is isometric would be in this case smaller than 2.5%. Considering preservation biases and measurement error, we here treat slopes with a value > 0.97 as reasonable approximations of isometric growth.

On the other hand, using U/D, H/D and W/D as a function of diameter would result in the following curves (taking U as an example parameter, i.e. $y = U$ and $x = D$):

The allometric curve: $U = b * D^a$

Would transform into: $\frac{U}{D} = b * \frac{D^a}{D} = b * D^{a-1}$

Which in logarithmic terms would become: $\log \frac{U}{D} = \log b + (a - 1) * \log D$

It follows that in order to have isometric growth (i.e. $a = 1$ in the first allometric curve) the slope of the logarithmic curve (i.e. $(a-1)$) should be 0. Hence, a p-value < 0.05 will definitely speak against isometric growth, as it rejects the null hypothesis (i.e. indicates that there is less than 5% probability for the null hypothesis to be correct). However, a p-value > 0.05 only allows us to claim that there is more than 5% probability that the slope is in fact 0 (hence no certain claim can be done). Both sets of parameters were here analysed, in order to have a solid corroboration of the results.

2. Results of growth analyses

The reduced χ^2 (consistently ≥ 0.96) indicates a very good fit of the linear models for all considered distributions (which could also be confirmed by the diagnostic plots of each model). For all morphs, table A1.1 shows that whorl compression remains more or less constant through ontogeny, since H/W shows no growth to very slight allometric growth (slope of 0.07 mm for *typus* morph). The ontogenetic curves of table A1.2 confirm the absence of H/W growth through ontogeny for *typus* and *nodosus* morphs. However, ontogenetic curves show a slight increase of H/W (0.2) for *walcotti*.

H/U as seen in table A1.1 seems to be constant through ontogeny only for *nodosus*, while it shows a very slight allometric growth for *typus* and *walcotti* morphs. Tests implemented on the ontogenetic curves (table A1.2), however, all would agree that H/U shows no change in growth in any of the morphs.

Overall for the analysis of the bulk of the sample (table A1.1), *nodosus* appears to show isometric growth in all parameters, with the exception of H and H/D. However, H/D has a p-value of 0.04 that translates to a slope of 0.99 for H considered as a function of D. Analyses performed on the ontogenetic curves, on the other hand, show *nodosus* to be isometric in all parameters with the exception of W, which also shows borderline values (slopes > 0.9). Such borderline values may hint to a distribution that could be shifted in either direction with the addition of more specimens, thus no definitive statements can be made in regard to the growth pattern of the two parameters.

The *walcotti* morph also shows isometric growth of all parameters except for H (thus also H/D), when considering the bulk of the sample (table A1.1). Ontogenetic curves, however, display allometric growth for W (and W/D) only.

Finally, the *typus* morph shows allometric growth for all parameters, though the borderline values of H/D (p-value of 0.02) and of H (slope of 0.998) indicate once again a distribution that could be shifted in either direction with regard to the height parameter (table A1.1). Ontogenetic curves of the best preserved specimens would however seem to support allometric growth of the width parameter only (W and W/D) with all other parameters growing isometrically.

When the analysis is performed on all three morphs taken together as a single group, all parameters seem to show an allometric growth (table A1.1).

Taking everything that has been discussed above into account, it appears that growth analysis yields discordant results between the bulk of the sample and ontogenetic curves.

On the one hand, this is not all too surprising when considering the impact that the large intraspecific variation characteristic of each morph has on each parameter. On the other hand, the impact of preservation biases, of juvenile plasticity and of early or delayed umbilical egression must also not be forgotten.

For this reason, results obtained from the growth analysis performed on ontogenetic curves seem to be the most reliable, as they illustrate the growth of single specimens, for which the impact of preservation biases is well constrained and which are not biased by the effect of intraspecific variation. Ontogenetic curves analysis seem to indicate an isometric growth pattern for all parameters. Only W shows borderline values that would hint to a slight allometric growth. However, W is the parameter most influenced by preservation biases, as crystallization made it sometimes difficult to identify the precise width of the innermost whorls. As such, these values could easily be approximated to an isometric growth.

Table 1.1 to 1.2: for U, H, W, H/W and H/U vs D: slope values of 1 (with p value < 0.05) indicate isometric growth D; if p-value > 0.05, it indicates absence of growth. For H/D, U/D and W/D: p-values < 0.05 allometric growth.

Table A1.1

Parameters (all sections)	typus	walcotti	nodosus	All 3 morphs together
U vs D	Allometric (s+2σ) = 0.90584 Red. χ ² = 0.998366	Isometric (s+2σ) = 1.21939 Red. χ ² = 0.9836066	Isometric (s+2σ) = 1.26841 Red. χ ² = 0.9722222	Allometric (s+2σ) = 0.96285 Red. χ ² = 0.9985994
H vs D	Allometric (s+2σ) = 0.998653 Red. χ ² = 0.9983766	Allometric (s+2σ) = 0.96497 Red. χ ² = 0.9836066	Allometric (s+2σ) = 0.99645 Red. χ ² = 0.9714286	Allometric (s+2σ) = 0.987945 Red. χ ² = 0.9986053
W vs D	Allometric (s+2σ) = 0.9519567 Red. χ ² = 0.9982877	Isometric (s+2σ) = 1.02202 Red. χ ² = 0.9830508	Isometric (s+2σ) = 1.0123 Red. χ ² = 0.96875	Allometric (s+2σ) = 0.95876 Red. χ ² = 0.9985294
H/W vs D	p-value: 6.089e-08- > Allometric (s*2σ) = 0.07527 Slope so tiny = VERY SMALL constant allo growth) Red. χ ² = 0.9982877	p-value: 0.2023 -> no growth(slope = 0) Red. χ ² = 0.9830508	p value = 0.4105 -> no growth(slope = 0) Red. χ ² = 0.9677419	p-value: 0.0001513 -> Allometric (s*2σ) = 0.05741 Red. χ ² = 0.9985272
H/U vs D	Allometric (s+2σ) = 0.16302 Red. χ ² = 0.998366	p-value: 0.03203 Allometric: (s+2σ) = -0.3025 Red. χ ² = 0.9836066	p-value: 0.328 -> no growth (slope = 0) Red. χ ² = 0.9714286	p-value: 0.01993-> Allometric (s*2σ) = 0.10725 Red. χ ² = 0.9985975
U/D vs D	Allometric p-value = 1.752e- 12 Red. χ ² = 0.998366	Isometric: p-value: 0.1379 Red. χ ² = 0.9836066	Isometric p-value = 0.444 Red. χ ² = 0.9722222	Allometric p-value = 0.0001481 Red. χ ² = 0.9985994
H/D vs D	Allometric p-value = 0.02414 Red. χ ² = 0.9983766	Allometric: p-value = 3.73e-06 Red. χ ² = 0.9836066	Allometric p-value: 0.04069 Red. χ ² = 0.9714286	Allometric p-value = 1.722e- 05 Red. χ ² = 0.9986053
W/D vs D	Allometric p-value = 4.261e- 13 Red. χ ² = 0.9982079	Isometric p-value: 0.2911 Red. χ ² = 0.9830508	Isometric p-value: 0.08674 Red. χ ² = 0.96875	Allometric p-value = 6.063e- 12 Red. χ ² = 0.9985294

Table A1.2

Growth of ontogenetic curves: coloured are the parameters that show allometric growth; in red titles are the 2 specimens (NPQ1.1; HT17) with the poorest fit of the linear model.

All species show isometric growth of all parameters except W.

H/U shows no growth. H/W shows growth only for H. walcotti.

	G22 H.typus	HT18 H.typus	NPQ1.1 H.typus	HT17 H.typus	WIL6.3 H.typus	B3.1 H.walcotti	HT144 H.walcotti	G89 H.nodosus	G91 H.nodosus	G28 H.nodosus
U	(s+2σ)= 1.342 Red. χ²= 0.833333	(s+2σ)= 1.04729 Red. χ²= 0.8	(s+2σ)= 1.358 Red. χ²= 0.666666	(s+2σ)= 1.5298 Red. χ²= 0.75	(s+2σ)= 1.2419 Red. χ²= 0.833333	(s+2σ)= 0.9998 Red. χ²= 0.833333	(s+2σ)= 1.08613 Red. χ²= 0.8	(s+2σ)= 1.22677 Red. χ²= 0.857143	(s+2σ)= 1.4457 Red. χ²= 0.833333	(s+2σ)= 1.5298 Red. χ²= 0.833333
H	(s+2σ)= 1.0498 Red. χ²= 0.833333 3	(s+2σ)= 0.9951 Red. χ²= 0.8	(s+2σ)= 0.95537 Red. χ²= 0.75	(s+2σ)= 0.96071 Red. χ²= 0.75	(s+2σ)= 1.02083 Red. χ²= 0.833333 3	(s+2σ)= 1.08309 Red. χ²= 0.833333	(s+2σ)= 1.11272 Red. χ²= 0.8	(s+2σ)= 1.00136 Red. χ²= 0.857143	(s+2σ)= 1.03065 Red. χ²= 0.833333	(s+2σ)= 1.24876 Red. χ²= 0.833333
W	(s+2σ)= 0.90376 Red. χ²= 0.833333	(s+2σ)= 0.98671 Red. χ²= 0.8	(s+2σ)= 1.0521 Red. χ²= 0.75	(s+2σ)= 1.00357 Red. χ²= 0.75	(s+2σ)= 0.95943 Red. χ²= 0.833333	(s+2σ)= 0.876245 Red. χ²= 0.833333	(s+2σ)= 0.90512 Red. χ²= 0.8	(s+2σ)= 0.94997 Red. χ²= 0.857143	(s+2σ)= 0.95591 Red. χ²= 0.833333	(s+2σ)= 0.96379 Red. χ²= 0.833333
H/ W	P value = 0.1137 = no growth Red. χ²= 0.833333 3	P value = 0.1367= no growth Red. χ²= 0.8	P value = 0.2792= no growth Red. χ²= 0.75	P value = 0.7906= no growth Red. χ²= 0.75	P value = 0.6592 = no growth Red. χ²= 0.833333 3	P value = 0.008413 (s+2σ)= 0.23538= Red. χ²= 0.833333	P value = 0.003885 (s+2σ)= 0.25116 Red. χ²= 0.8	P value = 0.0697 = no growth Red. χ²= 0.857143	P value = 0.4633 = no growth Red. χ²= 0.833333	P value = 0.05818 = no growth Red. χ²= 0.833333
H/U	P value = 0.291 = no growth Red. χ²= 0.833333 3	P value = 0.6003 = no growth Red. χ²= 0.8	P value = 0.6365= no growth Red. χ²= 0.666666	P value = 0.1396= no growth Red. χ²= 0.666666	P value = 0.6592 = no growth Red. χ²= 0.833333 3	P value = 0.1368= no growth Red. χ²= 0.833333	P value = 0.3771 = no growth Red. χ²= 0.8	P value = 0.1489 = no growth Red. χ²= 0.857143	P value = 0.4706 = no growth Red. χ²= 0.833333	P value = 0.5146 = no growth Red. χ²= 0.833333
U/D	P value = 0.291 Red. χ²= 0.833333 3	P value = 0.2381 Red. χ²= 0.8	P value = 0.9906 Red. χ²= 0.666666 7	P value = 0.1983 Red. χ²= 0.666666 7	P value = 0.8739 Red. χ²= 0.833333 3	P value = 0.1018 Red. χ²= 0.833333	P value = 0.3493 Red. χ²= 0.8	P value = 0.2084 Red. χ²= 0.857143	P value = 0.5538 Red. χ²= 0.833333	P value = 0.6956 Red. χ²= 0.833333
H/D	P value = 0.4238 Red. χ²= 0.833333	P value = 0.09791 Red. χ²= 0.8	P value = 0.02643 = allom. Red. χ²= 0.75	P value = 0.04139= allom. Red. χ²= 0.75	P value = 0.2246 = Red. χ²= 0.833333	P value = 0.6261 Red. χ²= 0.833333	P value = 0.5611 Red. χ²= 0.8	P value = 0.102 Red. χ²= 0.857143	P value = 0.2623 = Red. χ²= 0.833333	P value = 0.2944 = allometri c Red. χ²= 0.833333
W/ D	P value = 0.000549 5 = allom Red. χ²= 0.833333	P value = 0.08998 Red. χ²= 0.8	P value = 0.5204 Red. χ²= 0.75	P value = 0.1519 Red. χ²= 0.75	P value = 0.004683 = allom. Red. χ²= 0.833333	P value = 2.204e- 05 = allom. Red. χ²= 0.833333	P value = 0.008291 = allom. Red. χ²= 0.8	P value = 0.01795 = allom Red. χ²= 0.75	P value = 0.01879 = allom. Red. χ²= 0.833333	P value = 0.02228 = allom. Red. χ²= 0.833333

3. Clustering methods

Optimal number of clusters (2D) - different methods

Figure A1. PCA analysis: Different cluster methods are used to identify the number of clusters that might be present in the data. An average of 2 recognizable clusters can be assumed.

Figure A2: Results obtained via a Procrustes for the landmark-sample ontogenetic dataset. A) Overlay of landmark point configuration for all ontogenetic stages of landmark-sampled specimens. B) The mean shape configuration for the pooled ontogenetic stages, landmark-sampled dataset.

Fig A3. Outlines based geomorphometry. A) Superposition of the shape of all ontogenetic stages of all specimens; here as well no outliers are to be observed. B) Mean shape based on the shape space of fig A.

Supplementary Material: Chapter II

The late Smithian (Early Triassic) ammonoid fauna of the *Anasibirites* beds of north-east Nevada

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“The late Smithian (Early Triassic) ammonoid fauna of the *Anasibirites* beds of north-east Nevada”**Supplementary material**

Anasibirites from SIL119

Definitions in the legend describe the morphological grouping made according to the observed strength of ornamentation, to check for the presence of multiple species within the sample.

SIL119 all specimens

Fig S1: *Anasibirites multififormis*. Scatterplot of all specimens from SIL 119. The morphological groups correspond to the different degrees of ornamentation observed within the sample. This morphological grouping was implemented in order to check for the presence of multiple species within the sample. No difference among the three groups can be spotted for any of the considered parameters, except for a lower U and U/D values and higher H/U for the weaker ornamented specimens, which conforms to Buckman’s Law of Covariation.

Fig.S2: *Anasibirites multiformis* from SIL119. Boxplots of the three ornamentation-based morphological groups for: A) all specimens B) juveniles with a diameter < than 37.7 mm C) specimens with a diameter > 37.7 mm. The breaking point for the size classes was found through piecewise linear regression (PLR) with a lin-log scale. Boxplots show the increase of umbilical diameter (U/D) and decrease of involution degree (H/W) with coarser ornamentation as predicted by Buckmann's Law of Covariation. H/D and W/D mostly overlap.

FIGS3: *Anasibirites multiformis* from SIL119. Linear discriminant analysis implemented on A) all specimens; B) only juvenile specimens with diameter smaller than 37.7 mm; C) specimens with diameter larger than 37.7 mm.

Fig. S4: Measurements of *Eowasatchites arcuatus* from CS33A. Colours refer to the different strength of ornamentation observed, while symbols distinguish the specimens on which ribbing on the venter was observed, from those characterised by a smooth venter.

Neither the strength of the ornamentation nor the presence or absence of ventral ribbing allow the distinction of any groups among the specimens. Specimens showing ornamentation on the shell (blue, light blue and red colours) generally have a lower H/W and H/U ratio and higher W/D ratio. This indicates that these specimens are both more depressed and more involute compared to the smooth ones, thus conforming to the predictions of Buckman's Law of covariation. From these scatterplots it can also be observed that ornamentation, i.e., the development of tubercles on the mid-flanks, generally starts at a diameter of 30 mm, with only rare exceptions below 25 mm.

Eowasatchites arcuatus from CS33A: log scale

Fig S5: Measurements of *Eowasatchites arcuatus* from CS33A in logarithmic scale. In accordance with the results obtained through linear regressions, these plots show that H follows a clear allometric growth, while both W and U follow an isometric growth.

Fig. S6: Linear discriminant analysis of *Eowasatchites arcuatus*. Colours indicate morphological groups based on the strength of shell ornamentation.

Fig.S7: Boxplot of *Eowasatchites arcuatus* from CS33A. The more strongly ornamented the specimens are, the more depressed (low H/W) and the more evolute (high U/D) they become, in agreement with Buckamnn's Law of covariation.

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